

Journal of EcoAgriTourism

Bulletin of Agri-ecology, Agri-food, Bioengineering and Agritourism

Vol. 15 (2019), No 2 (39)

Journal of EcoAgriTourism
ISSN: 1844-8577

Journal of EcoAgriTourism is a follow up, by translation in
English of "Revista de EcoAgroTurism"
ISSN 1841-642X, first issued in 2005

ISSN: 1844-8577

EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

Department of Ecobiotechnologies and Equipment for Food and Agriculture

Transilvania University of Braşov
Bd. Eroilor nr. 29, 500036, Braşov,
Tel & Fax: 0268-415326, Tel:
0268-413000/161

Journal's Director

Prof. Romulus GRUIA Ph. D.

Editor-in-Chief

Prof. eng. Liviu GACEU Ph. D. Habil.

Scientific Board

Assoc. Prof. Ganesh Bora, Ph.D., Mississippi State University, United States;
Prof. Maria Isabel Bernuga, Ph.D., University Castilla La Mancha, Spain;
Prof. Mark Shamtsyan Ph.D. State Institute of Technology, St. Petersburg, Rusia;
Prof. Miklos Herdon, Ph.D. Hab., University of Debrecen, Hungary;
Prof. Ray F. Iunius, Ph.D., Director Business Development SA, Switzerland;
Prof. Stefan Stefanov, Ph.D., University of Food Technologies, Plovdiv, Bulgaria;
Prof. Valerii Sukmanov, Ph.D. Hab., University of Donuet, Ukraine;
Prof. Werner Hofacker, Ph.D., University of Applied Sciences, Konstanz, Germany;

Technical Board

Simona SOICA
Oana Bianca OPREA
Raisa SAMOILA
Raducu MICU
Bernadett DENES
Cristina RUSU
Nicoleta TINEA
Andrei APARASCHIVEI
Amalia ADAM
Luiza VOICILA

Published by:

Transilvania University Press
500091 Brasov, B-dul Iuliu Maniu 41 A
Tel: 0268-476050
Fax: 0268-476051
E-mail: editura@unitbv.ro
Co-editor: Romanian Society for Information Technology in Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism
www.rosita.ro/jeat
ISSN: 1844-8577

Center for Biodiversity in Agriculture and Forestry INCE/Romanian Academy-Research point ICDT/Transilvania University of Brasov
Romanian Society for Information Technology in Agriculture, Food, Environment and Tourism (ROSITA)

The Bio-Harmonism of „Agriculture - Tourism - Environment” Complex Systems

As we may observe, we live in a tumultuous historical period that gives birth to question marks and always looks for solutions. To understand reality presupposes to evolve in the manner we approach it. A direction in this respect is also to analyze the complex systems where we find interconnections with economic, but also socio-cultural value specific to the relations of certain multidisciplinary activities between agriculture and tourism, both in relation to environment. These interconnections, which in fact offer the profile of our publication („*EcoAgroTourism*”) may be deeply understood by new conceptual approaches. One of these ones comes from the **Theory of Bio-Harmonism**, but also from its applications sustained by **the Bioharmonist Ideology**.

We essentially refer to the approach that takes into consideration the ***Living Planet model*** as a „unity in diversity”, that shapes an integrated concept and an action manner that ideationally puts man and society back. Man may direct himself towards a ***superior conscience level***, and the society may institutionally change, respectively, beyond technological and legislative change, there is open the path towards ***the change of institutional culture***.

The analyzed fields, in the integration dynamics, impose change on multiple plans (both of consciousness, and of institutional culture). For an evolution that takes into consideration the 21st century provocations, there are necessary studies that, taking into consideration more and more factors of influence may use methods and techniques with harmonization effects of these factors, after the great complexity model of Nature, Living (bios) and biologic-informational Life. The understanding of agriculture, tourism and environment on the bases of ***the processes of bioharmonization*** appeals to methods, principles, field policies and specific strategies, having as specificity a certain type of analyses and synthesis. Briefly, the analyses is made taking into account the „minced” and deepened elements, and the synthesis, taking into account the multiple integrations in the interface of agriculture with tourism and, respectively, with natural environment. Their bioharmonization will have benefic effects, but also the potential to pass towards systems of superior level with maximized effectiveness and efficacy.

Director of the publication,
Full Prof. Romulus GRUIA,
PhD, PhD supervisor

SUMMARY

Editorial : <i>The Bio-Harmonism of „Agriculture - Tourism - Environment” Complex Systems – GRUIA Romulus</i>	
5	<i>IDENTIFICATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS RELATED TO THE LEVEL OF BIODIVERSITY TO DETERMINE URBAN SUSTAINABILITY OF TOURISM. CASE STUDY: Riobamba-Ecuador</i> C. M. VERDUGO, O. F. BALSECA
13	<i>ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGY, CONCEPT AND APPLICATIONS IN FOOD (outlined presentation)</i> R. GRUIA, L. GACEU
20	<i>RESEARCH REGARDING THE IMPORTANCE OF WOOD BIOMASS</i> GH.C. SPIRCHEZ, A.LUNGULEASA, L. GACEU
24	<i>STUDY CONCERNING BIO-HARMONISM PARADIGM, WITH APPLICATIONS TO THE EVOLUTION OF AGRITOURISTIC MANAGEMENT</i> R. GRUIA
31	<i>COMPARATIVE STUDY REGARDING THE ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF EUCALYPTUS, MENTHA PIPERITA AND HIPPOPHAE RHAMNOIDES - A REVIEW</i> N.R. SAMOILĂ, L. GACEU
38	<i>EXAMPLES OF „BIOHARMONIZATION” OF THE REALITY COMPONENTS, ARGUMENTS FOR THE NEW BIO-HARMONIST IDEOLOGY</i> R. GRUIA
46	<i>RECOVERY OF SOME VEGETABLE BYPRODUCTS WITH PHITOTERAPEUTICAL PROPERTIES FOR NEW DIETARY SUPPLEMENT</i> ANDREEA COZEA, GRUIA ROMULUS, NATALITA BORDEI, MIHAELA NEAGU, MARIANA POPESCU
50	<i>A METHODOLOGY FOR EVALUATION OF AGRITOURISM POTENTIAL. CASE STUDY: OLTINA VILLAGE</i> M. POPESCU
55	<i>ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA STRAINS FROM GOAT MILK FOR POTENTIAL USE IN THE PRODUCTION OF YOGURT</i> C. POPOVICI, M. TIȚA, A. CARTASEV, R. BRINZA, N. BOGDAN
67	<i>EATING OUT GLUTEN-FREE – RESULTS OF A SURVEY</i> T. CSAPÓNÉ RISKÓ, B. BENYOVSZKI
78	<i>FOOD WASTE AND FOOD LOSS PHENOMENON – NEW SYSTEMIC APPROACHES</i> C. S. IORGA, O. M. DUMITRU, A. STOICA, C. M. NICOLESCU

85	<i>FOOD SAFETY FOR MOUNTAIN PRODUCTS – STRATEGIES, POLICIES, ACTORS</i> <i>L. GACEU</i>
89	<i>OPTIMIZATION OF IMAGE ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES FOR QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF WHEAT BREAD WITH GRAPE SEED FLOUR SUBSTITUTION</i> <i>O. B. OPREA, L. GACEU</i>

IDENTIFICATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS RELATED TO THE LEVEL OF BIODIVERSITY TO DETERMINE URBAN SUSTAINABILITY OF TOURISM. CASE STUDY: Riobamba-Ecuador

C. M. VERDUGO^{1*}

O. F. BALSECA

¹Escuela Superior Politécnica de Chimborazo, Ecuador

*Corresponding author: catalina.verdugo@unitbv.ro

Abstract: *The incidence of Sustainable City Indicators turns out to be a key element in environmental management for the cities, which is why the survey of a comprehensive baseline of sustainability indicators in the city of Riobamba, Ecuador is undertaken, as the continuation of a ranking of cities sustainable, among which data from Quito, Guayaquil and Cuenca are the subject of a previous study (Verdugo, 2016). The measurement was made in the 5 urban parishes of Riobamba, given that the information is scarce. Eleven variables were collected based on the previous realization of the environmental component diagnosis in a first phase based on the review and analysis of other systems of global, regional and local indicators; Afterwards, it was determined that the areas to be studied will be initially, public space and georeferenced vegetation cover and finally those variables that are decisive in the level of sustainability of the city were weighted to issue subsequent recommendations to this reality.*

Keywords: *Indicators, Environmental, urban Sustainability, Riobamba, urban biodiversity*

1. Introduction

During the last decades in the field of environmental management, important efforts have been made to promote environmental indicators and sustainable development. At the end of the eighties, Canada and some European countries began this process; For its part, in Latin America, the first environmental indicators were assembled in the mid-nineties (Economic Commission for Latin America, 2007).

The State Coordinator of Coffee Producers of Oaxaca, (CEPCO, 2013), reveals that since the introduction of the idea of sustainable development in the eighties and its subsequent conceptualization as a harmonious triangle between economic growth, social equity and environmental conservation, academic discussions have increased significantly around the path to follow to achieve sustainable development, in the same way, questions have been raised about the main causes of environmental deterioration and global phenomena that deepen the economic, social and environmental gaps global, regional and / or local scale.

Organization of the United Nations, in the Conference on Housing and Sustainable Urban

Development Habitat III, held in the city of Quito in October 2016, essential parameters for the identification of factors that directly influence the investigative work. It states that the main indicators related to sustainable development have focused basically on the environmental factor of sustainability, that is, environmental indicators have been the most commonly used to assess the state of the planet, as well as to observe the differences between the different regions, countries and cities. However, at the international level, some indexes have been developed that seek to integrate the various aspects of sustainable development, such as the Prosperity Index (Habitat III, 2016).

In Ecuador, the Ministry of the Environment has been working since 2010 on a System of Environmental Indicators that includes information for environmental issues such as: Atmosphere and Climate, Soils, Ecosystems, Marine and Coastal Resources, among others. However, within this system there are no indicators to assess the state of the environment at the municipal level, in the same way that there is no information about environmental performance in cities. (MAE, 2010).

Several cities participated on behalf of Ecuador in the construction of the Green Cities

Index for the Latin American region. According to the data obtained at the time of the study, the city of Quito is located at a "Medium" level regarding its environmental sustainability, within the context of the 17 participating cities (Economist Intelligence Unit, 2010).

Within this panorama, this research proposes to identify information that will allow the future to determine indicators for environmental sustainability linked to the increase of biodiversity in the city of Riobamba, which will ecologically describe the state of sustainability in which it is located and allow to route a integral conservation process for the future.

2. Objectives

The main objective of this study is to: *Assess environmental indicators related to the level of biodiversity for the urban sustainability of Riobamba* and this was possible developing the following specific objectives: **a)** Validate environmental indicators related to biodiversity for determine the level of urban sustainability; **b)** Generate a database using geo-information in the urban environment about *public space* and *vegetation coverage*; **c)** Apply a data matrix to determine the level of sustainability.

3. Materials and methods

The analytical-descriptive method and field observation were used, through the analysis of secondary information from bibliographic sources and the collection of primary source data through participatory research between the Higher Polytechnic School of Chimborazo and the Municipality of Riobamba, whose objectives were fulfilled as follows:

1. Validate environmental indicators related to the increase of biodiversity to determine the level of urban sustainability in Riobamba

The diagnosis of the Environmental component in the increase of Riobamba biodiversity was made following the parameters:

- Access of citizens to green spaces;
- Compensation to waterproofing and sealing: Permeability index;
- Provision of trees in the public space;
- Green runners;
- A second layer of biodiversity in height;
- A second layer of biodiversity in height: greening of facades.

Taking as a starting point situations related to the analysis of urban biodiversity developed in different cities of Latin America and Europe, a compilation of essential factors that allow to know the reality of the city was carried out.

a. Selection and classification of indicators

The Urban Sustainability Indicators Plan is an instrument that responds to a certain more sustainable city model with the intention of quantitatively and qualitatively assessing the urbanization process of the city of Riobamba from an integral and systemic point of view with sustainability criteria.

Taking into account the aforementioned, the experiences of the countries that have carried out the studies on the urban biodiversity aspect have been used as an initial point to be analyzed and compared with the reality of the city of Riobamba.

In different cities or organizations such as; city of Vitoria-Gasteiz of Spain, the City Council of Malaga jointly with the European Union with the URBAN INITIATIVE URBAN SUSTAINABILITY INDICATORS, United Nations in conjunction with ECLAC in the project Application of urban sustainability indicators to social housing, Network of Networks of Sustainable Local Development, with the help of BCN Ecologia, the Government of Spain and the Special Plan of Indicators of Environmental Sustainability of the Urban Development Activity of Seville, are the cities that carry out indicators of sustainability to urban biodiversity.

b. Discrimination of the obtained indicators

Using the information of cities that have applied the indicators for biodiversity, having a total of 24 indicators of sustainability, we have proceeded to the verification in the field if the indicators can be adapted to the city, and if the information required by the indicators exists in the GADM Riobamba, otherwise they have discriminated from the table, thus being the first indicators of the city.

The indicators were adapted to the reality of the city of Riobamba in order to have coherent results using the methodology consisting of secondary information collection, interviews, observation, field work, which are used by Spain, the UN, Ecology BCN, ECLAC and the cities that are in the process of analyzing sustainability,

the same ones that when carrying out the studies only adapt the weights or update them to improve biodiversity in the urban area of the main cities.

c. National and international observations

Through the consultation of the international observations of the World Organization of the Departure (2010), the laws that govern within the Ecuadorian territory and of the competences of the GADM through the (COTAD 2016) the Territorial Organization of the GADM (municipality) Riobamba, will help us to observe if in the city, what is established by international observations is complied with as per the laws.

2. To fulfill the second objective: Generate a database using geoinformation in the urban area about public space and vegetation coverage

- Field trips were made to collect the geographic data with the GPS.
- Through the information obtained from GADM Riobamba and ESPOCH's forestry school, the geographically referenced data were integrated, edited, analyzed and incorporated.
- The GIS (Geographical Information System) was used as a tool, by means of information on the location and representation on maps

3. To fulfill the third objective: Apply a matrix to determine the level of sustainability

- The selected indicators were transferred to the Office Excel 2013 software, in which the degree of compliance with the criteria can subsequently be measured.
- For the data matrix as explained by (Walter, 2013) and according to the needs that this work requires, the first results are generated that show the sustainability of biodiversity in the city of Riobamba.
- The weights and statistical formulas that were used are those that have been handled in the aforementioned projects that will help measure the sustainability of the city of Riobamba, at the same time observe the existing shortcomings within the urban area.
- Eleven the results of the environmental measurement related to the increase in biodiversity in the parks of the Riobamba canton are obtained, the results will be systematized in order to discern and identify the sustainable areas

where the greatest weakness or deficit is found. in the fulfillment of the weights.

e. Surveys were applied to know the satisfaction of the urban community on the existing parks in the city, determining a representative sample based on the formula of finite populations.

$$n = \frac{N(P*Q)}{(N-1) \left(\frac{e}{z} \right)^2 (P*Q)}$$

Where:

- n: Sample size
 N: Studio Universe
 P: Probability of occurrence (50%)
 Q: Probability of non-occurrence (50%)
 e: Margin of error (5%)
 z: Level of trust (1,96)

4. Results and discussion

The investigation was conducted in the city of Riobamba located in the province of Chimborazo, in the central inter-Andean area of Ecuador. Coordinates in UTM, Zone 17S, DATUM WGS 84

X: 759607

Y: 9814770

Altitud: 2754m.s.n.m. (Fuente: Cartografía base del Instituto Geográfico Militar. 2002).

After analyzing the environmental indicators from various sources at the global, regional and local levels, it was determined that the following are those of greater adaptability to the reality of the city of Riobamba, especially to the vision that its population and local authorities have on environmental sustainability.

Due to the fact that the project has been compiling environmental indicators from 2016 to 2019, the amount of information on sustainability indicators, not only environmental, has become too large a repository to be presented in a single work. summarizes the indicators related to biodiversity measured in this specific work that has served to feed the database of the large *project Measuring the sustainability indicators (economic, social, environment, culture, technology and politics) of Riobamba* and its influence on activities such as tourism and others.

Sustainability of the city of Riobamba Interpretation (Annex 1 and 2)

a) Once the indicators were determined, we proceeded to assign percentage values to each one, considering as the maximum value, that is, 100%, the beginning of the value at which the "high" category begins; With the results obtained, it can be seen that the sustainability of Riobamba is in the category "Medium" corroborating the information in figure 1, it can be seen that there are low indicators such as the allocation of trees per hectare and the buildings of the historic center that comply with the greening of the facades, as average indicators the percentage of parks built that are not adequately cared for by the citizens and the municipality, the percentage of impermeability in green areas and of recreation, the percentage of tree species in the area, which are found in parks and recreation areas and the percentage of green corridors allocated to the total area of the urban area of the Riobamba canton; and high indicators being the amount in m² of green areas and recreation per

inhabitant, the percentage of buildable in relation to the total area of the urban areas of the canton, the number of trees that are considered as heritage within the historic center of the city and the percentage of green coverage in green areas and recreational areas, which allows Riobamba to be identified as a city that in its territorial planning has considered issues of sustainability in its biodiversity, however, there are environmental factors that must be improved so that it can meet with the necessary criteria to be considered as a city that applies international standards to be called "sustainable city" at the level of biodiversity within the urban area.

b) After applying the formula of the sample it was determined that the ideal number of surveys applied to the population is a number of 400, to know among other things its perseverance on the state of the environment of its city and the needs of green spaces for recreation.

Below is a summary of the main questions asked to the citizenship.

Table 2. Summary of questions asked to the citizen of Riobamba

QUESTIONS ASKED TO CITIZENS IN RIOBAMBA				
Question	Percentage			
	YES		NO	
1. Do you think the amount of parks and green spaces in Riobamba are sufficient to supply the demand and satisfaction of its inhabitants?	36%		64%	
2. How do you consider the state of conservation of parks/ green spaces in Riobamba?	Very good 1%	Good 27%	Regular 61%	Bad 11%
3. What do you think should be implemented in the parks and green spaces?	Trees 48%	bushes 47%	herbaceous 5%	
4. What do you think should be implemented in the parks and green spaces of the city to improve its appearance in buildings?	Sport courts 29%	Playgrounds 42%	entertainment scenarios 30%	
5. What material do you think should be implemented in the parks and green spaces to improve children's games?	Wood 33%	iron 17%	mixed 50%	
6. Are you agree that musical, cultural and sportive events perform in these parks?	Yes 92%		No 8%	
7. Your neighborhood has a suitable park	Yes 33%		No 67%	
8. Do you consider the parks/green spaces in your neighborhood are enough to satisfy the entire community?	Yes 21%		No 79%	
9. How do you consider the state of conservation of parks and green spaces in your neighborhood?	Very good 1%	Good 22%	Regular 50%	Bad 28%
10. Do you know any municipal ordinance or regulations about caring parks and the sanctions that imply their carelessness?	Yes 22%		No 78%	
11. Do you know if Riobamba can be classified as a sustainable city in relation to the parameters established in the Habitat III conference?	Yes 24%		No 76%	
12. Do you believe that projects should be carried out to improve the states of conservation, use, tourism and aesthetics of the parks and green spaces of the city?	Yes 92%		No 8%	

c) In addition, the main green areas of the city were georeferenced and those in a state of deterioration, among other indicators that will be presented in subsequent works (Fig.2, 3, Annex).

d) Finally, a series of improvement recommendations were delivered and socialized to the Environmental Management of the municipality of Riobamba, where in the future it is intended to publish material for the population of Riobamba to learn about this work and its possible collaboration in environmental improvement strategies for the city.

- Update biannually the cadastre of parks, green areas and recreational areas of the city of Riobamba, this in function of the rapid population growth of the city.
- Socialize the existing ordinances so that the population public employees become aware of their obligations and rights over the use of green and recreational areas.
- Insert in the school and school curricula the chair of environmental education to develop in the children and young people the love for their local resource and their own well-being.

Coordinate actions with the public, private and community sectors of Riobamba to organize family events where the psycho-physical benefits of the use of green and recreational areas are emphasized.

Conclusions

At the end of the review of both local and international indicators, it was possible to obtain 6 criteria and 10 indicators, of which only 1 indicator is worked by the Municipality of Riobamba corresponding to green areas, the rest of the indicators are from experiences carried out in other cities of the world, that allowed to know the reality of Riobamba in its biodiversity.

Using the geoinformation technique, 229 areas of green and recreational areas were obtained, distributed as follows: 29 green areas (13%), 112 parks (48%), 25 sports courts (11%) and 63 lots vacant lots (28%), with a total of 119.58 hectares representing 4.08% of the total area of the city.

With the results obtained from the baseline, 6 maps were represented with the relevant information of the indicators; type of building, existing green areas in the city, state of green areas, impermeability of green areas and parks that have trees. Through the application of the data matrix it was determined that the level of sustainability of the Riobamba city is at 61.97%, identifying itself as a degree of environmental sustainability at the "Medium" level of biodiversity.

The results obtained from the statistical analysis of satisfaction of the citizenship of the city shows that more than 80% of them do not agree with the works carried out by the GADM Riobamba due to the lack of importance given to the parks and areas green of the city.

Acknowledgements

A special recognition to Mario Arias.

References

1. Asamblea Nacional del Ecuador. (2016). Artículo 488, Código de Ordenamiento Territorial, Autonomía y descentralización. Quito – Ecuador;
2. Ayuntamiento de Málaga. (2009). Indicadores de la Sostenibilidad. Spain
3. Ciudades más verdes en América latina y el Caribe. ORGANIZACIÓN DE LAS NACIONES UNIDAS PARA LA ALIMENTACIÓN Y LA AGRICULTURA. 2014. Roma, pp. 50-53;
4. Conferencia Habitat III. La nueva agenda urbana. 2016. Conferencia de la ONU sobre la vivienda y el desarrollo urbano sostenible. Quito-Ecuador, pp. 20-27;
5. Coordinadora Estatal de Productores de Café de Oaxaca (CEPCO). Video 7:51min. Observatorio TV. Publicado 14 de marzo de 2016. Recuperado el 10 de enero de 2017;
6. Manual del Sistema de indicadores ambientales. Sistema Único de información Ambiental (SUIA). 2014. Ministerio de Ambiente de Ecuador, pp. 22-30;
7. Quiroga, R. 2007. Indicadores ambientales y de desarrollo sostenible: avances y perspectivas para América Latina y el Caribe. Manuales. Serie 55. CEPAL-ONU. Diciembre 2007. Santiago de Chile, Chile, pp. 15-21;
8. <http://www.igm.gob.ec/work/files/downloads/mapafisico.html>, recovered february 08, 2019;
9. https://repositorio.cepal.org/bitstream/handle/1362/5498/1/S0700589_es, recovered october 25, 2018;
10. <http://osse.org.mx/> Observatorio del sector social de la economía, recovered dec. 12, 2018;
11. <http://habitat3.org/wp-content/uploads/Brochure-Espa%C3%B1ol-Web-final.pdf>, recovered december 20, 2016.
12. http://suia.ambiente.gob.ec/documentos?p_p_id=20&p_p_lifecycle=0&p_p_state=normal&p_p_mode=view&p_p_col_id=column-1&p_p_col_pos=1&p_p_col_count=2&_20_struts_action=%2Fdocument_library%2Fview&_20_folderId=185876, recovered april 19, 2019.
13. <http://www.fao.org/ag/agp/greenercities/pdf/GCLAC/Ciudades-mas-verdes-America-Latina-Caribe.pdf>, recovered march 15, 2019.

Annex 1. Table 1. Evaluation matrix for the sustainability of the city of Riobamba

FOLLOW UP AND CONTROL							
SUMMARY OF BIODIVERSITY EVALUATION IN RIOBAMBA							
CRITERIA	Indicator	Current value	weighing	General weighting			
				Low	Medium	High	%
Access of citizens to spacesgreen	Quantity in m2 of green areas and recreation per inhabitant	8,18	Medium	0	1	0	68,20
	Percentage of parks built, not cared for by citizens and the Municipality of Riobamba.	58,08	Medium	0	1	0	41,92
Compensation to the waterproofing and sealing: Index of permeability	Percentage of buildability in relation to the total area of urban areas of Riobamba	27,52	Medium	0	1	0	72,49
	Permeability of impermeability in green areas and recreation	21,01	High	0	0	1	78,99
Endowment of trees in the public space	Asignación de árboles por hectárea	10	Low	1	0	0	4,92
	Number of trees that are considered as heritage within the historic center of the city	66	Medium	0	1	0	94,29
	Percentage of tree species in the area, found in parks and recreation areas	61,58	Medium	0	1	0	89,24
Green paths	Percentage of green corridors allocated to the total area of the urban area of Riobamba	14,85	Low	1	0	0	49,50
Percentage of green coverage in green areas and recreation	Percentage of green coverage in green and recreational areas	78,99	High	0	0	1	112,85
A second layer of biodiversity in height	Percentage of buildings in the historic center that meet the greening of facades	10,67	Low	1	0	0	7,73
	General sustainability	Total weighting		3	5	2	61,97

Note: Mario Arias. 2016

Fig. 1. General sustainability of Riobamba

Note: Mario Arias. 2016

Fig. 2. Green and recreational areas in Riobamba

Note: Mario Arias. 2016 and inventory of parks of Riobamba conducted by the School of Forestry ESPOCH. 2012.

Fig. 3. Situation of green areas and recreation in urban Riobamba

Note: Mario Arias. 2016 and inventory of parks of Riobamba conducted by the School of Forestry ESPOCH. 2012.

ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGY, CONCEPT AND APPLICATIONS IN FOOD (outlined presentation)

R. GRUIA^{1,2}, L. GACEU^{1,2}

¹Transilvania University of Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism

²CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy;

*Corresponding author: ecotec@unitbv.ro

Abstract: *The paper emphasizes a preoccupation of large actuality in the agri-food system, namely the multidisciplinary field from the alimentation branch, respectively the eco-biotechnology one. There is underlined a new technologic re-orientation modality in alimentation, that represents a superior level, passing from the green economy ecotechnologies to the last decade biotechnologies, in order that nowadays, but especially in prospect, we may talk about a bioharmonization between these ones, making up innovating technologies of „ecologic biotechnologies” or, referring to food, nutritional ecobiotechnologies. There are described, by images (slide type) applications of the model based on modern techniques of extracting bioactive substances from vegetal or animal resources. There is presented a technologic flow of a laboratory with applications for eco-bio-products from vegetal resources with gradual health generating potential in function of fulfilled criteria and respectively as validated health generating foods, i.e. bioproductive products with nutraceutical frequent utilizations.*

Keywords: *alimentation, eco-biotechnologies, food, nutritive extracts, nutraceuticals.*

1. Introduction

Today reality regarding **the alimentary act** emphasizes both the importance of the production quantity, and especially its quality. The quality is to be found both in case of primary foods (agricultural ones), such as „eco” aliments too (i.e. ecological or organic ones), or in case of industrial foods of first processing or processed as „bio” composite foods (i.e. based on *receipts* and „smooth” technologies in order to preserve the bioactive components), and in case of complex aliments (i.e. mixed dishes and drinks from excellence cuisine).

The conceptual evolution from the last decades, due to scientific revolutions on multiple plans, leads to new discoveries of a great relevance in the large alimentation sphere too. There are directions that sustain the food security also by the so called **smart food** (high quality aliments with health generating potential/ systemically bioharmonized food with minimum environment impact). These aspects demand to know the main

directions that characterize this problem, namely: *ecotechnology* and *biotechnology*.

Generically speaking, **Ecotechnology** (the Technology Eco) refers to green technologies necessary to reduce the impact upon environment. They include preoccupations, as for example: reduction of carbon dioxide emissions, energy conservation and utilization of energy salvation devices, utilization of electric energy for data center, tree plantation and herb plantation around and above main centers. In the field of food production, the most known direction is sustainable agriculture (ecological, organic, based on bioeconomy principles) that mainly stipulates to avoid use of chemical fertilizers, pesticides etc., and to use organic fertilizers and biological and biotechnical methods and means to fight against pests.

On the other hand, **Biotechnology** is a new scientific branch based on biology, whose basic aim is to use in technique microorganisms or derived products from these ones, of cultures of vegetal and animal cells in order to produce useful substances in agriculture and in food industry, pharmaceutical industry, etc., for the

human activity benefit. More concrete, from the perspective of food processing, the idea is to get aliments with improved properties, based on biological, chemical and physical processes in food production and transformation. We especially refer to the direction of *minimum processing* and, in general of technologies that allow to preserve components in active state (i.e. enzymes, phytohormones, vitamins etc. to remain bioactive, so that we may usually speak about „living foods”).

Trying a **ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGY** definition, from theoretic perspective this one represents **the bioharmonized connection of the “Ecotechnology - Biotechnology” Axis**, respectively of the specific principles, ecological and biological techniques and methods, which leads to the integrated model: „*environment – ecologic paradigm – biological revolution – smart food product*”. From the pragmatic perspective, eco-biotechnology represents the

relations between the parameters of the technological civilization and the human being adaptability on the health generating scale.

The **general objective** of the alimentary act eco-biotechnology has as aim nutrition applications, so that, by technological complementarities, to study thoroughly the understanding manner of physiological and genetic mechanisms through which foods and bioactive individual components may influence the consumer’s health. The **special objectives** of the eco-biotechnology model also aims the sustainability of the food safety in conformity with the new demands of the 21st century, on the line of technological reorientation and the achievement of agri-food products with *added ecologic and biologic value (AEBV)*, on basis of bioharmonist principles and of integrated model of ecotechnologies and biotechnologies WITH SPECIFIC FLOW.

2. The approach methodology

3. Results and discussions

Eco-biotechnological principles and criteria with applications at eco-bio-products of vegetal and animal origin

Eco-biotechnology conditions NECESSARY TO HEALTH GENERATING FOOD PRODUCTS
(clinically tested food eco-bio-products)

ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGY IN RELATION TO HEALTH GENERATING FOOD

❖ It represents the technological application that uses biodiversity with potential in food in **ecologic/organic** manner, and by a non-destructive processing nutritive substance bioactivity is preserved, so that the clinical tested result may lead to the make up of **PROJECTED FOODS** of the type:

HEALTH GENERATING
agro-zootechnical products, foods and
food dishes.

FOOD GROUPS AND CATEGORIES IN RELATION TO THE WHOLE FOOD ACT

HEALTH GENERATING INNOVATIVE FOODS

AS A RESULT OF ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGIES

BIOACTIVE SUBSTANCE EXTRACTION

- **Extraction methods of bioactive compounds**, mainly from vegetal products, proposed as applications in food biotechnology direction of advanced and/or minimum processing complementary to different usual methods (such as extraction with supercritical fluids, hydrodiffusion, hydrodistillation in close system, maceration, extraction in presence of ultrasounds etc.), applications that are in direct relation with improvement of quality dynamics.

- **Extraction forms:**

- Fluid extracts,
- Smooth extracts (viscous - max.20% humidity),
- Dry extracts (powdery - with max. 50 % humidity)

Perfecting extraction methods

GAS EXTRACTION WITH SUBCRITICAL PRESSURES:

- This extraction method of bioactive compounds from plants in "mild" extraction conditions, represent an **alternative** to replace usual extraction methods with different solvents, based on enzymes, or other modern extraction methods with supercritical liquids.
- Results show a possibility to extract active biological substances **much more numerous** (from our experiments at certain plants, even by doubling them).

Most frequent bioactive compounds from health generating foods

- Antioxidanys
- Izoflavones
- Phytosteroles
- Conjugate linoleic acid
- Probiotics (*living microorganismes*)
- Prebiotics (*probiotic growth factors*)
- Alimentary fibres
- Vitamin C
- Vitamin E
- Volatile oils
- Vegetal pigments (carotenoides, flavonoides, antocianes)

Of practical interest:

MAIN CLASSES OF SECONDARY VEGETAL COMPOUNDS IMPLICATED IN INTERACTION BETWEEN VEGETAL AND ANIMAL ORGANISMS

- Compounds with Nitrogen (approx. 6100 compounds)

- Terpenoids (approx. 3800 compounds)

- Phenols (approx. 2350 compounds)

- Secondary vegetal compounds from the group of NITROGEN COMPOUNDS -

CLASS OF COMPOUNDS	APPROX. NR. OF COMPOUNDS	DISTRIBUTION OF VEGETAL CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS
Alkaloids	5.500	Widespread in <i>Angiospermae</i> , especially in roots, leaves and fruit
Amins	100	Widely spread in <i>Angiospermae</i> , predominate in flowers
Nonproteic aminoacids	400	Generally widely spread; Predominate in vegetable seeds
Cianogenetic glicozides	30	Sporadic, especially in leaves and fruit
Glucosides	75	<i>Cruciferae</i> and other 10 families

- Secondary vegetal compounds from TERPENOID group -

CLASS OF COMPOUNDS	APPROX. NR. OF COMPOUNDS	DISTRIBUTION OF VEGETAL CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS
Monoterpenes	1000	Widely spread in ether oils
Sesquiterpenic lactones	600	Predominate in <i>Compositae</i> ; Also present in other <i>Angiospermae</i>
Diterpenes	1000	Widely spread in latex and in plant resins
Saponines	500	Identified in over 700 plant families
Limonoides	100	Especially present in <i>Rutaceae</i> , <i>Meliaceae</i> and <i>Simaroubaceae</i>
Cucurbitacin	50	Predominant in <i>Cucurbitaceae</i>
Cardenolides	150	Commune in <i>Apocynaceae</i> , <i>Aschepiadaceae</i> and <i>Scrofulariaceae</i>
Carotenoides	400	Universally spread in leaves, often in flowers and fruit

**- Secondary vegetal compounds from
PHENOL group -**

CLASS OF COMPOUNDS	APPROX. NR. OF COMPOUNDS	DISTRIBUTION OF VEGETAL CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS
Simple phenols	200	Universally spread in leaves and other tissues
Flavonoides	1000	Universally spread in <i>Angiospermae</i>, <i>Gimnospermae</i> and <i>Ferns</i>
Chinones	500	Widely spread, predominant in <i>Rhamnaceae</i>
- Other compounds -		
Poliacetilenes	650	Widely spread, predominant in <i>Compositae</i> and <i>Umbeliferae</i>

PRACTICAL ADVANTAGES OF HFC EXTRACTORS WITH LIQUEFIED GAZ AT SUBCRITICAL PRESSURE

➤ They may extract oils in pure estate, at room temperature and in absence of air, which allows to create new categories of large scale products of bioactive substances, as for example, from the group of alimentary flavors and respectively from perfume line, pharmaceutical products etc.

Conclusions

1. „Eco-technologies” and „Bio-technologies” are the complementary structures of the ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGY CONCEPT, that theoretically and practically substantiates the achievement of sustainable food and the corresponding health generating foods, **bioharmonizing** the relations of the technological civilization and human being adaptability (man’s mainly) on the health generating scale.

2. ECO-BIO-PRODUCTS of vegetal and/or animal origin are the ones *complementarily* accomplishing the qualities of ecologic, hygienic/non-toxic and bioactive food. By adding the positive results of clinical tests too, they become *scientifically validated health generating foods*.

3. HEALTH GENERATING INNOVATIVE ALIMENTS are made up on basis of eco-

biotechnological processes and are generally to be found in 4 groups of products: functional foods, smart culinary preparations, prophylactic menus and nutraceuticals.

4. In ECO-BIOTECHNOLOGICAL PROCESSES an important part belongs to permanent perfecting *the extraction methods* of bioactive substances from vegetal and/or animal genetic resources (*such as extraction with subcritical pressure gas, or more frequent the one with supercritical liquids, in comparison with usual methods*), of practical interest for man being extracts from the classes of compounds implied in the *interaction* between vegetal and animal organisms: compounds with nitrogen, terpenoids and phenols.

References

At the author

RESEARCH REGARDING THE IMPORTANCE OF WOOD BIOMASS

GH.C. SPIRCHEZ^{1*}, A.LUNGULEASA¹, L. GACEU^{2,3}

¹ Transilvania University of Brasov, Faculty of Wood Engineering

² Transilvania University of Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism

³ CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy;

*Corresponding author: cosmin.spirchez@unitbv.ro

Abstract: Combustion of solid fuels (including woody biomass) is a necessary activity for people's lives, whether the benefits are direct or through the industries they support. It is also known that there is no noxious combustion. The first problem is to use renewable combustible materials whose carbon dioxide emissions are compensated for by the equivalent carbon dioxide consumption by photosynthesis, biomass growth and development. Second, but last but not least, the combustion mechanism must be known to take all necessary measures to reduce the combustion noxes.

The most important thing since the combustion of biomass is that, following a proper driving of the combustion process, a neutral carbon dioxide is obtained. The impact on the environment of the burning of wood also includes the the impact of cutting impressive amount of material from the forest.

Woody biomass represent a regenerable source of energy. This doesn't contribute to the problem of environmental change, as it recycles carbon dioxide from the atmosphere. Also, its advanced combustion systems mean less smoke from burning wood.

Keywords: biomass, calorimeter bomb, energy density, wood

1. Introduction

Worldwide, biomass covered about 70% of the energy demand, which then gave way to hydro and photovoltaic fuels, and is currently the main fuel in which energy is produced in developing countries.

During the years of the energy crisis and the Gulf War, and recently at the beginning of the third millennium (2001-2010), when Romania and the European Union saw dependence on gas and oil imports from the Asian countries, producing and researching the production of gas, heat and energy from alternative sources.

Current energy sources present on the energy market have been divided into three major categories: fossil fuel, nuclear resources and renewable energy resources. The evolution of energy production from fuels has been divided into three essential period.

According to Piriou description, the first stage consisted of the discovery of fossil fuels and how to obtain energy from them.

The second stage begin when the energy crisis occurred in the 1970, which guides the world's population towards new direction and

visions of energy production, including renewable energy sources.

The third stage consists of exploiting and ensuring the energy need. Fossil fuel are considered to be an important part of biomass that has decomposed over time with energy relevant for energy production.

Energy consumption and volatile substance emissions have been the basis for discussions in the Kyoto Protocol in 1997 year.

At present, energy supply issue are so acute at the international level that it is very difficult to fully satisfy the energy requirement, also taking into account the issue of population growth in the world and the provision of energy needs for the social economic sector and the depletion of resources used to produce energy.

Biomass is one of the renewable energy sources used by the oldest type of people. Until the 18 th century, biomass is considered to be an important source of energy for cooking, and is also one of the most widely spread energy sources in the world.

2. Materials and methods

The installation used to determine the calorific value of wood biomass was the XRY-1C explosive type burner produced by Shanghai Changji Geological Institute in China (fig.1).

Fig. 1. Calorimeter bomb

1 binds to the cotton yarn 2 and put in the crucible of the bomb 3.

Connect the spiral nickel wire 4 to the sample and the cotton yarn, the place the protective cap 5 correctly. The crucible is connected to the calorimetric bomb cap 6 by 2 electrodes 7 and 8, which continues with the electrical coupling bomb of the calorimetric bomb 9 and 10.

By bombing cap, the bomb 11 is coupled through the stator 12 to the oxygen cylinder, introducing 3 atmospheres.

In figure 2 is presented working diagram.

Fig. 2. Working diagram

The method of determining the calorific value of wood material refers firstly to the preparation of the raw material, the to the actual determination and ultimately to the final result. The test sample

The test contains three distinct periods (fig.3).

Period	1	2	3	4	5	6
Fore period	22.996	22.992	22.987	22.983	22.978	22.974
Main period						
After period						

Fig. 3. Three distinct period at calorimeter bomb

The initial period aim to determine the the temperature variations of the water in the calorimetric vessel due to the heat exchange with the outside before the combustion.

The main period start with the ignition of the sample and consequently increases the temperature of the water in the calorimetric vessel. The final period aim to determine the average temperature variation of the water in the calorimetric vessel due to heat exchange with the outside. For *Fraxinus Excelsior*, $m_1 = 0.6600$ g, $U = 0\%$, gross calorific value is 19008 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 18370 kJ/kg, energy

density= 16.446kJ/cm^3 , $m_2 = 1.1180\text{g}$, $U = 10\%$, gross calorific value is 16238 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 15987kJ/kg, energy density = 15.194kJ/cm^3 , $m_3 = 1.2640$ g, $U = 20\%$, gross calorific value is 13788 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 13285 kJ/kg, energy density = 12.392kJ/cm^3 , $m_4 = 1.2770$ g $U=50\%$, gross calorific value is 6436 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 5179 kJ/kg, energy density = 4.533kJ/cm^3 .

In fig.4 is presented variation energy density for *Fraxinus Excelsior*.

Fig. 4. Variation of energetic density for “*Fraxinus Excelsior*”

For *Acer Pseudoplatanus*, $m_1 = 0.8510$ g, $U = 0\%$, gross calorific value is 18802kJ/kg, net calorific value is 18336kJ/kg, energy density = 15.802kJ/cm^3 , $m_2 = 0.9600\text{g}$, $U = 10\%$, gross calorific value is 16805 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 16618 kJ/kg, energy density = 15.953kJ/cm^3 , $m_3 = 1.006$ g, $U = 20\%$, gross calorific value is

15051 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 14668 kJ/kg, energy density = 14.756kJ/cm^3 , $m_4 = 0.9450$ g, $U=50\%$, gross calorific value is 9749 kJ/kg, net calorific value is 9166 kJ/kg, energy density = 8.662kJ/cm^3 .

In fig.5 is presented variation energy density for *Aesculus Hipocastanum*.

Fig.5. Variation of energetic density for “Acer Pseudoplatanus”

Conclusions

At present, all the world's states are channeling their investments on energy production from alternative sources that are projected to reach 20% of the total energy used in Europe by 2020. The high potential for energy production is held by biomass (47%), followed by hydro (45%), at European level.

References

1. Abassi, S.A, Nipaney, P.C., Schaumberg, G.D. Bioenergy potential of eight common aquatic weeds, *Biological Wastes*, vol.34, No.4, pag.359-366, 1990.
2. Gavrilescu, D Energy from biomass in pulp and paper mills, *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*, pag.537-546, 2009;
3. Juran, M. Calitatea produselor, Ed. Tehnică, București, 1973;
4. Lako J., Hanesok J, Yuzhakova T. Biomass-A source of chemicals and energy for sustainable development, *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*, vol. 7(5), pp. 499-509, 2009;
5. Lăzăroiu G, Mihăescu L. Combustion of pitcoal-wood biomass briquettes a boiler test-facility, *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*, pp 595-601, 2008;
6. Lunguleasa A. The calorific power of wooden biomass, *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov-Series II*, vol.2(51), pp.65-70, 2010;
7. Moya R., Tenorio C. Fuelwood characteristics and its relation with extractives and chemical properties of ten fast-growth species in Costa Rica, *Biomass and Bioenergy*, vol.56, pp.14-21, 2011;
8. Nielsen NPK, Gardner D. Importance of temperature, moisture content a species for the conversion process of wood residues to fuel pellets, *Wood Fiber* vol.41, pp 414-425;
9. Prasertsan S., Sajjakulnukit B. Biomass and bioenergy in Thailand: Potential , opportunity and barriers, *Renewable energy* , vol.31 , Nr.5, 2006;
10. Rahmann A, Masood MA Influence of size and shape in the strength by briquettes, *Fuel Process Technology*, vol.22, pp125-145,2013;
11. Roser D., Asikainen A. Sustainable use for Forest Biomass for Energy, *Springer Series in Wood Science*, 2006;
12. Sjostrom E. Wood chemistry, Academic Press, Helsinki, 2006;
13. Teuch O, Hofeanuer A, Troger F, From J. Basic properties of specific wood based materials carbonised in a nitrogen atmosphere, *Wood Science and Technology*, Springer, vol.38, nr.3, 2004;
14. Uslu A, Faaji A.P.C, Bergman P.C.A Pretreatment technologies, and their effect on international bioenergy supply chain logistics. Techno-economic evaluation of torrefaction, fast pyrolysis and pelletisation, *Energy*, vol. 33(8), pp. 1206-1223;
15. Walkowiak, M., Bartkowiak M., The kinetics of the thermal decomposition of the willow wood (*Salix Viminalis L.*) exposed to the torrefaction process, *Drewno (wood)*, vol. 55(187), pp.37-50;
16. Wang G.J., Luo Y.H., Deng J., Pretreatment of biomass by torrefaction, *Chinese Science Bulletin*, vol. 56(14), pp. 1442-1448;

STUDY CONCERNING BIO-HARMONISM PARADIGM, WITH APPLICATIONS TO THE EVOLUTION OF AGRITOURISTIC MANAGEMENT

R. GRUIA^{1,2}

¹Transilvania University of Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism

²CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy;

*Corresponding author: ecotec@unitbv.ro

Abstract: Being more and more aware of the fact that disharmonies at all levels produce huge inconvenient to the human society in general, up to all kinds of organizations and to every citizen, it becomes more than opportune to approach this complexity from other perspectives. One of which is the bioharmonism theory and ideology with unsuspected effects in the improvement of the systemic efficacy. Applying a series of bioharmonism principles and recommendations, the present study proposes to find solutions concerning the growth of efficiency and efficacy of the agro-touring sector. The mechanism to achieve this objective is applied management in agro-touring activity, especially through integration processes, taking into account the complex components belonging to agriculture, hospitality and environment. In order to emphasize managerial maximization, there is analyzed the integronic management with its principles and basic factors.

Keywords: agro-tourism, bioharmonism, management, human society.

Introduction

Generally management, but also management applied to agro-touristic farms and boarding houses is a process in continuous development. Taking into account the harsher and harsher competition that is to be seen on the European and national world agro-touristic market, we propose to analyze the manner the management of these organizations may evolve and theoretically and practically adapt itself.

We propose to start from general to particular because, paradoxically, at deep level of every agro-touristic farm and the corresponding boarding house, nothing can be accidental, but, whether we want it or not, there must be taken into consideration the general frame within which the respective unit functions.

We have in mind to raise the understanding level because only such a way will bring positive changes in the activity of the agro-touring farm. It must be regarded as a complex system “environment-economy”, i.e. an integrated system in the surrounding environment, in the business milieu and natural environment [8, 9, 13, 16, 20 - 24]. It is opportune to analyze new managerial and policy theories for another, deeper understanding of reality and going on future activity in agro-touring farms and boarding houses, as a case study of general bio-harmonist approach [11,12].

1. Synthesis elements of human society evolution

The manner the world has been **administrated** („**managed**”) along time practically shows us **our whence and our whither**:

<u>History Socio-economic development:</u> Agricultural society / Industrial society / Biological-informational society / Knowledge society / Awareness society.
--

These evolutions are directly linked to housekeeping, to resource ever better management, i.e. to the *development of theoretic and applicative management*, which, in the 20th

century constituted the so called: **Managerial Revolution** [3]. That is to say in the 20th century, from the point of view of management „awareness”, there took place two great

innovations: (a) generalization of access to science and (b) managerial revolution [2, 5, 10, 23]. In modern society science, from a good of a few persons became a good of all the people,

which means available knowledge, i.e. *mass access to science*, to “KNOWLEDGE”. Mankind, in its whole, in fact directs itself towards **Knowledge Society**.

Today the fundamental characteristic of the World Economy is rapid evolution towards globalization and use of informational and communication technologies. That is why, as it is especially observed in Europe, **knowledge policies** - research, innovation, education and professional formation – are of an exceptional importance for the Union future, in transition towards a Knowledge World, towards a **Knowledge Europe**.

The **Knowledge Society** progressively replaces the industrial one, the one that replaced the agrarian one at its turn, the last two ones being centered on the production of material values.

The **Knowledge Society** refers to all fields that imply knowledge. Knowledge essentially is a form of *information*, which is the modern society binder, having a more comprehensive level than the informational society. It is the one where *information* induces knowledge as a society propulsive factor. It means power, in the most general meaning – no matter if it is about the political one, the economic one, the financial one -, obtaining, mastering and superior capitalization of information thus being the keystone of this society. It confirms the famous maxim, said by Francis Bacon more than three centuries and a half ago, „*knowledge means power*”. Knowledge is essential for dynamic equilibrium and, respectively, for world „BIOHARMONIZATION”.

After equilibration and optimization by bioharmonization one may pass to a superior stage of understanding reality through „polished” information beyond the creative intelligence of the *Homo sapiens* species, towards wisdom, based on a high individual awareness and high mass spirituality at societal level. On long term we are referring to a real awareness society.

The **Awareness Society** obviously refers to society and to awareness. The industry emergence has not replaced agriculture, as passing information to the fore replaces neither industry nor agriculture, but leads them to other understanding levels, so that „information” has a training effect upon them, towards superior performances (fig.1).

The managerial and political vehicle towards the Knowledge Society is the THEORY OF BIO-HARMONISM [11]:

It is a theory based on a series of concepts referring to bringing into accord and in a new order the humanity creation (got at the crossroads) with the „planetary model”, by reorientation towards a new socio-cultural and economic model, Taking as a mark the **Living and Life in its whole complexity** („*the bios*”), after Nature *non-linear* model, in a *harmonization dynamics* based on methods and means of systemic reorganization (by fractal and integronic models), with tendencies towards efficacy and dynamic equilibrium, necessary to understand and achieve *The Knowledge Society* on a first stage and, on long term, the transition towards the *Awareness Society*. [1, 4, 6, 18, 19]

Bio-Harmonism as a scientific and philosophical theory may be applied at all levels, directions and fields of activity, but the efficacy of its transposition into practice may first of all belong to the political field. We refer to the **bio-harmonist doctrine and ideology** that develops

the integrated vision of economy with society in relation with the resources and environment as a whole. Consequently, a management based on the principles, laws and action direction of the Bioharmonist Ideology is a **management of integronic type with potential of systemic bioharmonization**.

Thus BIOHARMONIZATION balances different disharmonies and optimizes the multitude of factors and components of the human society (from the level of persons to the one of organizations, habitations, regions, states, continents, up to global level), after the „Living Planet” model, having „The Living” as basic mark, with Man as supreme expression, and LIFE with its economic and socio-cultural interconnections, all of them multiply integrated in Nature’s non-linear complexity.

To conclude, the bioharmonist approach to human society offers the opportunity to decode and systemically and in dynamic equilibrium optimize things, thus contributing to the holistic understanding of the reality *puzzle* from a distinct perspective.

A SYNTHESIS OF THE HISTORICAL PERIODS CONCERNING MANKIND'S EVOLUTION

Fig 1. Knowledge Society – medium term mark to approach present management

2. THE INTEGRONIC management, WORK METHOD IN THE BIO-HARMONIST PARADIGM

For a correct understanding of the complex and hyper complex systems of Environment – Economy type, an evaluative form of the modern management is the one of the scientific demarche of the integronic management, where the **system multiple integration** with different connection sequences is approached in the model of flow type, respectively like a *chain of systems in an integration dynamic process* (making up an “*integronic flow*”), such as technology is a concatenation of processes (making up the technologic flow). One may make a synthesis of certain aspects that constitute PREMICES of the new evolution level [3, 7, 10, 14, and 24]:

- Environment integration in the enterprise economic equation (bioeconomic approach) and of the business environment at all levels (up to the European and worldwide one);
- equilibrium or disorders (disharmonies) of the human activity impose mechanisms, methods

and means based on the principles certain **synthesis sciences**, of a large coverage, able to pilot any complex system with maximal efficacy;

- approach of the managerial action from the level of economic **efficiency** to the one of systemic **efficacy** and sustainable development;
- the last decade managerial revolution and the continuous improvement of the **managerial act**;
- recent **integronics** emergence, as being the science of the system coexistence, based on the general theory of integration, that studies integration processes and their composing elements, i.e. integrated systems;
- searching solutions made us associate *integronics* and *management*, i.e. two fundamental conceptual and operational elements, having as a result not only a new syntagm, but also a new scientific demarche with mostly diverse and surprising applications and implications under the efficiency and efficacy plan: i.e. : the **integronic management**.

INTEGRONIC MANAGEMENT represents the scientific demarche that studies integrated systems (as a consequence of their coexistence, in a multiple integration flow, in a system concatenation) and the integration processes, having in view global elements, the facts on the whole and sustainability, aiming to *synchronically and syncretically* pilot complex systems, with effect based on *emergent integration* and *synergy*.

The managerial act in integronic approach is the art or ability to combine diverse sciences, concepts, facilities and resources in order to accomplish pre established objectives, respectively to obtain goods and services and their sale in profitability and sustainability conditions, in a *synchronic* and *syncretic* manner: i.e. they take place at the same time within the given system as forming a whole, globally perceived.

Operationally, integronic management [10] is based on *emergent integration*, by which to explain a thing that emerges at a level obliges us to study certain adjacent levels in the context of a repetitive dynamics of „redundant echo” type with the emergence of the new of a superior order, as well as on *synergy*, i.e. on several actions coordination in view of a common result with means economy and, implicitly with the

system optimized efficiency. Integrronics, including in managerial systems, is to be found at different levels that characterize certain distinct components and a dynamics of *multiple integration in different combinations* of the given systems (table 1).

Integronic management may **methodologically** develop specific directions that give another dimension to the understanding of life and man activity complexity, such as eco-energetic or eMergetic evaluation of the Environment-Economy complex systems or of the component ecosystems and economic organizations; the sustainability degree of investment and productive activity and such like, practically uprising the conceptual level, as it has already been specified, from economic efficiency to systemic efficacy.

Table 1. COMPLEMENTARY COMPONENTS OF THE INTEGRONIC MANAGEMENT

<p>SUCCESSIVE INTEGRATIONS IN INTEGRONIC MANAGEMENT</p> <p>–structural levels in multiple integration, that take into account complex system piloting in <i>synchronic and syncretic dynamics</i>, with effect based on <i>emergent integration and synergy</i>, representing <i>BIO-HARMONISATION processes</i></p>	<p>- BIOLOGIC MANAGEMENT (ex. Management on life – <i>bios</i> - principles, of the competition between species, plus with the creative contribution of the human species, with effects of maximal efficiency in dynamic equilibrium and harmony at planetary level: „<i>bioharmonization</i>”)</p>	<p>BLUE ECONOMY (inclusive circular economy)</p>	<p><i>Knowledge Society (metabolic /living society)</i></p>	<p>Bio-logic informational rev.</p>
	<p>- ECOLOGIC MANAGEMENT (ex. Management of natural resource cycle; solar industry, nonconventional energies, ecologic agriculture and such like)</p>	<p>GREEN ECONOMY</p>	<p><i>Transition society</i></p>	<p>Eco-logic rev.</p>
	<p>- ENVIRONMENT-ECONOMY MANAGEMENT (ex. Industry 4.0; Agriculture: eco-farm management, agro-touring management, agro-mountain management, agro-forest-pastoral management, biotechnology management and such like)</p>	<p>BIO-ECONOMY</p>		<p>The 4th ind. rev. (robotics and/or bio-nano-technologies)</p>
	<p>- ENTERPRISE CLASSIC MANAGEMENT (production management, financial management, of human resources one, of waste one, of marketing one etc.).</p>	<p>STANDARD ECONOMY</p>	<p><i>Industrial society</i></p>	<p>Industrial rev. (approx. per. 1800-2000)</p>

Consequently to the short review of the most important evolutionary stages in figure management development, we may synthesize 2.

Fig. 2 – Management evolution as scientific demarche in relation to planetary evolution

a. Period of empiric management; b. Period of management imposing scientific bases; c. Period of modern management consolidation; d. Period of imposing integronic management.

2.1. MANAGEMENT PRINCIPLES APPLIED IN AGRITOURING ACTIVITY

Among management principles we will synthesis [2] five, in table 2, namely those considered more

important in order to organize and direct an enterprise from agri-tourism (farm + boarding house).

Table 2. FIVE BASIC MANAGERIAL PRINCIPLES APPLIED IN AGRITOURISM

Nr.	PRINCIPLE	CONTENT
1	Economic administration principle	= it is the one on the basis of which management must pursue corresponding utilization of production factors, reasonable administration of own resources, capital recovery and getting profit. By respecting this principle it is possible to create money reserve in order to constitute financial funds for self financing.
2	Economic growth principle	= it is the one in conformity with which any management system pursues to obtain maximal effects with as reduced as possible expenses. Lately, by adopting the model of sustainable development in developed countries, it is also taken into consideration the environment problem, in this case the problem being the growth of the system efficacy. This principle synthesizes in fact the goal of the management activity. In any moment and in any organization management pursues nothing else but to ensure the obtaining of high efficiency. It consists of increase of utile result in relation to the taken pain. Otherwise said, it consists in the fact that at the same taken pain, by a correct establishment of priorities and options by the leaders, the resources should be superiorly valorized and the results maximized.
3	The principle of unity of the direction and responsibility	= it refers to the whole organization system that must be conceived so that every manager should have precisely established attributions, responsibilities and action sphere. By respecting this principle there are created premises for order and discipline within the respective organization. Every employee will know his direct hierarchic boss, from whom he gets tasks and to whom he must respond for his whole activity. Thus there will be achieved the desired correlation between <i>authority</i> and <i>responsibility</i> , fundamental demands for an efficient management.
4	The principle of professional competence and employees' motivation	= it is necessary because on each hierarchic step there should be found the most competent persons and every employee should be motivated in conformity with precisely established criteria in the organization system (professional preparation, years of service, obtained results and such like). The principle application depends on knowing human qualities, on their correct evaluation, on the degree of explanation of every job exigencies and, last but not least, on the application manner of employees' motivational policy.

5	Flexibility principle	= it is the one in conformity with which the management system must be conceived so that it may be characterized by flexibility, in order to be continuously accommodated to new forms of organization and to changes that take place in the enterprise. The need to continuously accommodate and readapt management is dictated by numerous exterior influences, by the scientific evolution, by the world economic conjuncture and its impact upon the national economy and such like. Therefore, the flexibility principle permanently demands to conceive solutions for perfecting the organizations' management system, removal of rigidity, as well as of the tendency towards formalism.
---	------------------------------	---

From the previously mentioned general principles there issues the respect for certain conditions in order to achieve an efficient management: referring to production going on, ensuring optimal task distribution, precisely establishing leadership responsibilities, attracting and involving specialists in the managerial process and such like [7, 10, 15, 17]. Knowing the principles and respecting the imposed conditions, there are necessary a series of *factors* as well as their correct implementation, in view of a corresponding management orientation.

Referring to necessary factors for the evolution of agro-touring management we observe that the application manner in this field differs from one country to another and even from a firm to another firm, within the same country. The managerial pragmatism is characterized by *diversity*. Thus, every activity field has its management characteristics, as for example the existing differences between the management of touring holding and the one of alimentary processing sectors, or of the specificity of the activity in hospitality field (accommodation, meals, events). Therefore, every manager's in agro-tourism approaching diversity and „art” is directly or indirectly linked to rapid evolution generated by these **FACTORS**, that we enumerate here: *Macroeconomic managerial Policies / Economic integration (European, global) / Complication of market mechanisms / Difficulty of free access to resources / Acceleration of the innovation rhythm / Informational explosion.*

All these factors, together with mutations of political-social nature that are nowadays registered, shape the course of a certain agro-touring management dynamics and evolution and determine its perspective orientations.

Conclusions

1. The bio-harmonisation process equilibrates various disharmonies and optimizes the multitude of human society factors and components (from

the person level to the one of organisations, settlements, regions, states, continents, up to the global level), after the „*Living Planet*” model, having as a basic mark the „LIVING”, with Man as a supreme expression and LIFE with its economic and socio-cultural interconnections, all of them multiply integrated in Nature's *nonlinear* complexity.

2. Multiple integrations are expressed by **integronic management** that may *methodologically* develop specific directions that give another dimension to the understanding of life and man activity complexity, practically raising the conceptual level from „economic efficiency” to „systemic efficacy” sustained by bioharmonization processes.

3. It is observed that the evolution of the human society has been possible only by a permanent and evolutionary support of the organization and changeover manner and by a more and more profound understanding of the world, which makes opportune to **analyze the new managerial and political theories** in order to become aware of the reality, absolutely necessary element for the going on of the future activity, including in farms and boarding houses.

4. Knowing the principles and respecting the imposed conditions, it is necessary to understand and apply specific factors in order to correspondingly orientate management towards the diversity and „art” of every manager in agri-tourism approach manner; all these, together with mutations of political-social nature that are nowadays registered, have a certain dynamics to the **evolution of agri-touring management** and determine its perspective orientations.

References

1. Apostol L., Georgescu N., VătuIU I., Gaceu L., Egg surface decontamination by using high voltage pulsed, cold atmospheric plasma jets, J. of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.11, no.2, pp.45-47, 2015.

2. Cornescu, V. și col., 1994: Management - teorie și practică, Edit. Aclami București, 48-52.
3. Enache, C.E., Fedoreanu, A.M., 2011: Trends concerning the evolution of international tourism, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.7, nr2, 79-86.
4. Frioui M., Shamtsyan M., Gaceu L., Oprea O.B., Mnerie D., Rheological influence of (1-3)(1-6) mushrooms β -Glucan, used as flour substitution in bakery industry, Proceedings of the 45th intern. symposium on agricultural engineering „Actual Tasks on Agricultural Engineering”, pg. 377 – 384, Opatija, ISSN 1848-4425;
5. Gaceu, L., *Tehnici moderne de uscare a cerealelor si plantelor tehnice*, Editura Universității “Transilvania” din Brașov, ISBN 973-635-662-0, ISBN 978-973-635-622-9, 203 pg., 2006.
6. Gaceu L., Gadei G., Oprea O.B., Methodology for analyzing EU-conform label information content of meat products in Romania, Journal of Agricultural Informatics., pg. 1-6, 2014 Vol. 1, No. 4, Publisher: Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics (HAAI), ISSN: 2061-862X.
7. Gruia, R., 2003: Bazele științei managementului în ingineria alimentară, Editura Universității Transilvania Brașov, ISBN: 973-635-154-8;
8. Gruia, R. 2009: Curs Managementul pensiunilor agroturistice (platforma e-learning Universitatea Transilvania Brasov).
9. Gruia, R., 2010: „Food-Tourism” Concept Groundwork Prospective Development, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Publishing Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania, Vol.6
10. Gruia, R., 2013: Bazele managementului si directiile viitoare de evolutie, Ed. Lux Libris ISBN 978-973-131-230-9, 210 p.
11. Gruia, R., 2019: Bioarmonismul - de la teorie la o ideologie de viitor, Ed. Clarion Brașov, ISBN 978-606-94470-6-2.
12. Gruia, R., 2019: Ideologia bioarmonistă, izvor de regenerare politică într-o lume în schimbare
13. Harrington, H. J și Harrington J. S – Management total, Editura Teora, București, 2000, pag. 261
14. Hart, Christopher, Sasser, Earl, jr., The profitable art of service recovery, Harvard Business Review, july-august, 1994, pag. 148-156.
15. Herdon, M: et al, 2018: Development support of diversified food production and agrotourism by innovative agroforestry education, J. of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.14, Nr.1, 81-87.
16. Jones G. – Primii pași în afaceri, Editura Teora, București, 1999, pag. 98–106 .
17. Kovacs, T., Varallyai, L., Szilagyi, R., 2018: Possibility of agri- and food industry applications in higher education, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.14, Nr.1, 36-41.
18. Mnerie D., Gaceu L., Gubenia O., Shamtsyan M., Birca A., Mnerie G.V., Comparative study on the evolution of the food labeling quality in some countries from the black sea region, Journal of Hygienic Engineering and Design, pg. 60-65, 2016.
19. Mnerie D., Gaceu L., Oprea O.B., Mnerie G.V., Shamtsyan M., Web based forms regarding consumer’s opinion in food products labelling, Resource and Energy Saving Technologies of Production and Packing of Food Products as the Main Fundamentals of Their Competitiveness: Proceedings of the 3rd International Specialized Scientific and Practical Conference, pp.148-153, 2014.
20. Oprea O.B., Apostol L., Bungau S., Cioca G., Samuel A.D., Badea M., Gaceu L., Researches on the Chemical Composition and the Rheological Properties of Wheat and Grape Epicarp Flour Mixes, REV.CHIM.(Bucharest), Vol.69, Nr. 1, 2018, pag.70-75, ISSN 2537-5733.
21. Oprea O.B., Gaceu, L., Gadei, G., Investigation methodology about labels information content of the meat products from Romania, in accordance with European Legislation, Proceeding of the international conference Agriculture Informatics, pg. 7-12, Debrecen, Hungary, 2013.
22. Oprea, O.B., Schur, E., 2011: Experimental research on the possibility of photovoltaic panel use in the agroturistic zone of sanpetru-brasov J. of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.7, nr.2, pp.119-122.
23. Ospanov A.A., Gaceu L., et al., Innovative Technologies of Grain Crops Processing, Editura Infomarket, ISBN 978-973-1747-42-2, 439 pag., 2015.
24. Tane, N., 2016: Erms of defining some notions of tourism - consensus and contradictions, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.12, Nr.2, 94-97.

COMPARATIVE STUDY REGARDING THE ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF *EUCALYPTUS*, *MENTHA PIPERITA* AND *HIPPOPHAE RHAMNOIDES* - A REVIEW

N.R. SAMOILĂ^{1*}, L. GACEU^{1,2}

¹Transilvania University of Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism

²CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy;

*Corresponding author: raisa.samoila@yahoo.com

Abstract: The paper presents a review of antimicrobial activity of *Eucalyptus*, *Mentha piperita* and *Hippophae rhamnoides* which is detailed in chapter 3. In the first part of the study the biological importance of plants was appreciated, the most common being the antioxidant, antimicrobial, antibacterial and antifungal activity. The most interesting case was for *Eucalyptus* oil which is used internally and externally for catarrh of the respiratory tract and externally for rheumatic complaints. For the antimicrobial activity test, the two most common methods described in the last part of the article, Disk Diffusion Assay and Determination of Minimal Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Non-Inhibitory Concentration (NIC) have been described. MIC was used in most of the scientific papers that have been studied to prepare this review.

Keywords: review, antimicrobial activity, *Eucalyptus*, *Mentha piperita*, *Hippophae rhamnoides*

1. Introduction

Infectious diseases represent a continuous and increasing threat to human health and welfare. They are the major causes of enormous morbidity and mortality in all parts of the world, although developing countries are carrying the major part of the burden [5,22].

Aromatic plants and their components have been examined as potential inhibitors of bacterial growth and most of their properties have been linked to essential oils and other secondary plant metabolites [14]. Essential oils have been used for thousands of years in various cultures for medicinal and health purposes. Because of their antidepressant, stimulating, detoxifying, antibacterial, antiviral and calming properties, essential oils are recently gaining popularity as a natural, safe and cost-effective therapy for a number of health concerns [31].

In recent years, there has been an increase in consumer interest in non-synthesized, natural antimicrobials [13,14].

2. Biological importance

Eucalyptus is a genus of trees. There are over 700 species of eucalypts, and almost all of them

are in Australia. Eucalypts can be found in almost every part of the Australia, and they are adapted to many different habitats [30].

In vitro, eucalyptus oil has an antibacterial and fungicidal effect. The drug inhibits prostaglandin biosynthesis and has a mild hyperemic, expectorant and secretolytic motor effect when used topically. In animal experiments eucalyptus was demonstrably cough relieving and displayed a surfactant effect. In vitro, the oil was enzyme inducing and improved pulmonary compliance. It is secretolytic, expectorant, mildly antispasmodic, and a mild local hyperemic. *Eucalyptus* oil is used internally and externally for catarrh of the respiratory tract and externally for rheumatic complaints [18].

In the study made by Raho G. Bachir and M. Benali, 2012 it is recalled that *Eucalyptus* species are well known as medicinal plants because of their biological and pharmacological properties as anesthetic, anodyne, antiseptic, astringent, deodorant, diaphoretic, disinfectant, expectorant, febrifuge, fumigant, hemostat, inhalant, insect repellent, preventive, rubefacient, sedative yet stimulant, vermifuge, for a folk remedy for abscess, arthritis, asthma, boils, bronchitis, burns, cancer, diabetes, diarrhea, diphtheria, dysentery, encephalitis, enteritis, erysipelas, fever, flu, inflammation,

laryngalgia, laryngitis, leprosy, malaria, mastitis, miasma, pharyngitis, phthisis, rhinitis, sores, sore throat, spasms, trachalgia, worms, and wounds [6, 8].

Sometimes their demand is also high in the soap and cosmetic industries [7].

Fig. 1. *Eucalyptus* [29]

Mentha piperita is a perennial 50–90 cm high, strongly scented and a prototypical member of the mint family. The peppermint plant is aromatic, stimulant and used for allaying nausea, headache and vomiting. The leaves of peppermint are commonly used in herbal tea and for culinary purpose to add flavour and aroma. The oil obtained is widely used essential oils in food products, dental preparations, mouthwashes, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, soaps and alcoholic liquors [2, 23].

The oil has a high menthol content and also contains menthone and carboxyl esters, particularly menthyl acetate.

This type of *Mentha* has a spasmolytic effect on smooth muscle of the gastrointestinal tract. It is a carminative, cholagogue, antibacterial, insecticidal and secretolytic agent; it also has a cooling effect on the skin [18].

A recent study that investigated in vitro against three humane cancer cell lines (A549, HepG-2 and MCF-7) and four bacterial strains; two gram positive (*E. coli* and *A. Hydrophila*) and two gram negative (*S. aureus* and *E. faecium*) showed moderate in vitro anticancer activity and high antimicrobial activity [1].

Fig. 2. *Mentha piperita* [28]

Hippophae rhamnoides (sea buckthorn) is indigenous to Europe and some northern regions of Asia. The plant is an angular, thorny 1.5 to 4.5 m high shrub with numerous thorn-tipped and thorny branches. The leaves are 5 to 8 cm long, linear lanceolate, short petioled, glabrous above, tomentose beneath. The sea buckthorn

compounds are: chiefly malic acid, additionally acetic acid, quinic acid, ascorbic acid (0.2-1.4%), beta-carotene, gamma-carotene, isolinolenic acid, linolenic acid. It is used as a vitamin C supplement. The vitamin C constituent encourages the healing of wounds and epithelization. It strengthens sight and inhibits

sclerosis and the aging process. The oil has a liver-protective, ulcer-protective, tumor protective, anti-oxidative and wound-healing

effect. It is also promoter vascular elasticity and a good anticoagulant [18].

Fig.3 *Hippophae rhamnoides* [27]

3. Antimicrobial activity

3.1. Antimicrobial activity of *Eucalyptus*

The antimicrobial activity of essential *Eucalyptus* oil tested on *E. coli* and *S. aureus* concluded, according to the table, that greater inhibition was observed at a higher concentration of oil. At low concentrations, a very limited inhibitory effect was observed on the growth of microorganisms in comparison with those controls. With increasing essential oil leaves concentration, and

obvious inhibitory effect on the growth of and *S. aureus*, was significantly increase.

In most cases, the essential oil of *Eucalyptus* leaves has the same inhibitory effect on both germs except for the dilution 10^{-3} where we see that the gram (-) bacterium *E. coli* was found to be more sensitive to the oil than the gram (+) bacterium *S. aureus* [6].

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity evaluation of the essential oil of *Eucalyptus* g. leaves using the dilution broth method against the two bacterial strains [6]

Microbial strains	Essential oil dilution					Control
	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	
<i>E.coli</i>	+		+	++	+++	+++
<i>S.aureus</i>	+		++	++	+++	+++

++: Comparable growth with that Control +; slow growth

Another study that followed the evaluation of the antimicrobial activity of the essential oil from 8 species of eucalyptus concluded that the Gram (-) bacteria *P. aeruginosa* and *K. pneumoniae* were the most resistant to all the oils but more sensitive to the antibiotics, ciprofloxacin and ampicillin. Compared to antibiotics and antifungal fosfomycin, ampicillin, rifamycin and pevaryl, the clinical strains *S. aureus*, *H. influenzae*, *S. agalactiae*, *S. pyogenes*,

S.pneumoniae and all the tested fungal strains were more sensitive to *E. odorata* oil. [3]

3.2. Antimicrobial activity of *Mentha piperita*

A group of researchers who studied the antimicrobial activity of *M. piperita* essential oils through three types of extraction showed by Table 2 the susceptibility pattern of the *M. piperita* essential oils (HD, MAHD and SFME) (20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) against the bacterial isolates. The values of the diameter of inhibition zone (mm) caused by the three essential oils against four

bacterial strains indicated that all essential oils effect comparing with that of the reference treatments caused significantly antimicrobial antibiotic treatment [19].

Table 2. Diameter of Inhibition zone (DIZ) (mm) caused by (20 µg/ml) of *M. piperita* essential oils (HD, MAHD and SFME) against four bacterial strains

Treatments(20 µg/ml)	Gram-Negative bacteria		Gram-positive bacteria	
	E. coli	A. hydrophila	S. aureus	E. faecium
HD	7a	14f	16j	8m
MAHD	6b	13e	15i	9n
SFME	6b	15g	17k	8m
Streptomycin 10 µg	4a	11d	13h	5l

Different letters inside each column mean significant difference at $p < 0.05$.

*HD; MAHD and SFME- extraction methods

In another research paper that studied the antimicrobial activity of four types of essential oils: *Cinnamomum zeylanum*, *Mentha piperita*, *Flowering Bovis and Thymus vulgaris*, the results indicated that the antibacterial effect of the essential oils, particularly *C. zeylanicum* and *Z. multiflora* against some pathogenic bacteria.

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of the extracts of seabuckthorn leaf, bark, pulp and seed (50µL/well) against the tested microorganisms based on agar well diffusion method. [25]

Plant extract	Zone of inhibition; mm (inhibition%)					
	S. aureus	B. subtilis	E. aerogenes	P. aeruginosa	K. pneumonia	E. coli
Leaf						
Methanol	24(75)++	15(44)+	14(46)+	14(42)+	12(37)+	10(27)+
Acetone	22(68)++	18(52)++	13(43)+	13(39)+	12(37)+	-
Chloroform	14(43)+	10(29)+	20(66)++	14(42)+	11(34)+	-
Petr. Ether	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bark						
Methanol	22(65)++	16(47)+	14(46)+	14(42)+	11(34)+	9(24)+
Acetone	20(62)++	15(44)+	13(43)+	11(33)+	12(37)+	-
Chloroform	13(40)+	11(32)+	14(46)+	12(36)+	9(28)+	-
Petr. Ether	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pulp						
Methanol	18(56)++	10(29)+	16(53)++	12(36)+	12(37)+	10(27)+
Acetone	16(50)++	15(44)+	15(50)++	10(30)+	12(37)+	9(24)+
Chloroform	12(37)+	9(26)+	12(40)+	9(27)+	11(34)+	-
Petr. Ether	10(31)+	9(26)+	10(33)+	9(27)+	10(31)+	-
Seed						
Methanol	26(81)++	16(47)+	20(66)++	12(36)+	12(37)+	12(32)+
Acetone	19(59)++	15(44)+	17(56)++	10(30)+	11(34)+	9(24)+
Chloroform	16(50)++	9(26)+	14(46)+	10(30)+	10(31)+	-
Petr. Ether	16(50)++	10(29)+	15(50)++	9(27)+	9(28)+	-
Standard						
Amoxicilin	32	34	30	33	32	37

These essential oils can be used as natural antibiotics with fewer side effects than chemical antibiotics to deal with bacterial pathogens. Mint is not highlighted in the study of antimicrobial activity [19, 25].

3.3. Antimicrobial activity of *Hippophae rhamnoides*

The antimicrobial activity of the tested extracts of seabuckthorn showed different selectivity for each microorganism. The results revealed that *S. aureus* showed strong inhibition for seed (81%)

and leaf (75%) extracts, *E. aerogenes* showed moderate inhibition for leaf (66%), pulp (53%) and seed (66%) extracts and *B. subtilis* showed moderate inhibition for leaf (52%) extracts, respectively whereas weak inhibition was found for *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumonia* and *E. coli* for all organs extracts.[25]

According to Khan et al. 2010, the phenolic compounds of sea buckthorn both suppress gram-negative bacteria and reduce gram-positive bacteria (Kumar and Sagar 2007). [15,16,17]

4. Methods

For testing the antimicrobial activity of plant oils have been used in research two most common methods: Disk Diffusion Assay and Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Non-Inhibitory Concentration (NIC).

4.1. Disk Diffusion Assay

The disk-diffusion agar method tests the effectiveness of antibiotics on a specific microorganism. An agar plate is first spread with bacteria, then paper disks of antibiotics are added. The bacteria is allowed to grow on the agar media, and then observed. The amount of space around every antibiotic plate indicates the lethality of that antibiotic on the bacteria in question. Highly effective antibiotics (disk C) will produce a wide ring of no bacterial growth, while an ineffective antibiotic (disk A) will show no change in the surrounding bacterial concentration at all. The effectiveness of intermediate antibiotics (disk B) can be measured using their zone of inhibition. This method is used to determine the best antibiotic to use against a new or drug-resistant pathogen. [26]

In the case of testing the antimicrobial activity of essential oils, instead of antibiotic, the plant oil was put on the petri plate.

Fig. 4.- Disk Diffusion Test [26]

4.2. Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Non-Inhibitory Concentration (NIC)

Determination of MIC and NIC (fig. 5) values is carried out by bacterial growth in broth was monitored through changes in optical density of

bacterial suspensions in the presence of multiple concentrations of essential oils. The effect on the growth, measured by the optical density method, is manifested by a reduction in the area under the time or curve relative to control well at any specified time. [9,24].

Fig. 5. Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration [32]

Conclusions

In conclusion, taking into account all these results, *Eucalyptus* oil provide a promising product in the therapeutic application for the treatment of some respiratory bacterial infections and fungal diseases.

The essential oil of sea buckthorn that has undergone antimicrobial testing has been shown to suppress gram-negative bacteria and reduce gram-positive bacteria, as compared to essential oil of *Mentha piperita*.

The extracts from the three plants act differently for different bacterial strains, for example: *E. coli*, *A. hydrophila*, *S. aureus*, *E. faecium*, *B. subtilis*, *E. aerogenes*, *P. aeruginosa*, *K. pneumonia*. The most widely used method for determining the antimicrobial activity of plant extracts is disk diffusion assay.

References

1. Abdel-Hameed E. S., Salman M.S., Fadl M. A., Elkhateeb A., El-Awady M. A., *Chemical Composition of Hydrodistillation and Solvent Free Microwave Extraction of Essential Oils from Mentha piperita L. Growing in Taif, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and their Anticancer and Antimicrobial Activity*, Oriental Journal Of Chemistry, ISSN: 0970-020 X CODEN: OJCHEG 2018, Vol. 34, No.(1), pp. 222-233;
2. Ali M.A., Saleem M., Ahmad W., Parvez M., Yamdagni, R., *A chlorinated monoterpene ketone, acylated-sitosterol glycosides and a flavanone glycoside from Mentha longifolia (Lamiaceae)*, Phytochemistry 2002, 59(8): 889-895;
3. Ameer Elaissi, Zyed Rouis, Nabil Abid Ben Salem, Samia Mabrouk, Youssef ben Salem, Karima Bel Haj Salah, Mahjoub Aouni, Farhat Farhat, Rachid Chemli, Fethia Harzallah-Skhiri, Mohamed Larbi Khouja , *Chemical composition of 8 eucalyptus species' essential oils and the evaluation of their antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral activities*, , BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine, The official journal of the International Society for Complementary Medicine Research (ISCMR)201212:81, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-12-81> ;
4. Apostol L., Berca L., Mosoiu C., Badea M., Bungau S., Oprea O.B., Cioca G., *Partially Defatted Pumpkin (Cucurbita maxima) Seeds- a Rich Source of Nutrients for Use in Food Products*, REVISTA DE CHIMIE 69 (6), 1398-1402;
5. Awol Mekonnen, Berhanu Yitayew, Alemnesh Tesema, and Solomon Taddese , *In Vitro Antimicrobial Activity of Essential Oil of Thymus schimperi, Matricaria chamomilla, Eucalyptus globulus, and Rosmarinus officinalis*, Hindawi Publishing Corporation, International Journal of Microbiology, Vol. 2016, Article ID 9545693, 8 pages;

6. Bachir R.G., Benali M., *Antibacterial activity of the essential oils from the leaves of Eucalyptus globulus against Escherichia coli and Staphylococcus aureus*, Asian Pac J Trop Biomed. 2012 Sep; 2(9): 739–742;
7. Bajaj Y.P.S., *Medicinal and aromatic plants*. Berlin, Heidelberg, New York: Springer Edition; 1995. Vol.8, Biotechnology in agriculture and forestry; pp. 194–196;
8. Elliot WR, Jones D. *The Encyclopaedia of Australian plants*, Vol. 4. Melbourne: Lothian Publishing Company Pty Ltd; 1986;
9. Fitsiou E., Mitropoulou G., Spyridopoulou K., Tiptiri-Kourpeti A., Vamvakias M., Bardouki H., Panayiotidis M.I., Galanis A., Kourkoutas Y., Chlichlia K., Pappa A., *Phytochemical Profile and Evaluation of the Biological Activities of Essential Oils Derived from the Greek Aromatic Plant Species Ocimum basilicum, Mentha spicata, Pimpinella anisum and Fortunella margarit*, Molecules 2016, 21(8), 1069;
10. Frum A., Lengyel E., Georgescu C., Gligor F., Tita O., *Analysis of phenolic compounds extracted from three types of berries*, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Proceeding of 6th BIOATLAS Conference, Vol. 12, no.2 2016, pp 5-9;
11. Gaceu L., *Comparative study regarding the antioxidant activity of subcritical extracts from Vitis semen, Mustard and Polygonum Cuspidatum*, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, 2017, Vol.13, No.2, ISSN 1844-857, pp.48-52, ref.12
12. Gaceu L., *Aspects regarding electrochemical detection of the antioxidant activity for subcritical extracts from Pleurotus ostreatus*, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, 2017, Vol.13, No.1, ISSN 1844-8577, pp.53-57, ref.12;
13. Gyawali R., Ibrahim S.A., *Natural products as antimicrobial agents*, Food Control, Vol. 46, December 2014, pp. 412-429
14. Juliany Rivera Calo, Philip G. Crandall, Corliss A.O'Bryan, Steven C.Ricke, *Essential oils as antimicrobials in food systems – A review*, Food Control, Vol.54, August 2015, pp. 111-119
15. Khan B.A., Akhtar N., Mahmood T., *A comprehensive review of a magic plant Hippophae rhamnoides*, Pharmacogn J 16: 58-61, 2010;
16. Kumar S., Sagar A., *Microbial associates of Hippophae rhamnoides (Seabuckthorn)*, Plant Pathol J 6: 299-305, 2007;
17. Krejcarová J., Straková E., Suchý P., Herzig I., Karásková K., *Sea buckthorn (Hippophae rhamnoides L.) as a potential source of nutraceuticals and its therapeutic possibilities - a review*, ACTA VET. BRNO 2015, 84: 257–268;
18. Medical Economics Company, *PDR for Herbal Medicine*, Montvale, NJ.: ISBN: 1-56363-361-2;
19. Mohammadi A., Hashemi M., Hosseini M., *Antimicrobial Activity of Essential Oils of Cinnamomum zeylanicum, Mentha piperita, Zataria multiflora Boiss and Thymus vulgaris Against Pathogenic Bacteria*, Medical Laboratory Journal, Mar, Apr 2016; Vol 10: No 2, pp.32-40;
20. Oprea O.B., Apostol L., Bungau S., Cioca G., Samuel A.D., Badea M., Gaceu L., *Researches on the Chemical Composition and the Rheological Properties of Wheat and Grape Epicarp Flour Mixes*, REVISTA DE CHIMIE 69 (1), 70-75;
21. Popovici C., Oprea O. B., *The influence of phenolic compounds from membrane septum on the physical-chemical parameters of the walnut oil-enriched emulsion*, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Proceeding of BIOATLAS Conference, Vol. 10, no. 2 2014, pp.110-115;
22. Z. A. Memish, S. Venkatesh, and A. M. Shibl, *“Impact of travel on international spread of antimicrobial resistance,”* International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 135–142, 2003;
23. Zaidi S., Dahiya P., *In vitro antimicrobial activity, phytochemical analysis and total phenolic content of essential oil from Mentha spicata and Mentha piperita*, International Food Research Journal 22(6): 2440-2445 (2015);
24. Zhang X., Guo Y., Guo L., Jiang H., Ji Q., *In Vitro Evaluation of Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activities of Melaleuca alternifolia Essential Oil*, Hindawi BioMed Research International, Vol. 2018;
25. <https://academicjournals.org/journal/JMPR/article-full-text-pdf/15C446024100>
26. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Disk_diffusion_test
27. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hippophae>
28. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Peppermint>
29. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eucalyptus>
30. <https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eucalyptus>
31. <https://draxe.com/essential-oil-uses-benefits/>
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Minimum_inhibitory_concentration

EXAMPLES OF „*BIOHARMONIZATION*” OF THE REALITY COMPONENTS, ARGUMENTS FOR THE NEW BIO-HARMONIST IDEOLOGY

R. GRUIA^{1,2}

¹Transilvania University of Brasov, Faculty of Food and Tourism

² CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy;

*Corresponding author: ecotec@unitbv.ro

Abstract: *Within the large frame of bioharmonization process the paper proposes to find basic elements and solutions corresponding to the dynamic equilibrium of the territorial landscape and its components. With the help of the Bio-Harmonism Theory and its specific methodology (principally, the fractal analyses and integronic synthesis), the study describes a series of examples from practice, that are basic arguments for the „awareness” of the approach need through bioharmonist ideology. There are mentioned some bioharmonization examples at system level, respectively the existence of social and institutional bioharmonization processes, then concerning circular economy, or ecosystem bioharmonization. The present studies intend to be arguments that demonstrate the opportunity to apply these new approaches to the growth of the systemic efficacy, both for different organizations (enterprises) and for ecosystems in which these ones are integrated. The Model of the Living Planet, of the natural ecosystems, may be adapted in the bioharmonized re-conceiving of the artificial ecosystems, especially of those with a high anthropization degree such as agri-food modules. Among the pragmatic aspects the paper exemplifies models of policulture and of permaculture, where bioharmonization elements are described on basis of specific principles, rules and techniques (terraces, ponds, raised layers and such like), within policies and strategies of Bioharmonist Ideology.*

Keywords: *bioharmonization, bioeconomy, ecosystem, policulture, permaculture.*

1. Introduction

Reality has got in first and we are not aware of the impact of the new type of activities and, as it is known, good ideas make winners and it is only in weak countries that politicians win. From here also the impulse I've had to make a „puzzle” of „insular” ideas and to create a general frame of a unitary conceptual perspective. There resulted the Theory of Bio-Harmonism [12], but also its most penetrating application, i.e. through the political field, shaping the bioharmonist doctrine and ideology [13]. By defining the terms, elaborating the work methodology, establishing the principles and directions of action etc., the mentioned papers propose to contribute to make people aware of the type of society we are living in, namely one based on the Biological Revolution in a Digital Era. Bioharmonism intends to be a „vehicle” of the *sustainable development* (unanimously accepted) towards a

medium term creation of the Knowledge Society (including a European objective) and, on long (maybe very long) term of the Awareness Society described in numerous papers [1, 2, 4, 11, 17, 20, 22].

Although many people consider that we are living in a post-modern and post ideological world, in which mankind is similar to a convalescent after a severe illness, i.e. after the totalitarian ideologies of the 20th century, it becomes opportune to bring the necessary corrections and propose new paradigms that may set evolution going. More than that, as the *priest Stăniloae* said, „*Nowadays mankind is theologically worn-out*”, fact that imposes a new doctrinaire orientation and direction, not only a religious one, but also a scientific one, a political, social and philosophical one too. We mean conceptual regeneration in a changing world and, implicitly the genesis of new ideologies, such as

the **Bio-Harmonist Ideology** and the corresponding policy.

In the present paper we do not propose to analyze paradigmatic aspects and evolution directions in the bioharmonization processes, but to understand the starting base and the necessity to develop such a political theory and ideology. That is why we will center on a series of examples of bioharmonization that already take place around us and that have represented the „germ”, and then the generalization of the idea, i.e. of the new bioharmonist approach to human society.

The examples clearly show the importance of the Bio-Harmonist Theory and Ideology, but also the newness of the scientific and technical approaches that sustain new directions to solve, to streamline, to optimize, to grow the system efficacy (from enterprises up to state level), largely different and with strong impact for solving the 21st century provocations. All these described in comparison with the consecrated ideologies (liberalism, socialism, ecologism etc.) that have proved lacunas in solving problems, largely getting in fact to a doctrinaire exhaustion.

Within this context we consider it harmful to approach the idea of ideology „futility” (idea of post-ideological society), as the world is at a cross point when, in our opinion, more than ever, it is necessary to revive ideologies in order to save the human society at planetary level. It may sound alarming, but only creativity and new ideas may solve problems (grievous nowadays) and save humanity. We think that *bioharmonism* paradigm is one of the new ideas, based on

perceived reality, but not enough realized, that may contribute to solve world today and tomorrow problems.

The paper main objective is to argue and make it understandable for as many people as possible that bioharmonist ideology is based on the reality of bioharmonization processes that go on around us, in different activity fields. In this direction, in order to be aware of the solutions and counteract present society disequilibrium and disharmonies, we consider it useful to exemplify certain aspects of the *bioharmonization processes*, only just to show the necessity of the new manner to approach reality, namely by **bioharmonism**.

2. Work method

For the territorial landscape, especially from fragile zones such as the mountain ones, *the technological model of the systemic modulation* is based on integration, on *integrative dynamics* [10]. Methodologically, in all systems and their corresponding modules, it is taken into consideration the ontic triad that presupposes input and *Substance, Energy and Information* processing (the 3 aspects of the same *Fundamental existence*) together determined in modular dynamics (syncretically and synchronically) with synergic effect, having emergence towards a new level of a superior order as a resultant. As a method from IT perspective, the technologic model we have in view in modular bioharmonization of different systems is based on the scheme from figure 1.

Fig. 1. Overview scheme of the modular structure in process of systemic (bio)harmonization

3. Results and discussions

We mention that „*bioharmonization*” is the demarche that pursues to achieve new integrated economic and socio-cultural models by

optimizing connections from the ontic triad (I, E, S) omnipresent in the existence of all the things, processes and phenomena, having as a mark the *Living* and the *Life* in its whole, triad that we also find in infinite forms in Reality perceived from

the Living Planet *micro* level to *macro* level [9, 10]. Within this general context, the technical application & I.T. interest all complex systems exposed to the bioharmonization process, especially those of environment-economy type. This methodologically implies a series of reference elements necessary to adapting the intended modules [5-9, 14, 15, 18, 21], for different specific situations, as for example: - to be energetically autonomous on solar and aeolian basis, - to be able to recycle rain and used water, - to transform waste and dejections in natural fertilizers, - in agro-modules to organize a rotation of cultures in order to allow land to regenerate without chemical fertilizers and so on. Thoroughly studying the problem, there will be also taken into consideration climate changes, plant exposure in relation to cardinal points, as well as from the soil and subsoil offer (as, for example there may be arranged subsoil greenhouses).

The Bio-Harmonist Ideology has the gift to create the general frame favorable to equibrately develop, counteract disharmonies (including those of climate change type), consolidate democracy (“harmonize” state components) etc. Without entering into details, we will exemplify what elements of principle must be rethought and re-equilibrated for our country: - to create conditions for the development of the Romanian civil society; - to achieve conditions for a *REAL market economy* based only on competition; - to consolidate the state of law by *REAL independence* and power equilibrium in state (aspects that in fact indicate a „Third Republic”, with the corresponding constitution) etc.

In order to understand and elaborate a bioharmonist policy, as a first step it is necessary to point out **the interest components**, such as those on economic, social, cultural and scientific, juridical and moral line and such like (fig.2).

APPLICATIONS OF BIOHARMONIST IDEOLOGY

APPLICATIONS OF THE THEORY OF BIO-HARMONISM AT REALITY
ESSENTIAL MARKS BY EXEMPLIFYING THE MAIN REFERENCE FIELDS

Fig. 2. Directions to elaborate general bioharmonist policies, based on sector policies

A **bioharmonist policy** will consider re-projecting from particular (organizations) to general (step by step, up to the new world

economic system), on a series of „key” directions (fig.3), taking also into account the idea to „bioeconomically globalize based on

bioharmonism, on bioethics, through ecologic and humanist education”.

Fig. 3. *Relation between Environment, Technology and Society, framework of interest in bioharmonic policies*

To simplify, one may say that nowadays the consecrated models of „communism” and „capitalism”, „socialism” and „classic liberalism” type and such like either have already „fallen”, or are disorientated, in crisis and, in certain situations, even in down fall. Common sense logics says that one may not make a brainless policy, with no ideologies and doctrines („*post - post-ideology*” is even mentioned !). Therefore it results the fact that reality cannot chaotically be analyzed, without taking into account planetary equilibriums, but only on bases of theories, principles, rules etc., merged in ideological approaches [3, 23]. In this direction, **Bio-Harmonic Ideology** has the potentiality to find viable and of high efficacy solutions at all levels (from persons, up to the most complicated systems, from empirics to science, awareness and spirituality), that may correspondingly solve the 21st century complex problems.

BIOHARMONISM deeply analyses surrounding Reality, being based on existing concrete elements that take place on certain places and in certain situations, such as: of optimization, of productivity growth, of efficiency and „reconciliation” with the

environment, with biocenosis (planetary living), with society and nowadays culture. All these in the idea to improve man’s life quality, but also the one of the other beings this one is dependent in the planetary model.

Therefore, we may understand Reality as „it is” and not as „it is sold” to us by mass-media means, by experts in marketing, by politicians etc. Therefore we consider it opportune to give a series of **examples of bioharmonization** of different systems (from the simplest such as enterprises and institutions and finishing with complex systems of environment-economy type, of different types of ecosystems etc.), so that we may emphasize the basis and arguments in order to understand their approach within the unitary framework of a new ideology: the Bio-Harmonic Ideology.

• GENERAL EXAMPLES OF BIOHARMONIZATION PROCESSES

To exemplify bioharmonization processes we will just mention, from the multitude of the application field of the bio-harmonic ideology (v.fig. 2), some eloquent aspects for anyone who

wants to understand nowadays reality „aware of” through the new political paradigm surrounding us and the one we may be better (table 1).

Table 1. Exemplification of bioharmonization processes on some interest groups

Nr.	EXEMPLIFIED FIELD	SPECIFICITY CONCERNING BIOHARMONIZATION PROCESSES
1	Social and institutional bioharmonization:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ There is counteracted the rupture between certain social components, as for example the one from education with the ones from production, or both with the political ones and such like, that, especially in developing countries, are many times disharmonic and even „parallel”.
2	Bioharmonization on bioeconomic line through circular economy:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Passage from the present model „take-make-consume-throw”, to the model „share - reuse - repair - renovate – recycle existing materials and products as much as possible”. Thus, the product life cycle is extended <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Examples:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - plastic material products such as chemically recycled plastic material wrappers; - building materials got from building and demolition waste; - utilization of fruit pulp resting after processing from juice industry by transformation in a healthy ingredient with added value that may be added to cereals, snacks and chocolate; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - flakes got from pressed apple pulp; - organic waste may be recycled, making compost that may be used as fertilizer in parks, plantations or gardens; - whey is a sub product resulted when preparing cheese, casein and protein co precipitates, that may be capitalized under another cheese form, as for example <i>Ricotta cheese</i>; or one may get fermentable or non-fermentable drinks; - from soft cheese, by insemination with bacteria cultures one may obtain <i>albuminoidal cheese</i>; - from processing fruit residuum by distillation one may obtain alcoholic drinks; - from the majority of residuum from alimentary industry one may get fodder for animals and all the like.
3	Ecosystem bioharmonization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ We distinguish the <i>socio-economic perspective</i> that has as an objective: regeneration of viability and diverse geographic zone attractiveness (it is the object of other studies and researches), as well as the <i>ecologic-technical perspective</i> that has as an objective the dynamic equilibrium of the given territorial module (ex. mountain) on <i>bioharmonism principles</i>. We refer to a consequence of the multiple integrations (integronic dynamics) with capacity to re-equilibrate and harmonize after the nature model of the ecosystem components (forests, pastures, waters, agricultural land, zootechny, rural space etc.)

• **CONCRETE EXAMPLES IN THE BIOHARMONIZATION OF CERTAIN AGRI-FOOD MODULES**

Our demarche is done to this end, from rethinking flows in agriculture (from agro

ecosystems), respectively bioharmonization of the agri-module by policulture, by permaculture, by innovatory methods and technologies as for example hydroponic, aeroponic cultures and such like. In principle we refer to eco-farms [8] where bioharmonization is characterized by reducing

the dependence on conventional energies, by diminishing pollution or even by non-altering the environment, by increasing ecologic productivity and respectively, by maximizing ecosystem efficacy by an adequate creative

management, based on the strategies of the alternative agriculture, of the modular agriculture, to remind only the most important directions for solving the food manner in this century (table 2).

Table 2. Systemic bioharmonization through basic directions of the modular agriculture, in relation to the landscape

Nr.	APPLIED CONCEPT	EFFECT UPON BIODIVERSITY	TYPE OF AGRICULTURE WITH DIFFERENT BIOHARMONIZATION DEGREES
1.	MONOCULTURE (efficiency, large productions = quantity principle)	Biodiversity pauperization	- Modern agriculture (intensive, of large economic productivity) in the rural outside of built up area space - Peri-urban agriculture (industrial agro-zootechny)
2.	POLICULTURE (ecosystem efficacy = quality principle)	Biodiversity enrichment	- Semi-subsistence agriculture - Sustainable mountain agriculture - Sustainable agriculture of wet zones - Urban agriculture of the future – vertical farms
3.	PERMACULTURE (ecosystem optimization and reconstruction = bioharmonization)	Reconfigured and in dynamic equilibrium biodiversity	- Agriculture of fragile zones (hardly accessible mountain ones, wet ones, far away ones etc.)

POLICULTURE

In the bioharmonization processes pursued by policulture there are taken into consideration trophic chains, recycling, self regulations and other technical, biological and managerial. We mention that the pragmatic aspect of the functional intermission of cybernetic type of the subsystems that assure the *phytocenoses-zoocenoses* connection of an ecological system represents the eco-farm itself. The model of this ecosystem unit (as an agro-alimentary module) that will more and more frequently appear (including in the idea of *spatial colonization*), may have as primary germ the **policulture system** already practiced starting with the pisciculture field [8].

In short it is about breeding several fish species in lakes with different biological necessities, that consume a rich aquatic vegetation (primary production) and eliminate excrements still having 50% non-digested organic substances from food, of which

microscopic creatures benefit. There are intensively bred poultry, pigs, cows and silkworms on the lakeside. There are mulberry trees planted on dams (thus they consolidate borders against erosions) where there are placed a series of vegetal cultures (irrigated with water from the lake). The silkworm chrysalis is used as fish food, and poultry and pig dejections represent a good fertilizer for aquatic vegetation. Certain species of aquatic plants are used in feeding cows. The rich silt gathered on the bottom of the lake is pumped out on border cultures as fertilizer.

Such a **bioharmonized agroecosystem**, with such phytocenoses-zoocenoses connections, that is made in China at Suzhan, may produce: 1390 t fish for consumption (various species, especially Chinese carp) and breed 10 000 fowls (ducks and hens), 1000 pigs and 50 milk cows on a 24 ha lake. There is achieved a dynamic equilibrium, good eco-farm productivity and the efficacy of agro-module piloting approaches natural ecosystem productivity, in conformity with the *Living Planet* model that is bioharmonism basic mark.

PERMACULTURE

The concept of permaculture represents the system that imitates nature *structurally* based on ecosystems and *functionally* on natural cycles. **Bioharmonization is generally made by land terracing and permaculture techniques.**

The motion has been introduced by the Australian ecologist Bill Mollison and his student, David Holmgren, and, as an origin, it comes from the term of „permanent agriculture” (to which, of course, new meanings and dimensions have been added), the concept having been developed since 1978 [11, 16].

In syntheses, especially for fragile ecozones such as those of high altitude too, respectively **mountain permaculture** [19], we mention a few elements of operational order: - projecting (creation of terraces, overbuilt strata, aquatic gardens, ponds, ditches for depositing humus and different microclimates); as well as - pisciculture, - aquatic plant cultivation, - animal breeding, - fruit cultivation, - alpine pasture maintenance and alpine and medicinal plant cultivation; there is also present forestry agriculture (integration of trees and bushes in agriculture), and complementarily, neither even tourism is excluded [24].

Conclusions

1. Generic awareness of the *bioharmonization process* means an important step for the future productive activity, especially if we take into consideration climate, ecologic, economic and social provocations, i.e. the complementary transition from green economy to blue economy, by obtaining alimentary and non-alimentary eco-bio-products, as an expression of bioeconomy and sustainable development found in the **Bio-Harmonist Ideology**.

2. The bioharmonized territorial module continues the logics of complex systems of „environment-economy” type, where structural components are in dynamic equilibrium (with harmonious relation, with ecologic efficacy and economic efficiency) between its elements. The bioharmonized module may be regarded as a **territorial "bioreactor"** (the analyses of raw materials, of the processed products and of waste) on bioeconomy principles, respectively of circular economy.

3. We practically find bioharmonization processes in all fields (economic, social, ecologic

ones), and bioharmonization practically exceeds production systems based on the quantity principle, by excellence aiming to the **quality principle**.

4. As important examples of bioharmonization we mention agri-food modules, emphasizing technical means and methods based on concepts of policulture and permaculture that in essence represent systems that **imitate nature**, they being based on bioharmonization processes, *structurally* on ecosystems and *functionally* on natural cycles.

References

1. Bell, D., 1967: Sfârșitul ideologiei în occident, in Political Ideas in the Fifties, London, 400-410.
2. Bogdan, A.T., Gruia, R., Toba G.F., Pasalau Carmen (2014): Scientific basis of a national, strategic and preference interest project, of agri-food bioeconomy, by innovative valorization of the Romanian territorial capital in the 21-st century, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Brasov, Romania, ISSN 1844- 8577, Vol.10 (2014), Nr.2, p.9-10.
3. Commoner, B., 1971: The closing circle. Nature, Man and Technology, Alfred A.Knopf Inc., New York.
4. Drăgănescu, M., 2007: Societatea conștiinței, Institutul de Cercetări pentru Inteligență Artificială al Academiei Române, ISBN 978-973-0-05307-4 în sursa: <https://www.scribd.com/>
5. Gaceu, L., *Tehnici moderne de uscare a cerealelor si plantelor tehnice*, Editura Universității “Transilvania” din Brașov, ISBN 973-635-662-0, ISBN 978-973-635-622-9, 203 pg., 2006.
6. Gaceu L., Gadei G. , Oprea O.B., Methodology for analyzing EU-conform label information content of meat products in Romania, Journal of Agricultural Informatics., pg. 1-6, 2014 Vol. 1, No. 4, Publisher: Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics (HAAI), ISSN: 2061-862X.
7. Gaceu L., Comparative study on European legislation about hygienic engineering and design, 7th Bioatlas Conference, Sibiu, Romania, 25-26 May 2018, Journal of EcoAgriTourism Vol.14 No.2, pp. 42-47, ISSN1844-8577;

- 8.** Gruia,R., 1998: Managementul eco-fermelor, Ed. Ceres București, ISBN 973-40-0425-5, p.112-115.
- 9.** Gruia,R. (2011): Study on energy resources integration and sustainability of the new modular agriculture pattern, Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, Gheorghe Asachi Technical University Iasi, ISSN 1582-9596, Vol.10., nr.8, p.1213-1219.
- 10.** Gruia,R., (2013): Bazele managementului si directiile viitoare de evolutie, Ed. Lux Libris, ISBN 978-973-131-230-9, 137-198.
- 11.** Gruia,R. et al., 2015: Studiu privind aplicarea conceptului de permacultură montană în Carpații Românești, lucrare susținută la Conferința CE-MONT Vatra Dornei, 18-19 sept.2015; - text l.ro & l. engl. - pentru publicare în Journal of Montanology
- 12.** Gruia, R., 2018: Theory of Bio-Harmonism, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Publishing Clarion Brasov, Romania, ISSN: 1844-8577 , Vol.14, Nr.2, pag. 17-31.
- 13.** Gruia, R., 2019: Ideologia bioarmonistă - izvor de regenerare politică într-o lume în schimbare, Editura Clarion, ISBN 978-606-94470-7-9.
- 14.** Gruia,R., Bogdan,A.T., Rey,R., Tobă,G.F. (2015): Integronic alimentation through whole natural food biodiversity, in relation with altitude Gradation, 2nd International Conference 'Economic Scientific Research - Theoretical, Empirical and Practical approaches', ESPERA 2014 Book Series: Procedia Economics and Finance ISSN: 2212-5671 Volume: 22/2015. Pages:114- 123.
- 15.** Herdon,M: et al, 2018: Development support of diversified food production and agrotourism by innovative agroforestry education, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.14, Nr.1, 81-87.
- 16.** Holzer, S (2010):Sepp Holzer's Permakultur , Amalietti&Amalietti, ISBN:978-961-6654-56-2.
- 17.** Martinez, R., Enríquez, J., West, J. (2003): DNA Space. The Geography of the Genome, *Wired*, June 2003, p. 160.
- 18.** Kovacs, T., Varallyai,L., Szilagy,R., 2018: Possibility of agri- and food industry applications in higher education, J. of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.14, Nr.1, 36-41.
- 19.** Rey,R., Gruia,R., Rey, A. (2015): High quality " mountain polyflora ", "mountain product" and the mountain family farm , "keys" for safeguarding and sustainable development of mountain agri-food economy, in a cooperative-associative system, for South-Eastern Europe " The International Conference "*Sustainable mountain regions: make them work*", Time: 14-16 May 2015, Place: the Rila Mountain resort of Borovets, Bulgaria.
- 20.** Smyth, S. J., Aerni, P., Castle, D., Demont, M., Falck-Zepeda, J. B., Paarlberg, R., Phillips, P. W. B., Pray, C. E., Savastano, S., Wesseler ,J., Zilberman, D. (2011): Sustainability and the bioeconomy: Policy recommendations from the 15th ICABR conference. *AgBioForum*, 14(3), 180-186.
- 21.** Tane,N., 2016: Erms of defining some notions of tourism - consensus and contradictions, Journal of EcoAgriTourism, Vol.12, Nr.2, 94-97.
- 22.** Wesseler,J., Spielman, D.S., Demont,M. (eds.) (2011): The Future of Governance in the Global Bioeconomy: Policy, Regulation, and Investment Challenges for the Biotechnology and Bioenergy Sectors. *AgBioForum*, 13(4), 288-290.
- 23.** Zugrăvescu, D., Munteanu,Fl., 2011: Planeta Pământ - Planeta vie, Institutul de Geodinamică „Sabba G. Ștefănescu” al Academiei Române, Catedra UNESCO de Geodinamică - România, Eagle Publishing House, ISBN 978-606-8315-29-4, 45-47, 63-66, 90-94.

e-Bibliografy

- 24.** <http://www.Gesundheitsbewegung.net> - Sepp Holzer ein Vorreiter der Permakultur zeigt seinen Permakulturhof den Krameterhof; Holzer,S. (2000): Permakultur - Landwirtschaft im Holzer,S. (2002): Aquakultur - Wasserwirtschaft im Einklang mit der Natur ; Holzer,S. (2002): Terrassen und Hügelbeete.

RECOVERY OF SOME VEGETABLE BYPRODUCTS WITH PHITOTERAPEUTICAL PROPERTIES FOR NEW DIETARY SUPPLEMENT

A. COZEA^{1*}, R. GRUIA¹, N. BORDEI²,
M. NEAGU², M. POPESCU²

¹ Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania, Faculty of Food and Tourism Brasov, str. Castelului no. 148
Tel / Fax: 0268 472222

² S.C.HOFIGAL EXPORT IMPORT SA Intrarea Serelor No.2, sector 4, Bucharest, Romania Research and
Development Department

*Corresponding author: andreea.cozea@yahoo.com

Abstract: This study proposes to exploiting some by-products resulted from food industry to obtain new products that presents both nutritional properties and certain phytoterapeutical effects. The new group of products resulted from the exploitation of natural by-products from getting virgin oil cold pressed (cakes), and which by their composition have phytotherapeutic properties and regeneration of the body, and represent in the same time a cheap raw material. Also, in the context of efforts of avoiding of pollutants of any kind, the material proposed for use by the Company Hofigal is ecologically grown and processed according to European GMP, TUV approved manufacturing company. The plant material proposed is : Thistle, Soy, Pumpkin, Seabuchorn, Rapeseeds, Flax, Hemp, Safflower. This plant material obtained after removal of fatty oil (in large amounts in seeds, over 30%) are more enriched in molecular species of interest such as proteins, gum inhibitors, amino acids, simple and complex sugars, plant fibers, enzymes, minerals, lipids, lipoproteins, lecithin, flavones, polyphenols, phytosterols, etc. The paper presents main constituents of byproducts analyzed.

Keywords: products, nutrition, phytotherapy

1. Introduction

Often unbalanced diet with calorique components excess (lipids, certain types of proteins) and biostimulating components deficient (vitamins, minerals and enzymes) leading to the gradual installation of nutrition disorders (obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease). As it is known how diet influences health and vitality significantly interfering body often troublesome in causing metabolic imbalance.

Economic and technical evolution of the last decades have led to excessive industrialization of human nutrition and public health implications, taken less into account from the beginning, leading to negative consequences.

Comparing the modern human condition created by nowadays civilization, contemporary scientists suggested coming back to nature from the standpoint that an informed society is possessing a highly advanced means of research

and knowledge, which has led and will lead, in further to the development of new types of food supplements.

Purpose and Objectives

Studies conducted by the authors took into account the capitalization of natural products with ecological origin (cakes) in order to achieve the balanced action of metabolic products affected by various harmful environmental factors and nutrition.

The study aims that nutritional „Biocomplex” constituted with byproducts beeing riched in nutrients so, the study pursuing the following objectives:

- Selection byproducts with increased phytotherapeutical and nutritional potential;
- Enzymatic and biochemical analysis of selected plant material;
- Development of technologies for superior utilization of this plant material.

2. Plant material and methods used

Modern scientific research considered as one of the current strategies of preventive and permanent protection of the body is the use of phytotherapeutic preparations and reducing the consumption of synthetic preparations.

The plant material used for this study is: Thistle, Soy, Pumpkin, Seabuckthorn, Flax, Hemp, Safflower, which due to their byproducts composition, act as „food-drug” and can be used successfully to prevent nutritional imbalances and currently motivate their use and their scientific investigation.

The plant material (cakes) comes from cold pressing of the seeds to obtain seeds by fulfilling spared extraction conditions (temperature below

40°C) as main constituents are preserved unaltered and plant enzymes (which due to labile proteins structure that are destroyed at simple heating to temperatures above 40°C).

Biochemical analysis and methods used meet the requirements of the Romanian Pharmacopoeia and European editions in use, supplemented with other Pharmacopoeia's and international literature.

3. Results and discussions

The plant material obtained after removal of fatty oil like byproducts, were analyzed in terms of content in proteins, residual lipids, enzymes, flavones, polyphenols, simple sugars and complex minerals.

Table 1. Results obtained from analysis of the main phytochemical compound in studied byproducts

No	Plant material analyzed	Determination						
		Humidity g/100g	Fatty substances g/100g	polyphenol acids (expr. Caffeic acid) g/100g	Flavones (expr. in rutin) g/100g	Proteines, g/100g	Direct reducing Carbohydrates g/100g	Total Carbohydrates, g/100g
1.	Thistle	7.24	3.61	0.31	0.04	15.64	7.93	16.10
2.	Soybean	10.00	4.71	Under limit	Under limit	31.72	8.85	24.92
3.	Pumkin	7.62	5.92	0.01	0.02	29.39	7.28	15.88
4.	Seabuckthorn	8.30	4.56	0.80	0.34	16.59	8.93	18.44
5.	Rape	8.20	7.18	0.15	0.90	14.08	8.13	17.00
6.	Flax	6.45	6.83	0.26	0.12	14.40	7.19	16.26
7.	Hemp	7.19	5.18	1.05	0.16	24.86	6.52	13.04
8.	Safflower	9.83	6.94	0.09	0.08	29.02	6.31	9.61

Table 2. Results obtained from analysis of the main minerals in some of the studied byproducts

No.	Plant material analyzed	Microelements (mg/100 g)									
		Ca	Mg	Na	K	Mn	Fe	Zn	Cu	Pb	Cd
1	Thistle	120	520	30	160	3.5	11	3.0	<5	ND	ND
2	Soybean	37	200	36	1500	2.5	15	7.0	3.0	ND	ND
3	Pumkin	14	400	23	1000	2.6	13.0	8.5	<2	ND	ND
4	Hemp	30	800	20	840	22	3.5	2.2	1.5	ND	ND
5	Safflower	50	400	3	450	3.2	5.0	5.0	2.0	ND	ND

The data obtained are remarkable high in content of protein in all byproducts (14-30%) which allows combinations and varied associations for food industry and in association with various medicinal and aromatic plant extracts for getting new dietary supplements with certain phytotherapeutic properties. Through such combinations can diversify the types of protein and amino acids sequence variation

in inhibitors, stimulating and helping biosynthesis processes in the liver and cellular regeneration process.

Experimental study using the technique of absorption spectrometry atomic emission under flame, revealed no heavy metals (lead, cadmium) of the material analyzed who is an important aspect, knowing that they have a harmful effect on the body by blocking the enzyme reactions and accelerate the oxidation of fats and fat-soluble vitamins from food. It was also shown

that all byproducts shows a beneficial mineral content in the body, such as manganese, potassium, iron, zinc, calcium, magnesium.

In further were analyzed the contents of some interest digestive enzymes is shown in Fig. 1 (amylase, lipase, protease).

Fig. 1. Determination of the main digestive enzymes of byproducts

Amylases belong to the subgroup - glycosidases are hydrolases which catalyze the hydrolysis of the α -1,4-glucan polysaccharides (starch, glycogen related oligo- and polysaccharides).

Lipases are the enzyme that hydrolyzes triglycerides of fats to fatty acids and glycerol using olive oil as substrate.

Proteolytic enzymes known as proteases, or peptidases, are enzymes that catalyze the hydrolysis of polypeptide chains.

Conclusions

1. Perform an extensive study on the composition of the byproducts obtained in food industry (cakes) for their superior use in food industry and in phytotherapy.
2. In the food industry can be used as a protein source in different mixtures, taking into account the overall composition of this beneficial plant material.
3. In Phytotherapy- can be used in food supplements in different enzyme remarkable combinations considering the content of some of these cakes. These Plant (cakes) used in Phytotherapy were priced much lower than currently used synthetic compounds that have harmful side effects on the body, thus can achieve a range of competitive products in terms of quality and the price.
4. Impacts of technology on the environment is raised by the fact that the technology for

obtaining vegetable oils and finished products is not polluting.

Two blank lines (10pt.+10pt.) are inserted between the keywords and the body of paper.

The departments and institutions the authors belong to are referred to in the footnotes (the bottom section of the page), under a separation line (40 mm long and 0.1 mm thick). The space between the separation line and the body of paper is identical with the space between two lines of text (no additional spacing). Use wildcards to identify footnotes.

The abstract must not exceed seven lines, and is placed into a single, centered, 110 mm column,

There is a blank line before and after a chapter title.

The paragraphs of each chapter start from tab position 3 (about 3 mm from the leftmost position on current line).

Line spacing within a paragraph and between paragraphs is single (one line).

The formulae, figures (drawings, diagrams, images) and tables are sequentially included in the text. The small ones are inserted within the paragraphs, and their width must not exceed the width of the column they belong to; the larger items are inserted on the entire page width, preferably on the top or at the bottom of the page.

In formulae, letters are italicized, functions, constants (e.g. \sin , \exp , $e = 2.71$, etc.) or Greek characters use regular font style; symbols in the body of the text use the formula style. After the last chapter, the list of references is displayed on two columns.

Each entry has an index number, followed by a full stop (do not use brackets). Each reference consists of the author(s)' surname and initials of first names, separated by a comma, the title of the original reference and, if applicable, the English translation of the title (within brackets), italicized, followed by the place, the publishing house and publishing year (for monographs), or the title of the periodical, volume number, issue number, and referenced pages (for periodicals).

Acknowledgement:

This paper is supported by the Sectoral Operational Programme Human Resources Development (SOP HRD), financed from the European Social Fund and by the Romanian Government under the project number POSDRU/159/1.5/S/134378.

- Postdoctoral scholar: *Dr. Andreea COZEA*

- Postdoctoral tutor: *Prof. Romulus GRUIA, PhD, PhD Supervisor*

References

1. Bahrim, G., Nicolau, A. - *Biotehnologia preparatelor enzimatică*, Editura Academică, Galați, 2002, p. 17-19;
2. Bairoch A., - "The ENZYME database în 2000" (PDF). 28 (1): 304-5;
3. Bugg, T., - *Introduction to Enzyme and Coenzyme Chemistry*. (2nd edition), Blackwell Publishing Limited, 2004;
4. Cherry, J.R., Fidantsef, A.L., - *Directed evolution of industrial enzymes: an update*. Curs. Opin. Biotechnol., 2003, p.14:438-443;
5. Flomenbom O, Velonia K, Loos D Et Al., - "Stretched exponential decay and correlations in the catalytic activity of fluctuating single lipase molecules". Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. UŞA 102 (7): 2005 p.2368-2372;
6. Georgescu, L.A. - *Enzimologie Generală*, Editura Academică, Galați, 2003, p. 62-117;
7. Grisham, Charles M.; Reginald H. Garrett,- *Biochemistry*. Philadelphia: Saunders College Pub. 1999 p. 426.

A METHODOLOGY FOR EVALUATION OF AGRITOURISM POTENTIAL. CASE STUDY: OLTINA VILLAGE

M. POPESCU^{1*}

¹Transilvania University of Braşov, Faculty of Food and Tourism, 148 Castelului, 500014 Braşov, ROMANIA

*Corresponding author: popescu.marius@unitbv.ro

Abstract: *The purpose of this paper is to present a methodology for evaluating the agritourist resources and their role for sustainable local development of a rural area. The research methodology is represented by bibliographic documentation and field research for to list and evaluate of agritourist resources. In this case, the Oltina village has a variety of resources (agricultural, natural, and cultural), which by association will emphasize the agritourist feature of this area, as a solution for sustainable rural management. Thus, it could be a tourist village as part of an agritourist trail along Danube, between Ostrov and Ghindăreşti, as a solution for sustainable development of the rural community from South-Western Dobrogea.*

Keywords: *agritourism, Oltina, potential, rural, sustainable.*

1. Introduction

The Oltina village is located on the right bank of the Danube River, in the area of Oltina Tableland, in South-West part of Southern Dobrogea territorial system [5]. It has a favorable geographic location which gives it a valuable natural potential. Although it is a village with agricultural profile, also it has some great natural and cultural heritage [8].

The geographical position, traditional farming activities, also the presence of natural and cultural resources are factors that may provide tourist valences of Oltina village [8].

The purpose of this paper is to identify and evaluate the agritourist resources of Oltina village, as well as the opportunities for their exploitation in order to sustainable development in rural area of this region.

2. Material and Method

Informations about agritourism potential needed for evaluation were obtained through bibliographic documentation and field research to Oltina administrative-territorial unit (ATU).

The methodology proposed in this study is based on *the methodology for assessment of tourist potential in administrative-territorial units of Romania* [12], *the European tourism indicator system* [11], *other methods* [3,9], also I applied *the method of multicriteria analysis* [1].

Resources of the agritourism potential of an administrative-territorial unit were grouped on 7 criteria, each with 5 indicators (see table 1).

The multicriteria analysis method was applied separately for each criterion. Thus, the indicators were compared and it was calculated the weighting coefficient.

By multiplying it with a note granted for the evaluation of each indicator, a value was obtained, which by summing with the values of the other indicators determined the final score of evaluating a criterion.

For each criterion was assigned a weight (10-30%), which by summing it will result an absolute value of 100.

The result of the evaluation of each criterion, correlated with the weighting assigned to it, and the sum of the values of 7 criteria, it will determine a real score of evaluation of the agritourism potential.

Depending of the value of the score obtained, it will rank the administrative-territorial unit according to the scale of agritourism potential, with 10 levels, and 5 categories (see table 2).

The evaluation of agritourism potential for administrative-territorial units of an area is a component that could be the basis for the elaboration of managerial solutions [4] or models of socio-economic development to local or regional level.

Table 1. Criteria of Agritourism Potential

Criteria		Weight(%)
C ₁	NATURAL GEOTOURIST RESOURCES (relief, climate, waters, flora and fauna, protected areas/natural landscape)	15
C ₂	ETHNOCULTURAL HERITAGE (ethnic structure of inhabitants, folk costumes/folklore, traditional architecture, traditional techniques/crafts, traditional events/feasts)	15
C ₃	TRADITIONAL FOOD PRODUCTS OF THE LOCAL COMMUNITY (agro-vegetable potential, agro-zootechnical potential, processing of vegetable products, processing of animal products, traditional cuisine)	30
C ₄	ANTHROPIC SIGHTS AND LOCATIONS (archaeological sights, religious sights, museums, monuments/statues, other)	10
C ₅	TECHNICAL AND MATERIAL INFRASTRUCTURE (utilities, local services, accommodation, meals and catering, therapeutical/leisure infrastructure)	10
C ₆	COMMUNICATIONS AND TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE (telecommunications, roads, railways, airport, river transport)	10
C ₇	TRADITIONAL CRAFT PRODUCTS OF THE LOCAL COMMUNITY (textile art, stone craft, wood craft, decorative arts, other)	10
Total		100

Source: own methodology

Table 2. Scale of evaluation of agritourism potential

Rank I	Rank II	Rank III	Rank IV	Rank V	Rank VI	Rank VII	Rank VIII	Rank IX	Rank X
≥90.00	89.99-80.00	79.99-70.00	69.99-60.00	59.99-50.00	49.99-40.00	39.99-30.00	29.99-20.00	19.99-10.00	<10.00
High		Medium-high		Medium		Medium-Low		Low	

Source: own methodology

Being located along Danube, in a tableland area, the agritourism valorisation of natural, cultural and agricultural resources from Oltina administrative-territorial unit will contribute to relaunch of the local rural economy.

Thus, for Oltina village exists opportunities of promoting as representative tourist village from Southern Dobrogea territorial system.

3. Research Results

The Oltina administrative-territorial unit is located in Oltina tableland, on the right side of Danube, with an area of 118 km² and 2,696 inhabitants (96.3% Romanians and 3.7% other ethnics), which live in 4 villages (Oltina, Răzoarele, Satu Nou, Strunga) [10].

The landscape is hilly nature, with altitudes up to 170 m, fragmented of short deep valleys, and terminate to river lake. This area is a part of continental-temperate climate, with average annual temperatures of 10.0-11.0°C and rainfall of 400-450 mm annually. It is an area with features of steppe and forest-steppe, climatic conditions favoring a vegetation of Mediterranean type. This region belongs hydrographic basin of the Danube (fig. 1) with

fluvial lakes (*Oltina-Iortmac* Lake) and short rivers [5].

The land use is represented by 11,762 ha, of which: 24.3% - lakes and wetlands, 12% - forest areas, 58.2% - agricultural lands (possible resources as support for agritourism) that includes - 76% arable land (especially for cereal and industrial crops), 22% grass-lands (for livestock), and small areas under 2% (vineyards, orchards) [10].

The tableland, slightly wavy, with gentle slopes and meadows have enabled the complex agricultural use. The meridional agro-climatic potential from Oltina area, it is favorable for vineyards (quality grapes and wines) and orchards (apricots, peaches, cherries), this village being a wine center from Ostrov Vineyard [8,9].

Due to the geographical location of the village on the right bank of the Danube (fig. 1), the traditional occupations are agriculture, livestock, fishing and beekeeping, less the trade and other services [2].

Oltina is a village with a strong Dobrogea's tradition, which has utilities that favors the development of agritourism activities. In terms of resources for agritourism, Oltina area enjoys a cultural heritage represented by archaeological or

religious sights. To these were added customs and traditions of the local population, traditional folk costumes specific to Danube Plain and South Dobrogea, traditional architecture of the country houses [6], local cuisine, traditional local feasts

and events. Also, it has a significant natural tourist potential that offers the possibility of developing a sector with positive results for the local economy [7].

Source: own figure

Fig. 1. Geographical location of Oltina ATU in Southern Dobrogea

In the rural area of Oltina stands out the contrasting territorial landscapes determined by relief, Danube, lakes, natural protected areas, rural settlements with cultural resources and specific socio-economic activities [8].

The agritourism potential of this area resulting from the traditional farming activities (viticulture, fruit growing, fish breeding, beekeeping or sheep breeding) associated with the presence of historical or religious sights, and local customs [4,7]. The features of the agritourism potential evaluation criteria are presented for each criterion.

C₁-Natural geotourist resources are represented by typical plateau landscape, the wetland of Danube with *Iepurașului* island, right arm of

Danube river, *Oltina-Iortmac* Lake (fluvial lake, protected bird area, 2,300 ha), *Bratca* and *Cetate* forests (fig. 1).

C₂-Ethnocultural heritage is represented by Romanians inhabitants, traditional folk costumes specific to Southern Dobrogea and Danube Plain, Dobrogea's traditional architecture of the country houses with features of transhumance from Transcarpathian area, values of cultural heritage, traditional techniques for fishing or beekeeping, building of fountains, local customs, events and feasts.

C₃-Traditional food products of the local community are represented by traditional farming (cereal crops, vegetables, viticulture, fruit growing, sheep breeding, beekeeping), 2 fishing

farms, 24 certified local farmers (processing of milk, dairy, fruits and vegetables), Romanian cuisine with Turkish and Bulgarian influences, fishery cuisine.

C₄-Anthropic sights and locations are represented by archaeological site *Altinum* Fortress, *Strunga* Monastery, orthodox churches in every village, Stone Fountain from the middle of XIXth Century, fountain with pulley and roof, other 7 fountains (the most from Dobrogea region), a traditional house proposed as small rural museum.

C₅-Technical and material infrastructure is represented by paved roads, water, energy, sewage system in progress, small rural markets, small guesthouse (with 6 places for accommodation), 2 fishery farms, 2 parks, opportunities for water sport.

C₆-Communications and transport infrastructure is represented by post office, fixed and mobile phone, radio-TV network, county road DJ391A (16km) for connecting with national road DN3 (Constanța-Ostrov), more than 20 km of local roads which connect all villages; the rutier acces is of 115 km to Constanța (5 buses/day), and 54 km to Cernavodă; the closer railway station is Cernavodă (54 km), and the International Airport of Constanța is located to 120 km; also, it is a small harbour at Danube, but with occasional using, especially for boats.

C₇-Traditional craft products of the local community are represented by wood and stone craft for building traditional houses, fiber craft

for textile art, but currently inhabitants must be reinvigorate them.

Table 3 shows the evaluation of agritourism potential with 7 criteria for Oltina ATU:

- for the evaluation of *Natural geotourist resources* criterion was accorded a score of 49.90 points and weighting of 14.76%;
- for the evaluation of *Ethnocultural heritage* criterion was accorded a score of 33.38 points and weighting of 10.13%;
- for the evaluation of *Traditional food products of the local community* criterion was accorded a score of 44.32 points and weighting of 26.48%;
- for the evaluation of *Anthropic sights and locations* criterion was accorded a score of 39.72 points and weighting of 7.66%;
- for the evaluation of *Technical and Material Infrastructure* criterion was accorded a score of 36.70 points and weighting of 7.19%;
- for the evaluation of *Communications and Transport Infrastructure* criterion was accorded a score of 35.68 points and weighting of 6.89%;
- for the evaluation of *Traditional craft products of the local community* criterion was accorded a score of 38.32 points and weighting of 7.70%.

By summing the values of 7 criteria it results a total of 278.02 points.

Table 3. The evaluation of agritourism potential of Oltina ATU

Criteria		Value	Wight(%)
<i>C₁</i>	Natural Geotourist Resources	49.90	14.76
<i>C₂</i>	Ethnocultural Heritage	33.38	10.13
<i>C₃</i>	Traditional Food Products of the Local Community	44.32	26.48
<i>C₄</i>	Anthropic Sights and Locations	39.72	7.66
<i>C₅</i>	Technical and Material Infrastructure	36.70	7.19
<i>C₆</i>	Communications and Transport Infrastructure	35.68	6.89
<i>C₇</i>	Traditional Craft Products of the Local Community	38.32	7.70
Total		278.02	80.81

Source: own methodology

The figure 2 shows a graphic model with seven axis reported to an ideal model of agritourism potential evaluation. Thus, with a weighting of 80.81%, Oltina ATU is included to the first category (*high potential*) of agritourism potential, according to the methodology presented in this study. Due to the existence of diverse tourist

resources, in Oltina rural area tourists may practice the following forms of tourism: *agritourism* by capitalizing on local products (bee, fish, and wine), *cultural tourism*, *ecotourism* (birdwatching), and *leisure tourism* (fishing or water sports).

Source: own figure

Fig. 2. Agritourism model of Oltina ATU

Conclusions

The Oltina village has natural and cultural resources that can highlight the local agritourism potential, but the weaknesses are the lack of accommodation infrastructure and the promotion of this area.

A priority goal of local authorities to the future development of the Oltina village economy must be an integrated strategy for recovery of the local heritage, the organization of guesthouses with traditional specificity, to establish of a tourist information center, and signaling of local sights.

The evaluation of the agrotourism potential of an administrative-territorial unit in a region, correlated with a diagnostic analysis, and the hierarchy of the ATUs at the local or regional level, contributes to the elaboration of an action plan for the socio-economic sustainable development of a territorial system analyzed.

An efficient management of agricultural, natural and cultural resources integrated in a polyvalent agrotourist trail along the Danube, between Ostrov and Ghindărești, could be a solution for sustainable socio-economic development of Oltina rural area.

References

- Bobancu, Ș.: *Creativitate și Inventică. Note de curs*, Universitatea Transilvania din Brașov, 2014
- Bordânc, Floarea: *Analiza regională a spațiului rural dobrogean*. București. Editura Universitară, 2008
- Ciangă, N.: *România. Geografia turismului*. Cluj-Napoca, Editura Presa Universitară Clujeană, 2001
- Gruia, R.: *Management și dezvoltare în industria turismului*. Brașov. Editura LuxLibris, 2017
- Iordan, I., Dobre, Silvia (coord.): *Podișul Dobrogei de Sud*. In: *Geografia României*, vol. V, București. Editura Academiei, 2005, p.758-790
- Nicoară, V.: *Dobrogea. Spațiu geografic multicultural*. Constanța. Edit. Muntenia, 2006.
- Nistoreanu, P.: *Aprecieri asupra fenomenului turistic rural*. In: *Journal of tourism Issue 3*, University "Ștefan cel Mare" of Suceava, 2007, p. 16-23
- Popescu, M., Gruia, R.: *Study regarding the management mechanisms for touristic integration of Oltina Plateau from Southern Dobrogea*. In: *Journal of EcoAgriTourism*, Vol. 12(2), Brașov, Transilvania University Press, 2016, p. 112-118
- Popescu, M.: *Aspects concerning of agri-touristic potential of Ostrov village, Constanța county*. In: *Lucrări Științifice Management Agricol, seria I*, vol. XIX(1), Timișoara, Edit. Agroprint, 2017, p. 193-198
- *** *Anuarul Statistic al județului Constanța 2017*. www.insse.ro
- *** 2016, ETIS toolkit for sustainable destination management, Comisia Europeana, http://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/tourism/offer/sustainable/indicators/index_en.htm
- *** 2016, Metodologie privind evaluarea potențialului turistic în unitățile administrativ-teritoriale de bază, http://www.mdrl.ro/_documente/dezvoltare_teritoriala/amenajarea_teritoriului/patn_elaborate/secVI/metodologie.pdf

ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA STRAINS FROM GOAT MILK FOR POTENTIAL USE IN THE PRODUCTION OF YOGURT

C. POPOVICI^{1*}, M. TIȚA², A. CARTASEV³,
R. BRINZA¹, N. BOGDAN³

¹Faculty of Food Technology, Technical University of Moldova

²Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, Food Industry and Environmental Protection, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania

³Scientific and Practical Institute of Horticulture and Food Technology, Republic of Moldova

*Corresponding author: crisrina.popovici@toap.utm.md

Abstract: In the presented research, the physico-chemical and microbiological characteristics of goat's milk were determined. The strains of valuable native lactic bacteria of the species *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* were selected with stable technological characteristics for the fermentation of goat's milk, corresponding to the requirements for lactic bacteria intended for the manufacture of yogurt. The scheme for preparing starter cultures and recommendations regarding the use of consortia of symbiotic cultures for the manufacture of goat milk yoghurt have been elaborated. Starter cultures were obtained for the manufacture of goat milk yogurt, with biotechnological properties characteristic for fermented dairy products.

Keywords: goat milk, lactic acid bacteria strains, yogurt.

1. Introduction

Balanced nutrition is a priority concern, in order to ensure and maintain the state of health and good functioning of the human body. Recently (in last decades), nutrition, as a science, has progressed in understanding the physiological and genetic mechanisms by which nutrition and individual components of food influence health. At the same time, it is a paradox that nutrition is essential to maintaining life, it can also be a cause of many chronic diseases.

Goat's milk has a promising source of protein, vitamins, minerals, and fatty acids [1, 2]. Due to its low lactose content, goat's milk has better digestibility, reduced allergenicity, [3, 12, 24]. The advantages of goat's milk are expressed through an advanced dispersion of lipid globules which increases digestibility, has a richer content of Ca, Zn, Fe more easily assimilable and contains less cholesterol, has a higher antioxidant properties which is beneficial to the human body, the fractionated composition of proteins is more homogeneous. Goat milk contains more unproteinized nitrogen, the proteins are of better quality, with a higher thiamine content than any other food and practically does not cause allergic reactions and digestive disorders. It is known that

α s1-casein - the main protein of cow's milk - is a potent allergen for humans. All these give goat milk products dietary and curative properties [4].

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Goat milk physico-chemical analysis

The main physico-chemical properties of goat's milk are: density, freezing point, pH, mass fraction of proteins, of skimmed dry matter, lactose and fat.

2.1.1. Density

Density is influenced by the dry substance content as well as by the ratio between the fat and non-fat matter. The milk density is between The title must be as short possible. If necessary, a subtitle is provided.

According to sanitary-epidemiological safety, the goats have a much lower disease risk, they do not suffer from brucellosis, tuberculosis and other diseases that affect cattle [5, 12]. From the goat's milk you get butter, yogurt, sour milk. A particular taste have fermented dairy products, that have a fine consistency and pleasant, specific taste. The goats farming has an important food potential, which must be exploited at industrial level.

On the national level, goat's milk is not used industrially, and there are no sour milk products from goat milk on the market place. In the Republic of Moldova, at the present time, no scientific results have been obtained regarding the use of goat milk.

At the international level, the proposed topic carries researches on the preparation and optimization of goat milk yogurt technology and manufacture [13-15]. In order to develop the industrial level of goat's farming, obtaining the high quality goat's milk products, is necessary to determine the milk quality clues and the harmlessness as a raw material. Therefore, the taken milk samples, obtained with technical-normative support from the individual household were investigated to physico-chemical and microbiological clues. The purpose of the research was the selection of lactic acid bacteria to determine the most promising combinations for use in the preparation of starter cultures for yoghurt manufacture.

The density increases simultaneous to the non-fat substance increase in the content. It decreases in proportion, opposite to the fat content increase. Knowing the density is important, both for detecting possible counterfeiting through milk diluting, as well as for determining the dry substance content.

2.1.2. Degreased dry substance

It is performed indirectly by calculation, respectively by reducing the fat content (F, %) from the total content of dry substance (D.S., %). Higher values may indicate: feeding with preserved fodder specific for the winter season; addition of sour cream in milk, addition of other substances (milk powder, starch, etc.) milk from animals at the end of the lactation period. Lower values may indicate: milk from animals at the beginning of the grazing period; excessive feeding with succulent fodder or green meal; counterfeiting by adding water.

2.1.3. Milk fat content

The fat content is determined according to MS ISO 11870 [25]. 10 ml of sulfuric acid is added in the butyrometer, as well as 5 ml of milk product and 6 ml of distilled water. Also 1 ml of isoamyl alcohol is added. The butyrometer is covered with a rubber stopper and then homogenized. After homogenization, the sample is centrifuged for 5 minutes at 1000-1200 rpm, then placed in the water bath at a temperature of 65° C. The fat content is read on the butyrometer stem and the indicated value is multiplied by 2,2.

2.1.4. Determination of milk protein substances

Protein substances in milk are an important source for both growing organism and the adult one, having a high biological and nutritional value due to its content in amino acids, both quantitatively and qualitatively, containing all the essential amino acids that the human body receives only with food. The goat milk proteins have a high level of digestion (95-97%). About 95% of the nitrogenous substances in milk are of protean (casein, lactalbumin, lactoglobulin.etc) and 5% of non-protean (amino acids, amides, etc.). The nitrogenous substances content gives information about nutritional and technological value of the milk as well as about its destination in processing [10].

2.1.5. Determination of lactose content in milk

Milk lactose is one of the components of the total dry extract representing about 35%. Lactose is an unstable compound undergoing fermentation under the influence of microorganisms contained in milk. In some cases, goat's milk contains a higher mass fraction of lactose, compared to the same indicator in cow's milk, but its molecule size in goat's milk is smaller and lactose contained in goat milk is more strongly attacked by the enzyme-lactase (β -galactosidase), produced by the starter culture. This could be an opportunity to use goat's milk for special adults and children diet [13, 14].

2.1.6. Freezing point or cryoscopic point of milk

The freezing point is defined as the temperature at which the milk freezes. For each percentage of added water the freezing point increases by 0.006 °C. The freezing point can be expressed in degrees (°H) or in degrees (°C). The value of the freezing point should be edited according to the acidity of the milk. The correction is progressive if the acidity of the milk is 7-8 °SH (Soxhlet-Henkel degrees) and regressive if the acidity of the milk is <8 °SH.

2.1.7. Ionic acidity (milk pH)

Due to the buffering capacity of proteins and mineral salts (citrates, phosphates), a sudden change in pH is observed, pH values may change from 4.5 to 6.5 [9]. The physico-chemical composition of goat's milk is conditioned by race, growth area and age, also by the nature of the feeding, the lactation phase, as well as the frequency and duration of the milking and the animal's health [15].

2.2. Microbiological analysis of goat milk

2.2.1. Number of coliform bacteria

The primary dilution is prepared from 1g of product through a series of decimal dilutions, so that it is possible to determine the estimated number of coliform bacteria or the quantity provided in the regulatory document for a particular product. Each dilution (in triplicate) is introduced into tubes with nutritional environment prepared according to GOST standard 30518 [19]. The tubes are thermostated at 37 ± 1 °C for 24 ± 2 hours. If gas bubble formation or turbidity is not observed, gas incubation is continued for a further 24 ± 2 hours. The tubes in which the formation of the gas is observed after 24 ± 2 hours or after 48 ± 2 hours are considered positive.

2.2.2. Number of coagulase-positive staphylococci (*Staphylococcus aureus*)

Contamination may occur during unhygienic milking, transmission of the pathogen agent through contaminated hands, and possible contamination of *S. aureus* (for example) in raw milk may occur from infection of the mammary glands.

2.2.3. Identification of pathogenic microorganisms, including *Salmonella*

Bacteria of the genus *Salmonella* can be present in the product in small quantities, with a large number of other bacteria in the family Enterobacteriaceae or other families. Therefore, prior enrichment of the culture, required for the detection of a small number of bacteria of the genus *Salmonella*, is mandatory. According to SM EN ISO 6579 Standard, 25 g of the product under analysis is heated to 37 ± 1 °C and suspended in buffered peptonate water, followed by incubation at 37 ± 1 °C for 18 ± 2 hours. The incubated cultures were seeded on the agar medium and thermostated at 37 ± 1 °C for 24 ± 3 hours [27]. Colonies suspected to be of the

Salmonella genus are subsequently identified by specific biochemical and serological tests.

Determination of these bacteria in goat milk is mandatory. According to veterinary standards, *Salmonella*-like bacteria must be absent in 25 ml of milk [20]. The presence of this microbiological indicator in milk shows its epidemic risk.

2.2.4. Total number of aerobic mesophilic germs (NTG / ml or UFC / ml)

Assessing the quality of all microorganisms in goat milk is a very difficult problem. Therefore, as a rule, the quantitative assessment is used first, that is, the total number of germs (NTG) in 1 ml of milk, or from the contemporary method, the total number of mesophilic aerobic germs and facultatively anaerobic colony-forming units (NTUFC). In case the microbial load does not exceed 106 / ml NTG (Total Number of Germs) the decision is made that milk can be used in the manufacture of food.

2.3. Statistical analysis

The results variation analysis was carried out by the method with application of Microsoft Office Excel program. Differences were considered statistically significant if probability was greater than 95% ($q < 5\%$). All assays were performed at room temperature, 20 ± 1 °C. Experimental results are represented according to standard rules.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Analysis of the physico-chemical properties of goat milk

The determination of the physico-chemical clues of the goat's milk was recorded using the EKOMILK Total Bulteh 2000 automatic milk analyzer. Physico-chemical characteristics of goat milk are shown in table 1.

Table 1. *Physico-chemical characteristics of goat milk*

No	Characteristics	Values
1	Fat mass fraction, %	3,58±0,19
2	Mass fraction of dry degreased substance (DDS), %	9,32±0,5
3	Protein mass fraction, %	4,1±0,11
4	Protein mass fraction, % (Kjeldahl method)	4,28±0,03
5	Lactose mass fraction,%	4,4±0,2
6	Cryoscopic temperature, °C	- 0,530
7	Density, g/cm ³	1,031±0,0028
8	pH	6,5±0,70

In goat milk according to ISO 8968-1: 2014 (Milk and dairy products - Determination of nitrogen content - Part 1: Kjeldahl method and calculation of crude protein content) was determined the mass fraction of proteins,%, which constituted 4.28 ± 0.03 .

It is known that the chemical composition of milk differs depending on season, feeding, age, lactation period. Also, at the beginning and at the end of the lactation, the fat content is higher, in the middle, when the productivity of the animals is maximum (the summer feed), the fat content decreases, the density of the milk grows at the beginning of the lactation period, the acidity (freshness) of the milk also grows during the summer period, which is related to the temperature of the environment [16-19].

The high content of skimmed dry matter in goat's milk indicates that it is better for technological processing. In some cases goat's milk contains the higher fraction of lactose, but its size in goat's milk is smaller and lactose of goat's milk is strongly attacked by the enzyme-lactase (β -galactosidase), produced by the starter microflora. This is a better opportunity to use goat's milk for special diets and for children nutrition [13, 14].

3.2. Microbiological analysis of goat milk

Milk samples collected under aseptic conditions were subjected to microbiological analysis. Microbiological control of raw materials is the most important step in the system of preventive measures to avert the infections through milk and dairy products consumption. Therefore it was necessary to determine the degree of

contamination of goat milk by different groups of microorganisms, to establish the microbiological harmlessness.

Milk contamination can occur from various sources, and the microbial load can be quantitatively and qualitatively quite varied, depending on the conditions under which milk is produced, handled and processed. Microorganisms reach food from natural or external sources as a result of processing and handling, until consumption. Milk microbiota consists generally of non-pathogenic microorganisms as well as facultative pathogenic or pathogenic. The category of non-pathogenic microorganisms includes lactic-acid bacteria, widely distributed in nature, which play an important role in the fermentation of many foods and feeds. Contamination of milk with saprophytic germs increases the risk of including pathogenic germs. Many pathogenic bacteria do not multiply in milk (*Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *M. bovis*, *Brucella*, *Rickettsia*), their danger is depending on the initial degree of contamination of the milk, its subsequent dilution, also treatments it is subjected to, time before consumption of milk and other factors. Other pathogenic germs (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, etc.) can multiply in milk. The metabolic activity of most pathogenic germs is inhibited at low temperatures, this is why it is very important to immediately cool the milk after it is obtained, until it is heated and further processed.

The microbiological characteristics of goat milk are shown in table 2.

Table 2. *Microbiological characteristics of goat milk*

No	Characteristics	Values
1.	Number of mesophilic aerobic and facultative anaerobic bacteria, UFC / 1cm ³	$5.4 \pm 1.9 \times 10^3$
2.	Salmonella content, in 25g / product	not found
3.	Number of <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> bacteria in 1.0g / product	not found
4.	Number of coliform bacteria, in 0.01g / product	not found

Analyzing the data presented in table 2 it was found that the number of aerobic mesophilic and facultative anaerobic bacteria in goat milk does not exceed 8.0×10^3 , which represent an admissible content and the presence of pathogenic germs like *Salmonella*, *Staphylococcus*, coliform bacteria milk is not detected.

As a result of researches to determine the physico-chemical and microbiological indices, it

can be seen that goat's milk is characterized by high technological properties and can be used to obtain yogurt.

3.3. Recognition and selection of valuable lactic bacteria strains for the goat's milk fermentation with high content of bioactive compounds

Particular attention has been paid in recent years to the selection of starter cultures of EPZ-producing lactic bacteria, which may not only be

a natural alternative source of food additives, which improve the rheological parameters of fermented dairy products, but also, important factors contributing to the adhesion of microorganisms and probiotics in the intestinal environment [21].

In the food industry EPZ plays an important role in the manufacture of dairy products such as yogurt, fermented cream, cheese. EPZs significantly improve the texture and stability of the final product, which increases the shelf life. With the help of EPZ-producing cultures, the synthesis (separation of whey) of yogurt and fermented cream is reduced [22]. EPZ is responsible for hydrophilic molecules that bind free water, which makes the final product less sensitive to synergy [23].

To prevent synergy, coagulated yogurt is prepared with higher concentrations of stabilizers (0.7%), as is the normal 0.3%. Yogurt drink is also mixed, being prepared from yogurt with a low dry matter content. The texture of the yogurt drink changes due to the mechanical action on the product, which requires the use of EPZ-producing starter cultures that ensure a stable structure.

The strongly filamentous stems generate the products with an unpleasant appearance when spinning from the spoon (that's why the spoon sensory analysis test was introduced); a similar sensation occurs by chewing when the clot is sticky and adherent to the palatin. Individual value has only the strains of the "thickening" group, the others will be used only in mixed cultures after preliminary tests [25].

EPZ starter cultures can be used for the production of yogurt drink as well as for the yogurt with low content of dry matter, lipids or even for the manufacture of skimmed yogurt. This type of crop forms have a more consistent (bonded) texture, higher viscosity, improves structure, prevents gel breakage and whey elimination.

The technology of acidic dairy products involves the fermentation of milk with pure cultures or bacterial consortia containing different strains of lactic bacteria. In this case, it is important that the strains used in the composition of the starter cultures are biocompatible and ensure the viable microbial cell number from 10^8 to 10^9 in 1 cm^3 (g). In the

manufacture of yogurt, it is recommended to apply EPZ-producing strains in starter cultures, which provide organoleptic and rheological characteristics, that are necessary for the finished products without the use of food additives.

It is known that multicomponent starter cultures possess higher biochemical action with high resistance to different negative factors compared to the starter cultures prepared from monocultures and offer completely new probiotic properties to the products [11]. Therefore the native strains of *S. thermophilus* have been used in consortia for the manufacture of yogurt with high content of bioactive compounds.

When developing lactic acid bacteria consortia for starter cultures, it is important to consider the relationship between strains and possible changes in microflora during the subsequent cultivation of dairy products. By combining different species of lactic acid bacteria and regulating the fermentation temperature, it is possible to obtain a product with the desired taste and aroma, texture and dietary properties.

In this regard, at this stage, the purpose of the research was the selection of lactic acid bacteria to determine the most promising combinations for use in the preparation of starter cultures for yoghurt manufacture.

In order to obtain the starter culture from the Ramurala Collection, two strains of *S. thermophilus*, CNMN-LB-79 were obtained, which were selected from the goat's milk in the thesis of doctor by Bogdan Nina: "Harnessing the microbial strains isolated from goat's milk for industrial application" and a CNMN-LB-50 strain that was selected as an EPZ-producing strain in the thesis by Dr. Cartasev Anatolii: "New native strains of *Streptococcus thermophilus* and their use in the manufacture of fermented dairy products".

The cultures were restored from the lyophilized state and appreciated according to the main technological criteria: the restoration duration, the appearance of the clot, the microscopic aspect of the cells, the acidifying activity in whole milk with the inoculum of 5% culture. The selected strains correspond to the requirements of fermentative activity, acidification of the active milk, relative viscosity, high EPZ content. The test results are shown in table 3.

Table 3. Technological properties of native lactic bacteria *S. thermophilus* strains

No	Characteristics	<i>Streptococcus thermophilus</i> Strains	
		LB-50	LB-79
1.	The restoration duration, hours	6±0,5	6±0,5
2.	The microscopic aspect	Cocci, associated in diplococci and different lengths chains	
3.	The clot appearance	Homogeneous, viscous, filamentous	Homogeneous, viscous
4.	Consistency	Creamy, dense	dense
5.	Elimination of whey	no whey elimination	
6.	Acidifying activity in whole milk, inoculum 5% culture		
7.	Duration of clotting, hours	4,0±0,5	5,0±0,5
8.	The titratable acidity, ° T	77±1,5	71±0,3
9.	Cinematic viscosity, cSt	41,7±1,7	47,4±0,5
10.	EPZ, mg / 100 ml	44,5±1,2	0

According to results from table 3, the technological properties of the native strains of *S. thermophilus* lactic bacteria manifested in goat's milk, shows that the strains have the appearance of homogeneous, dense consistency, without

eliminating the whey, and corresponds to the technological requirements for the lactic bacteria yoghurt manufacture. The microscopic aspect is shown in figures 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Microscopy of *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-50 strain

Fig. 2. Microscopy of *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-79 strain

According to the Technical Regulation the yogurt is a dairy product made by fermenting milk with starter cultures *S. thermophilus* and *Lb. delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*. Therefore, for the composition of the consortia of lactic bacteria in yoghurt manufacture (Food Technologies Directorate, IŞPHTA), native *Lb. bulgaricus* strains were selected and tested.

The *Lb. bulgaricus* bacteria is asporogenic, immobile, Gram positive, anaerobic or facultative anaerobic. They do not produce catalase, cytochrome oxidase - negative, do not reduce nitrogen, do not liquefy gelatin. They have a reduced proteolytic and lipolytic activity, fermenting lactose, maltose, sucrose (especially in the logarithmic development phase), glucose, fructose and galactose. It requires mineral

substances and all the vitamins from B group to growth. It develops well in the environment with pH 5.5-5.8, but also at pH 5.0. They can develop within wide temperature limits (5-53 °C), but the optimal temperature is between 30 and 45 °C.

The relationship between the two species in starter cultures is symbiosis, which is important for the formation of lactic acid, the typical taste and aroma of the product. The cultures were also restored from the lyophilized state and appreciated according to the main technological criteria: the duration of restoration, the appearance of the clot, the microscopic aspect of the cells, the acidifying activity in whole milk with the inoculum of 5% culture. The results are presented in table 4.

Table 4. Technological characteristics of *Lb. Bulgaricus* strains

No	Characteristics	<i>Lactobacillus bulgaricus</i> CNMN - Strains				
		LB-40	LB-41	LB-42	LB-43	LB-44
1.	Restoration time, hours	18±0,5	18±0,5	18±0,5	18±0,5	36±1,0
2.	The appearance of the clot	Homogeneous, viscose				
3.	Consistency	dense			moderately dense	moderately
4.	Elimination of whey	without whey elimination				with whey elimination
5.	The microscopic aspect	Separated bacilli associated in chains of different lengths				
6.	Acidifying activity in whole milk, inoculum 5% culture					
7.	Duration of clotting, hours	4,5±0,5	3,5±0,5	4,5±0,5	4,5±0,5	7,0±0,5
8.	The titratable acidity, °T	130±1,1	124±1,0	118±1,5	118±1,5	120±2,5
9.	Cinematic viscosity, cSt	17,41±0,5	15,41±0,8	26,84±1,0	18,55±0,5	11,13±0,1
10.	EPZ, mg / 100 ml	0	0	0	0	0

From the presented data we can conclude 4 *Lb. bulgaricus* cultures CNMN-LB-40, CNMN-LB-41, CNMN-LB-42, CNMN-LB-43 - were restored in the required time, according to the maximum requirements 20 hours. The restored cultures formed the shell in 3.5-4 ± 0.5 hours, with a homogeneous appearance, dense consistency, some slightly viscous, clean taste of fermented milk, with moderate titratable acidity between 89-94 °T. Stem *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-44 was restored with a delay of 16 hours, forming a moderate coagulation, which does not

meet the technological requirements and therefore cannot be applied in combinations for starter cultures intended for yoghurt manufacture. The product obtained by fermentation of the investigated strains had a low viscosity index between 11.13 - 28.84 cSt. Strains do not produce EPZ. For use in the composition of starter cultures intended for the manufacture of yogurt, the *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42 strain was selected. The microscopic aspect is shown figure 3.

Fig. 3. Microscopy of the *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42 strain

3.4. Obtaining selected strains for starter culture used in manufacture of goat milk yogurt with high content of bioactive compounds

It is from practice known that the manufacture of the yogurt presents frequent complications for the producers, because the consistency of the products is slightly damaged at different mechanical actions in the technological process

during transport and storage. Even more, the decrease in fat content influences the structural properties of the product, causing the elimination of whey and the formation of granules. As a rule, yogurt starter crops consist of *S.thermophilus* and *Lb. bulgaricus* having an average activity of acidifying the milk for 5-7 hours. Starter cultures were prepared according to the diagram shown in figure 4.

Fig. 4. Scheme of preparation of starter culture for the manufacture of goat milk yogurt

In the next step, the research was intent on the association between *S. thermophilus* strains within the species. In order to create combinations between strains of the same species, the strains selected by *S. thermophilus* were gradually associated in a 1:1 ratio, their compatibility at the level of acidifying and coagulating action being studied. The strains were inoculated into milk (20-30 ml). After incubation, until the clot was obtained, the obtained combinations were re-seeded twice in

sterile skimmed milk. Were selected associations, which have demonstrated intensive acidogenesis action - within 5 hours, with the formation of a homogeneous, dense, creamy or viscous coagulation with moderate filant. An association of strains was developed within the species *S. thermophilus* and investigated according to biotechnological indices: EPZ culture - *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-50 + *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-79. The results of the investigations are shown in table 5.

Table 5. Characteristics of strain associations within the *S. thermophilus* species

Duration of clotting, hours	The titratable acidity, °T	Viscosity, cSt	Amount of EPZ, mg / 100 ml	The appearance of the clot
3,5±0,5	71±2	100,23±0,85	53,4±2,1	O, V, F, D, C, fz

Note: O - homogeneous, V - viscous, nV - non-viscous, F - filant, F + - very filant, D - dense, C - creamy, fz - without whey.

The obtained data show that the association of *S. thermophilus* strains CNMN-LB-50 + *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-79, consisting of a strain that is EPZ-producing and 1 non-EPZ-

producing, exhibits high viscosity 100.23 cSt, fermenting milk in 4 hours, forming the dense shell, without eliminating the whey, with the titratable acidity 70 °T. As a result of examining

the association of *S. thermophilus* cultures it can be seen that the combination is successful and will be used in the manufacture of yogurt.

Fermented dairy products are very popular all over the world for their specific properties and beneficial effect on the human body. A crucial role in their manufacture is played by the biochemical processes caused by starter cultures. Therefore, the quality of dairy products depends on the quality of the starter cultures used in their production, which, in turn, is determined by the characteristics of the microorganisms within the starter culture.

The starter crops for the manufacture of yogurt should be made of *S. thermophilus* and *Lb. bulgaricus* species. Therefore, in the next stage, associations formed of lactobacilli and thermophilic streptococci were created and

studied. Based on the associations formed within the species, combinations of strains for starter crops were created for the manufacture of yogurt:

1. *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-50 + *S. thermophilus* CNMN-79 + *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42 - EPZ starter culture;

2. *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-50 + *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42 - EPZ culture starter;

3. *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-79 ++ *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42 - starter culture without EPZ.

There were 3 associations of strains of *S. thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* species, of which two EPZ starter cultures and one starter culture without EPZ as a control culture, which were investigated according to biotechnological clues. The results of the investigations are shown in table 6.

Table 6. The associations description of native strains for goat milk yoghurt

No	Duration of clotting, hours	The titratable acidity, ° T	Viscosity, cSt	Amount of EPZ, mg / 100 ml	The appearance of the clot
1	3,5±0,5	112±2	43,97±1,3	58,43±1,9	O, V, F, D, fz
2	3,5±0,5	118±1	70,25±1,72	47,49±1,3	O, V, F, D, fz
3	4,0±0,5	98±2	106,51±1,0	0	O, D, nF, fz

Note: O - homogeneous, V - viscous, nV - non - viscous, F - filamentous, D - dense, fz - without removing the whey.

Based on the data obtained from the formation of associations between the species *S. thermophilus* and *Lb. bulgaricus* in starter cultures for the production of goat milk yogurt, it is obvious that the starter culture consisting of 2 *S. thermophilus* strains CNMN-LB-50 + *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42 has a higher viscosity and faster clotting time than the starter culture consisting of 3 *S. thermophilus* strains CNMN-LB-50 + *S. thermophilus* CNMN-79 + *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42. In all the varieties, the

elimination of the whey was not detected, the titratable acidity was within the permissible limits and contained 98-118 ° T. Therefore, the associations formed correspond to the requirements stipulated for the starter cultures intended for the manufacture of fermented dairy products. Also, the elaborated starter cultures were examined microscopically to determine the ratio between *S. thermophilus* and *Lb. bulgaricus*. The results are shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Microscopic aspect of the formed associations, amplification x100

As a result of the research of the associations for the starter culture intended for the manufacture of yogurt, 2 starter cultures were selected:

1. YO1 - *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-50 + *S. thermophilus* CNMN-79 + *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42
2. YO2 - *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-50 and *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42;
3. YO3 - *S. thermophilus* CNMN-LB-79 and *Lb. bulgaricus* CNMN-LB-42.

The starter culture compounds were tested for the technological characteristics and symbiotic nature in the case of multicomponent cultures in order to select the ones with the highest prospects for use in the manufacture of fermented dairy products. The cultures were inoculated in goat milk within 5% amount.

At the initial stage, the acidogenesis activity of the native starter cultures was analyzed. The results obtained are shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Acidogenesis activity of elaborated native starter cultures

As a result of the studies on the acidification activity of the starter cultures for 8 hours of fermentation at temperatures of 40 ± 1 °C, it was found that the decrease of the acidity of the starter had a 5 hours of fermentation and values equal to 4.58 ± 0.02 - 4.31 ± 0.03 pH units. After 5 hours of fermentation, when the clot is already formed, the decrease of the activity of the starter culture continues in parallel with some small deviations.

After 8 hours of fermentation the active acidity has the following values: the pH of the cultures YO1 - 4.17 ± 0.05 , YO2 - 4.15 ± 0.02 , YO3 - 4.28 ± 0.01 , which after 8 hours they have not changed fundamentally, from where we can conclude that starter cultures will not cause the deterioration of the finished product during storage.

Conclusions

The technology of dairy acid products involves the fermentation of milk with pure cultures or bacterial consortia containing different strains of lactic bacteria. In the manufacture of yogurt, it is recommended to apply EPZ-producing strains in

starter cultures, which provide organoleptic and rheological characteristics, that are necessary for the finished products without the use of food additives. When developing lactic acid bacteria consortia for starter cultures, it is important to consider the relationship between strains and possible changes in microflora during the subsequent cultivation of dairy products. By combining different species of lactic acid bacteria and regulating the fermentation temperature, it is possible to obtain a product with the desired taste and aroma, texture and dietary properties. In the presented research, the physico-chemical and microbiological characteristics of goat's milk were determined. The strains of valuable native lactic bacteria of the species *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* were selected with stable technological characteristics for the fermentation of goat's milk, corresponding to the requirements for lactic bacteria intended for the manufacture of yogurt.

The scheme for preparing starter cultures and recommendations regarding the use of consortia of symbiotic cultures for the manufacture of goat milk yoghurt have been elaborated. Starter cultures were obtained for the manufacture of

goat milk yogurt, with biotechnological properties characteristic for fermented dairy products.

Acknowledgements

This work was done in the framework of Independent Project for Young Researchers 16.80012.51.23A "Innovative product from goat milk with high biological properties" (InoBioProd), cofounded by the Ministry of Agriculture and Food Industry and coordinated by the Academy of Science of Moldova.

References

1. Anuarul Statistic al Republicii Moldova. Chişinău, 2016, p.410.
2. Banu C. Tratat de industria alimentară: probleme generale. Bucureşti: Editura ASAB, 2008. 608 p.
3. Brevet de invenţie MD 865, A23C 9/12, A23C 9/127, A23C 1/00, A23C 1/08, A23C 23/00, C12R 1/46, C12R 1/225. Procedeu de obţinere a produsului lactat fermentat praf. Brevet de invenţie de scurtă durată/ Cartăşev Anatoli, BUREŢ Elena, COEV Ghenadii (MD). Cererea depusă 2014.06.30, BOPI nr. 1/2015.
4. Cartăşev A., Bureţ E. Culturi de *Streptococcus thermophilus* producătoare de exopolizaharide. În: Materialele Simpozionului Ştiinţific Internaţional „Agricultura Modernă – Realizări şi Perspective”, vol. 34, Chişinău, Moldova, 2013, p. 409-412. ISBN 978-9975- 64-246-0.
5. Cartăşev A., Bureţ E. Culturi de bacterii lactice producătoare de exopolizaharide. În: Papers of the Sibiu Alma Mater University Conference „Challenges for Science and Research in the Crisis Era”, sixth edition, vol. 2, Sibiu, România, 28-30 martie, 2013, p. 103-106. ISSN 2067- 1423.
6. Cerere de brevet de invenţie nr. s 2017 0090. Procedeu de obţinere a concentratului bacterian uscat pentru fabricarea produselor lactate fermentate. / Cartăşev Anatoli, Coev Ghenadii (MD). Cererea depusă 07.08.2017.
7. Cicala E.F. Metode de prelucrare statistică a datelor experimentale. Timişoara: Politehnica, 1999. 197 p.
8. Coev G., Bureţ E., Şveţ S., Cartăşev A. Valorificarea genofondului autohton de bacterii lactice cu destinaţie industrială. În: Conferinţa ştiinţifico-practică internaţională „Edificarea societăţii durabile”, Chişinău, Moldova, 2011, p. 209-213. ISBN 978-9975-64-221-7.
9. Costin G. Produse lactate fermentate. Galaţi: Editura Academica, 2005, 384 p.
10. Florea T., Costin G. Polizaharide. Chimia alimentelor. Galaţi: Academica, 2001, vol. II, p. 393-450.
11. Frioui M., Shamtsyan M., Gaceu L., Oprea O.B., Mnerie D., Rheological influence of (1-3)(1-6) mushrooms β -Glucan, used as flour substitution in bakery industry, Proceedings of the 45th intern. symposium on agricultural engineering „Actual Tasks on Agricultural Engineering”, pg. 377 – 384, Opatija, ISSN 1848-4425;
12. Gaceu L., Gadei G. , Oprea O.B., Methodology for analyzing EU-conform label information content of meat products in Romania, Journal of Agricultural Informatics., pg. 1-6, 2014 Vol. 1, No. 4, Publisher: Hungarian Association of Agricultural Informatics (HAAI), ISSN: 2061-862X.
13. Giurgiulescu L. Procese şi tehnologii în industria laptelui. Baia Mare: Universitatea de Nord, 2009. 260 p.
14. Guzun V., et al. Industrializarea laptelui. Chişinău: Tehnica-info, 2001. 488 p.
15. GOST 8.207-76 „Sistem de stat pentru asigurarea uniformităţii măsurătorilor. Măsurători directe cu observaţii multiple. Metode de prelucrare a rezultatelor observaţiilor. Principii de baza” Moldova-Standard”, 1992, 8 p.
16. GOST 3624-92. Lapte si produse lactate. Metode titrimetrice pentru determinarea aciditate. Chişinău: Departamentului "Moldova-Standard", 1992, 10 p.
17. GOST 3626-73 Lapte şi produse lactate. Metode de determinare a umidităţii şi substanţei uscate. Chişinău: Departamentului "Moldova-Standard", 1992, 10 p.
18. GOST 10444.12-88. Продукты пищевые. Метод определения дрожжей и плесневых грибов. Chişinău: Departamentului "Moldova-Standard", 1992, 6 p.
19. GOST 30518-97. Продукты пищевые. Методы выявления и определения количества бактерий группы кишечных палочек (колиформных бактерий). Chişinău: Departamentului "Moldova-Standard", 2000, 7 p.

20. GOST R 51455-99 Iaurt. Metoda potențimetrică de determinare acidității titrabile.
21. Hotărâre cu privire la Reglementarea Tehnică „Lapte și produsele lactate”. Nr. 611 din 05 iulie 2010. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 13.07.2010, Nr. 119-120.
22. Hotărârea nr. 221 cu privire la reguli privind criteriile microbiologice pentru produse alimentare din 16.03.2009. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 24.03.2009, nr. 59- 61, art. 272.
23. Metodica determinării efectului economic sau al unui alt efect pozitiv obținut în urma utilizării propunerilor de raționalizare. Nr. 146 din 13.06.2003. În: Monitorul Oficial al Republicii Moldova, 13.06.2003, nr. 116-120.
24. Oprea O.B., Gaceu, L., Gadei, G., Investigation methodology about labels information content of the meat products from Romania, in accordance with European Legislation, Proceeding of the international conference Agriculture Informatics, pg. 7-12, Debrecen, Hungary, 2013.
25. SM ISO 11870:2014. Lapte și produse lactate. Determinarea conținutului de grăsime. Linii directe generale privind utilizarea metodelor butirimetrice. Institutului Național de Standardizare, Chișinău, 2014, 16 p.
26. SM EN ISO 4833-1:2014. Microbiologia lanțului alimentar. Metoda orizontală pentru enumerarea microorganismelor. Partea 1: Tehnica de numărare a coloniilor la 30 °C prin metoda turnării în plăci. Chișinău: Institutul Național de Standardizare, 2014, 21 p.
27. SM EN ISO 6579-1:2017 Microbiologia lanțului alimentar. Metoda orizontală pentru detectarea, numărarea și tipizarea serologică a bacteriilor de genul Salmonella. Partea 1: Detectarea bacteriilor de genul Salmonella. Chișinău: Institutul Național de Standardizare, 2017, 65 p.
28. SM SR EN ISO 6888-2:2013. Microbiologia produselor alimentare și furajelor. Metodă orizontală pentru enumerarea stafilococilor coagulazo-pozitivi (Staphylococcus aureus și alte specii). Partea 2: Tehnică ce utilizează mediu de agar cu plasmă de iepure și fibrinogen. Chișinău: Institutul Național de Standardizare, 2013, 28 p.
29. SM SR ISO 15214:2014. Microbiologia produselor alimentare și furajelor. Metoda orizontală pentru numărarea bacteriilor acidolactice, mezofile. Tehnica numărării coloniilor la 30°C. Chișinău: Institutul Național de Standardizare, 2014, 15 p.
30. Vata C., Musca L., Segal R. Îndrumar de lucrări practice pentru biochimia produselor alimentare. Galați: „Dunarea de Jos” Foundation Publishing, 2000. 144 p.

EATING OUT GLUTEN-FREE – RESULTS OF A SURVEY

T. CSAPÓNÉ RISKÓ¹, B. BENYOVSZKI²

¹ Institute of World Economy and International Relations, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Debrecen, 138 Böszörményi Str, Debrecen, Hungary, 403

² Former BSc student of the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Debrecen, 138 Böszörményi Str, Debrecen, Hungary, 403

*Corresponding author: tunde.risko@econ.unideb.hu

Abstract: Coeliac disease is a serious medical condition and affects about 1 in 100 individuals worldwide, although there are variations in the rate of prevalence in the different countries. The only treatment for coeliac disease is a strict gluten-free diet. Despite strict adherence to the gluten-free diet at home, eating out can often amount to a serious health hazard. Efforts to completely eliminate foods containing gluten from the diet when eating out can be quite difficult in certain cases. Eating is a means of social interaction not only a physiological process of meeting an individual's nutritional needs. Thus social gatherings, holidays and other special occasions can cause stress for people with coeliac disease. These people often feel isolated, shame and being a bother, face ignorance, fear about contamination, and as a result dissemble their condition and take risks when eating out. If people with coeliac disease are going out to eat, it is advised to call the restaurant or check their website ahead to see if they have gluten-free options. If they are attending a catered event, it is advised to check if they can request a gluten-free meal prior to the event, etc. The aim of our empirical research was to investigate the eating out possibilities and behaviour of people with coeliac disease, as well as to explore their satisfaction with gluten-free restaurants nowadays in Hungary. The online survey was carried out in Spring 2018 among people with coeliac disease in Hungary (N=342). The study revealed that majority of respondents regularly visit restaurants. When choosing a restaurant the most important aspects are: safe gluten-free dining, quality of service, menu, price, location. There is a lack in gluten-free restaurants in Hungary. Respondents are not satisfied with the gluten-free restaurants. When choosing a restaurant the majority of respondents check the restaurant online to see if they have gluten-free options. They are willing to pay more and travel further for a restaurant where they can eat safely gluten-free.

Keywords: celiac disease, gluten-free, eating out.

1. Introduction

Some people are intolerant of certain foods in their diet. Their reactions can vary from mild to severe and possibly life threatening. Allergy is an example of this type of intolerance. An increasing number of people are being diagnosed with food allergies. The number of sufferers has increased fourfold over the past 20 years so that 30% of adults will develop an allergy in their lives and 40% of school children already have at least one allergy. If a person has been identified as having allergy to a certain food item, he/she should avoid that food. Although it is far not easy when the public purchases so many products that have already been prepared. The most common foods causing allergic reaction include nuts, fish

and shellfish, eggs, dairy products, soya and (Pratten, 2003 and Pratten, 2004).

1.1. Coeliac disease and the gluten-free diet

Coeliac disease is a chronic inflammatory disorder of the small bowel that affects 1% of the population (Demirkesen et al., 2010 in Ozola – Straumite, 2014; Sanders et al., 2003 in Aziz et al., 2014). People with coeliac disease react to the gluten in wheat and some other cereals in such a way as to damage the lining of their small intestine and reduce their ability to absorb enough food for their needs. The disorder can appear either in childhood, affecting growth and development, or in adulthood. The symptoms can include chronic diarrhoea, weight loss, tiredness, poor growth (Craciun et al., 2009; Pratten, 2003).

Epidemiological studies carried out in the previous decade have revealed the fact that coeliac disease is one of the world's most common life-long diseases (Jones and Green, 2010 in Regnerová et al., 2015). The general prevalence is up to 1:10-200 (Páv, 2006 in Regnerová et al., 2015). Effective treatment requires a strict gluten free diet. Patients on a gluten free diet experience substantial and rapid improvement of symptoms (Aziz et al., 2014; Pratten, 2003; Murray et al., 2004 in Regnerová et al., 2015). The grains to be avoided on a gluten-free diet are wheat, barley and rye. The gluten-free diet is not an easy undertaking, since these grains are the main ingredient in various foods.

Wheat is the basis of main grain-based foods, including breads, pasta, cakes, cookies, pastries and many snack foods. Wheat is often used as a thickener for sauces and gravies as a coating for meat and fish and as an additive for stabilizing, flavouring and other functions. Barley malt is often used as a flavouring agent in a variety of goods, including corn-based and rice-based cereals, candies and syrups. Rye is used less commonly by the food industry, except for making rye bread and crackers (Ozola – Straumite, 2014; See et al., 2015). Adhering to a gluten-free diet is challenging. Inaccurate or incomplete labelling of food ingredients, cross-contact with gluten-containing foods and the need to rely upon others to help determine if food is safe may all lead to gluten ingestion. Ingestion of gluten by persons trying to follow a gluten-free diet appears to be fairly common. In cross-sectional studies up to 50% of persons with coeliac disease trying to follow a gluten-free diet report consuming gluten either intentionally or unintentionally (Silvester et al., 2016 and Hall et al., 2013 in Silvester et al., 2016). Biagi et al. (2009) (citing Case, 2005; Mayer et al, 1991; Ljungman and Myrdal, 1993; Greco et al., 1997; Rashid et al., 2005; Karajeh et al., 2005; Ciacci and Mazzacca, 1998; Collin et al., 2004) also report that an absolute and complete gluten-free diet is unrealistic due to the lack of sufficient information, lack of knowledge of the problem on the part of chefs and other individuals working in the catering sector, and also to the fact that gluten may be present in packaged foods considered to be gluten-free.

Coeliac disease changes the life not only the patients, but their families' life also. It is common that in addition to supporting and understanding this condition and diet, family

members adjust their diet to the diet followed by the coeliac family member and exclude products containing gluten from their consumption also (Ozola and Straumite, 2014).

The study of Sverker et al. (2007) explored dilemmas experienced by close relatives when a family member has coeliac disease. Three main categories of coeliac dilemmas were identified:

- 'Disease-related worries' such as bad consistence, anxiety, witnessed vulnerability
- 'Management of daily life' such as double domestic work, restricted freedom of action, preferential right of interpretation
- 'Disturbances in social life' such as lack of information, lack of knowledge, lack of understanding.

The dilemmas were experienced in the arenas:

- 'Within the family'
- 'In social relations with friends and relatives'
- 'In interaction with service professionals in restaurants and shops'

Most gluten-free products are 2-3 times more expensive than the conventional ones. Their availability is limited, especially in less developed areas. Many supermarkets provide now gluten-free foods, although these special food are not universally available especially in small shops (West et al., 2014 and Kang et al., 2013 and Rubio-Tapia et al., 2012 in See et al., 2015).

1.2. Gluten-free labelling

The Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers entered into application on 13 December 2014. The obligation to provide nutrition information has to be applied from 13 December 2016. The new law combines 2 Directives into one legislation:

- [2000/13/EC](#) - Labelling, presentation and advertising of foodstuffs (applicable until 12 December 2014)
- [90/496/EEC](#) - Nutrition labelling for foodstuffs.

Some key changes:

- Improved legibility of information (minimum font size for mandatory information);
- Clearer and harmonised presentation of allergens (e.g. soy, nuts, gluten, lactose) for prepacked foods (emphasis by font, style or background colour) in the list of ingredients;

- Mandatory allergen information for non-prepacked food, including in restaurants and cafes;
- Requirement of certain nutrition information for majority of prepacked processed foods;
- Same labelling requirements for online, distance-selling or in shop retail (ec.europa, 2019).

Service providers in the catering industry can provide guests with allergen information in several ways. The staff personally should be able to supply details to guests. Regarding menus they can provide information with listing the allergens together with the introduction of the certain meal literally with numbering them or with pictograms.

The term gluten-free does not refer to the total absence of gluten. In the definition of gluten-free, some residual amount of gluten is allowed. This amount is strictly regulated by the Codex Alimentarius Standard. The EU Commission Regulation No. 41/2009 recommends the products not exceeding 20 mg/kg of gluten should be considered gluten-free (Ozola – Straumite, 2014). This definition applies both to products gluten-free by nature and to foods containing industrially purified wheat starch (See et al., 2015).

It is important to emphasise that gluten is often found in many food products that one would not expect, and gluten containing ingredients can be found in almost any processed food product. Therefore, it is important to always check food labels. Individuals with coeliac disease have make their purchases with caution and look for certified gluten-free products (Csapóné et al., 2017). People with coeliac disease must become expert label readers, they must check labels at each purchase. When shopping an average person with coeliac disease spends an additional 10-20 hours per month reading food labels (Pietzak, 2005 in See et al., 2015).

1.3. Cross contamination

Cross contamination occurs when gluten-containing food comes into contact with gluten-free food. Table 1 shows some examples of cross-contamination. As regards gluten-free restaurants, all the ingredients must originate from gluten-free sources, the storage of ingredients and the preparation and serving of meals must be safely gluten-free.

Table 1. *Common sources of cross contamination*

Location	
Field	origin of seeds; crop rotation; grains grown in adjacent fields; grains harvested on shared equipment; grains shipped together
Factory or retail	products stored or processed in the same plant; products made on shared equipment; open bins in food co-ops; damaged packaging; damaged take-away or home delivery boxes
Home	shared toaster; cutting boards; counter tops; colander; cupboards; shared spreads (butter, margarine); shared utensils and kitchen equipment; oil used to deep fry
Restaurant	storage of ingredients; grill; deep fryers; salad bar; serving utensils; food handling by unaware employees

Source: See et al., 2015; Csapóné and Péntek, 2018

1.4. Eating out gluten-free

The consumption of food is part of human nature and essential condition for life. Food consumption is joyful and pleasurable activity, deserving greater attention especially in connection with health (Nagyová et al., 2009 in Regnerová et al., 2016). Eating is more than just a physiological process of meeting an individual's nutritional needs, but also a means of social interaction (Sverker et al., 2005 in Aziz et al., 2014). People with coeliac disease often report isolation, shame wide-spread ignorance, fear of contamination and being a bother and as a result some have avoided disclosure of their

condition and have subsequently taken risks when having to eat out (Lee et al., 2012 and Zarkadas et al., 2013 and Karajeh et al., 2005 and Sverker et al., 2005 and Addolorato et al., 2008 and Whitaker et al., 2009 and Taylor et al., 2013 and Rose and Howard, 2014 in Aziz et al., 2014).

Gluten-free diet adherence is the most challenging in the social realm, where coeliac patients must self-identify and rely on others when ordering at a restaurant or eating at another person's home (Silvester et al., 2016).

The gluten-free diet often limits social interactions. Eating out or travelling is always complicated because of the availability of gluten-

free meals and the fear of possible gluten contamination (See et al., 2015). The simple act of choosing a meal from a menu can become a complicated task to avoid gluten and can even involve fear over communicating with the staff. Some patients even fear their condition will get worse as the result of innocent mistakes made while eating at a restaurant (Cureton, 2006 in Regnerová et al., 2016). As a summary we can say that visiting a restaurant can often amount to a serious health hazard (Bryan 2012 in Regnerová et al., 2016).

An increasing number of people are eating in restaurants, fast food restaurants, bars, etc. The catering industry is going to encounter an increasing demand for special meals to serve those with food allergies (Pratten, 2003 and Pratten, 2004). The increasing interest towards gluten-free meals has lead restaurants to offering gluten-free options to their guests. Karajeh et al. (2005) in See et al. (2015) reports that the patients' worries have been justified as it has been proven that, in the UK, chefs' knowledge about coeliac disease has been lower than that of the general public.

As regards travelling, many travel websites and mobile applications identify gluten-free friendly restaurants, hotels, cruises and grocers near one's travel destination (See et al., 2015).

The website of the Hungarian Coeliac Society provides reliable information on the availability of gluten-free restaurants, pizzerias and hotels in Hungary. All those businesses are taking part in their "Restaurant Project". They all serve gluten-free dishes (Iiszerzekený, 2019).

Managing allergen risks is a shared responsibility of all the stakeholders and requires a consistent approach across the industry in order

to be effective. The food industry and the tourism and catering sector must ensure that allergenic ingredients are declared and accidental residual allergen levels are safe for the vast majority of allergic consumers (Craciun et al., 2009).

Despite strict adherence to gluten-free diet at home, a large proportion of individuals admit to intentional dietary indiscretions when away from home, 81-88% at social events, 82-88% at restaurants and 58-67% with friends (Lee et al., 2012 in Aziz et al., 2014). These violations inevitably lead to health problems and may account for persisting chronic inflammation (Lee et al., 2013 in Aziz et al., 2014).

2. Material and methods

The aim of our empirical research was to investigate the eating out possibilities and behaviour of people with coeliac disease, as well as to explore their satisfaction with gluten-free restaurants nowadays in Hungary. The online survey was carried out in Spring 2018. The questionnaire, including 28 questions, was shared in closed gluten-free Facebook groups. The first question was a filtering question: 'Do you have coeliac disease?' Altogether 388 persons filled in the questionnaire, but only 342 answered 'yes' to the filtering question. Thus the sample size is 342. The questionnaire included Likert Scale (1-5) and checkboxes questions. The filled in questionnaires have been processed and evaluated with Microsoft excel programme.

As regards the gender distribution of the sample, ratio of female and male is 92,1 % (315prs) and 7,9 % (27prs) respectively. We have to add, that in Hungary gender distribution of patients with coeliac disease is: female (81%) – male (19%) (Vojnits, 2012).

Fig. 1. Age distribution of the sample (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

As Fig. 1 shows most respondents belong to the 26-35 and 36-45 age groups.

Fig. 2. Educational background of the respondents (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

Most respondents have college or university degree (49,2%) or high school degree (37,4%) (Fig. 2). As regards the place of residence of

respondents (Fig. 3), we can state that all the NUTS 2 regions of Hungary are represented in the sample.

Fig. 3. Distribution of the sample: Place of residence (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

As regards the legal status of respondents (Fig. 4), most of them are white-collar workers (42,70%).

Fig. 4. Distribution of the sample: Legal status (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

As regards the perceived income level of respondents (Fig. 5), most of them considered themselves as having average income.

Fig. 5. Distribution of the sample: Perceived income level (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

3. Results and discussion

The first questions referred to general restaurant visiting habits. It was asked if they visited restaurants at all. 95% of respondents answered ‘yes’. It means that although they have coeliac disease they visit restaurants, although it might be dangerous to them. We asked our respondents with whom they usually visited

restaurants. They could mark more than one option at this question. As Fig. 6 shows primarily they visit restaurants with their family members (307 answers), followed by colleagues (183 answers) and friends (68 answers). It is not common visiting restaurants alone among the respondents.

Fig. 6. ‘With who do you usually visit restaurants?’ (Number of answers) (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

With the next question we wanted to find out how they choose a restaurant. They had to rate (1-5) the following options: safe gluten-free dining, price, easy to reach, variable menu, quality of service on a Likert scale 1-5. As Fig. 7

shows, safe gluten-free dining is extremely important for the respondents although the quality of service and the variable menu is also important for them.

Fig. 7. 'How important are these aspects to you?' (Number of answers) (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

We wanted to find out how they collect information before visiting a restaurant. Our respondents prefer collecting information on the Internet (61,7%). It is the fastest way to collect information. Nowadays most households have internet access and most restaurants have a website, introducing the offered meals, drinks

and services. They can also communicate there if they are prepared to serve guests with special dietary needs. Among the 'other' answers we have to mention the answer: 'at the restaurant personally' or 'in Facebook groups'. Results are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. 'How do you collect information before visiting a restaurant?' (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

We also asked them how long they stay at a restaurant usually. As Fig.9 shows the

respondents usually spend 1-2 hours at the restaurant occasionally.

Fig. 9. 'How long do you usually stay at a restaurant?' (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

We wanted to find out their opinion on the availability of gluten-free restaurants in Hungary. Almost 40% of respondents believe that there is

only a few of them in Hungary (Fig. 10). To answer this question they could use a Likert scale 1-5.

Fig. 10. Availability of gluten-free restaurants in Hungary

Source: own research, 2018

We also asked them on the availability of gluten-free restaurants in their NUTS2 region. To answer this question they could use a Likert scale 1-5 again. 32,2% of respondents answered that the availability of gluten-free restaurants in their region is very poor. Only 4,6% answered 'very good' to this question. As regards the NUTS 2

regions of Hungary, respondents living in the Central Hungary region and in Budapest are the most satisfied. The least satisfied respondents are living in the Southern Great Plain and Northern Great Plain regions. Answers can be seen in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Availability of gluten-free restaurants in the NUTS2 region of the respondent (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

We asked our respondents on the quality of gluten-free restaurants. They could answer this question on a Likert scale 1-5. Almost 40% of the

respondents believe that the quality of gluten-free restaurants is average ('3'). Results can be seen in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12. Satisfaction with gluten-free restaurants (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

As regards the affordability of gluten-free restaurants, most respondents believe that they are slightly or too expensive. Results can be seen in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Affordability of gluten-free restaurants (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

We also asked them about the deliciousness of gluten-free meals served in restaurants. They could answer this question by using a Likert scale 1-5. Results are shown in Fig. 14. Most respondents believe that the deliciousness of these meals are average or good.

Fig. 14. Deliciousness of gluten-free meals (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

As regards the menu of gluten-free restaurants, 34,5 % of respondents believe that their level is of average. Regarding the deliciousness of gluten-free meals and the menu of gluten-free restaurants we have to point out that it is a great challenge to eliminate gluten-containing ingredients from the original recipes and substitute them with gluten-free ingredients. The taste, texture and smell of these meals are obviously different from the conventional ones. If

a restaurant 'makes up, invents' a good recipe, it offers that meal for a long time. Although they are continuously working on new recipes. Results can be seen in Fig. 15.

We asked our respondents if they had any health problem after consuming their meals in a gluten-free restaurant. Almost 10% answered 'yes'. We believe that this is high ratio, in a gluten-free restaurant such problems should not be experienced.

Fig. 15. The menu of gluten-free restaurants (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

We asked our respondents about the first information source on gluten-free restaurant. As we expected, Internet is the main source of information. A reliable information source for them is the gluten-free Facebook groups. In these

groups people with the same problems share information, like evaluating food or restaurants, availability of restaurants at a certain location, etc. Results can be seen in Fig. 16.

Fig. 16. First source of information on gluten-free restaurants (N=342)

Source: own research, 2018

Conclusions

The life of patients with coeliac disease is rather complicated. Considerable part of the society, including friends, colleagues, people working in the tourism and catering sector do not understand the disease and the consequences of consumption of gluten. The circle of people requested to take up the training should be broadened with staffs of kindergartens and schools, as well.

Most respondents with coeliac disease visit restaurants, which means that they are potential guests for restaurants just like healthy guests. If a family or other group is planning to visit a restaurant they prefer the ones where everyone in the group, including the member with special dietary needs can safely eat. Since the number of people with special dietary needs is continuously increasing, restaurants must follow this trend and

offer dining options to these guests as well. People with coeliac disease safe gluten-free dining is extremely important, thus they prefer gluten-free restaurants. The availability of gluten-free restaurants is weak in Hungary and most respondents are not satisfied with them. Central Hungary is the region where respondents are satisfied with the availability of gluten-free restaurants. There is a need in Hungary to establish more gluten-free restaurants where people with such dietary needs can safely eat. These restaurants are relatively expensive. Most respondents collect information on the Internet before visiting a restaurant. Thus it can be suggested that restaurants should have attractive, informative and up-to-date websites and if they are prepared to serve guests with special dietary needs they should communicate it obviously.

10% of our respondents experienced health problems after consuming their meals in a gluten-

free restaurant. It would be reasonable and desirable to develop a mobile application to share information on safe gluten-free restaurants, hotels, etc. It could be community application that people with coeliac disease could download to their mobile phones. When they visit such a gluten-free restaurant, the application gets activated and guest could share their experiences. Since symptoms may appear later, the programme would appear in the 'inform menu' and it would be possible to add the experiences even later, when the experiences are reliable. From these data, information could be provided with an ageing algorithm. These information would be available to everyone and users could decide if they want to visit a certain place or not. The ageing algorithm would ensure that information are based on up-to-date data. We believe that such an application would be useful for all partners (people following a gluten-free diet and service providers in the tourism and catering industry). In the next stage of our investigation we are planning to develop and test this application. It is hoped that though this application the ratio of people with negative experiences in a gluten-free business would be even lower.

References

1. Kassargian, Aziz, I., Karajeh, M. A., Zilkha, J., Tubman, E., Fowles, C., Sanders, D. S. (2014): Change in awareness of gluten-related disorders among chefs and the general public in the UK: a 10 year follow-up study. *European Journal of Gastroenterology & Hepatology*. Vol. 26 No. 11, pp. 1128-1233;
2. Biagi, F., Andrealli, A., Bianchi, P. I., Marchese, A., Klersy, C., Corazza, G. R.: A gluten-free diet score to evaluate dietary compliance in patients with coeliac disease. *British J. of Nutrition* (2009), 102, pp. 882-887;
3. Cracu, I., Ignat, E., Marculescu, A., Badea, M., Gaceu, L., Restani, P., Bucchini, L. (2009): Risk management for food allergens in cereals and derivatives. *Proc. Rom. Acad., Series B*, 2009, 2-3, pp. 175-178;
4. Csapóné, R. T., Péntek, Á., Wiwczarowski, T.: Bread consumption habits in the gluten free diet. *APSTRACT* Vol. 11. Number 3-4. 2017. pp. 113-120;
5. Csapóné, R. T., Péntek, Á.: Kenyér és péksütemény fogyasztási szokások a gluténmentes diétában. *The Hungarian Journal of Nutritional Marketing*. 2018/1. pp 77-89;
6. Ozola, L., Straumite, E.: Characteristic of gluten-free products: Latvian consumer survey. *International Journal of Social, Behavioural, Educational, Economic, Business and Industrial Engineering*, 2014, Vol: 8, No: 6, pp. 1848-1852;
7. Pratten, J. D.: Food allergies: a problem for the catering industry. *British Food Journal*. Vol. 105 No. 4/5, 2003. pp. 279-287;
8. Pratten, J. D.: Food allergies and the UK catering industry. *Journal of Industrial Training*. Vol. 28 No. 6, 2004. pp. 490-498;
9. Regnerová, O., Sálková, D., Varvazovská, P.: The availability of food for a gluten-free diet and possibilities at dining establishments. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*. 2016, Vol. 64 No. 4, pp. 1365-1372
10. See, J. A., Kaukinen, K., Makharia, G. K., Gibson, P. R., Murray, J. A.: Practical insights into gluten-free diets. *Nature Reviews. Gastroenterology & Hepatology*. 2015, Vol. 12 pp. 580-591
11. Silvester, J. A., Graff, L. A., Rigaux, L., Walker, J. R., Duerksen, D. R.: Symptomatic suspected gluten exposure is common among patients with coeliac disease on a gluten-free diet. *Aliment Pharmacol Ther* 2016; 44: 612-619
12. Vojnits, B.: Bármely életkorban lecsaphat a lisztérzékenység. 2012. http://semmelweisfigyelohu.hu/osszes_kiemelt_cikk/hir/3060 (Accessed: 17 Jan. 2018)
13. ec.europa (2019): https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/labelling_nutrition/labelling_legislation_en
14. liszterzékeny: GF Hotels, Restaurants and Pizzerias. <http://liszterzeken.hu/tiki-index.php?page=%20GF%20Hotels%2C%20Restaurants%20and%20Pizzerias&structure=%20Gluten-free%20in%20Hungary> (Accessed: 31 July 2019).

FOOD WASTE AND FOOD LOSS PHENOMENON – NEW SYSTEMIC APPROACHES

C. S. IORGA^{1,2}, O. M. DUMITRU^{1*}, A. STOICA³, C. M. NICOLESCU^{3,4}

¹National Institute of Research and Development for Food Bioresources – IBA Bucharest, 5, Baneasa Ancuta street, District 2, 02033, Bucharest

²University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, 59 Mărăști Boulevard, District 1, Bucharest, 011464, Phone: +40 (21) 318 25 64, Fax: +40 (21) 318 28 88,

³Valahia University of Targoviste, Faculty of Environmental Engineering and Food Science, 13, Aleea Sinaia, 130004 Targoviste, Romania

⁴Valahia University of Targoviste, Institute of Multidisciplinary Research for Science and Technology, Targoviste, Romania, 13, Aleea Sinaia, 130004 Targoviste, Romania

*Corresponding author: [oanamniculae@yahoo.com](mailto: oanamniculae@yahoo.com)

Abstract: Food waste is one of the main challenges of modern society. It's economic, environmental and social implications generates major research efforts among all categories of scientists, from natural sciences to economy ethics. Thus, a wide range of research approaches targeting this phenomenon were recorded: system impact analyses, economic assessments, ethical aspects related to food security, economic sustainability or technological approach tackles in reducing food waste and loss. The present communication is an original contribution to consolidation of state of art in the food waste and loss research, and it presents a systematic study from the perspective of main approaches used in timeframe of 10 years, from 2007 to 2017, and 80 peer reviewed articles published in this period were analyzed in detail. It was found that five main approaches were adopted by research on addressed topic, and they were highlighted in this paper

Keywords: food waste, food loss, circular economy, biovalorisation, systemic analysis

1. Introduction

Food waste is a major concern of modern society, Romania is among the countries aiming to adopt circular economy principles, with a view to protect, preserve and improve the quality of environment, to protect human health, as well as to ensure an efficient and rational utilization of resources. Thus, understanding the various perspectives adopted by the research activities on the topic of food waste and loss, together with conclusions drawn by research studies in the field are of a major importance in setting up procedures on food wastes management at all levels, both local communities an national level. The international context as described by international organisms in the field (FAO, etc) is that food wastes /loss is considered as a large phenomenon, likely to affect food security worldwide. Even if access to food sources has grown, a high malnutrition level exists at global level. On one hand, generation of food wastage does not have always the same causes. Food may be lost either during production, or because of

inadequate consumption, and also because of inappropriate marketing strategies and legislation. On the other hand, causes of food loss may be different depending on: the level in the food supply chain where occurs, the type of product, the geographical place, etc. It was observed that different behaviors adopted in each sector of the food chain may lead to elimination of edible foods in the harvest and storage phases, or by transporting in inappropriate conditions, or by mistakes in labeling, as well as by bad habits of the final consumers [1,2]. It was considered that consumer behavior has a major impact on the global phenomenon [3].

The aim of this study was to contribute to consolidation of state of art in the field of food waste and food loss research, by analyzing the various approaches adopted by scientists and conclusions that may be drawn from the work that was done. This short communication paper is a first part of the conclusions drawn from our study, further data will be presented in a different paper.

2. Methods

The bibliometric part of our study considered research peer reviewed publications on the topic of food waste and food loss, in a time frame of 10 years, between 2007 and 2017, and are visible in ISI Web of Science adopted as source of data. Searching keywords used were “food waste”, “food loss”, “food waste management”. A number of 80 selected articles were analyzed in detail from the perspective considered in the aim of the study.

3. Results and discussions

Food waste is a phenomenon with profound implications in modern society and not only; it has ethical, political, economic and environmental impacts [4-7]. In the current context of the global interdependencies of the food chain, globalization of the economic interests of primary production and food processing, food waste raises food security issues which creates a constant pressure on food flows to the high buying power markets, rather than to poor markets. The lack of local, regional or global regulation negatively contributes to this general situation [8].

Synthesis regarding various approaches to the food waste and food loss phenomenon

The need to correlate the data packages related to the phenomenon of food waste as well as its control and prevention actions have generated a large number of synthetic researches. Some bibliometric researches revealed the existence of almost 2500 articles published between 1997 and 2014 [9]. Their distribution is widely spread, with a higher dynamic in time, and mostly generated from industrialized states or which have emerging economies. A prevalent area in the research studies is analysis of the efficiency of various methods for the evaluation of food waste related systems. C. Baldini and co-authors synthesized the environmental impact at the milk industry level by applying the *Life Cycle Analysis (LCA)* method [10]. They demonstrated the role of standardization in strengthening the regulatory role of the method, with an influence on the assessments on global warming, acidification, eutrophication and energy and resource consumption. A summary of the challenges which the LCA must answer in order to be successful is related to several aspects that are characteristic for the agricultural system. First of all, it is necessary to go beyond the simplistic logic that higher output per hectare is sufficient

to ensure increased ecological efficiency. Actually, despite that increased efficiency of land use appears to be a logical way to face the pressure of the use of agricultural lands for other purposes (*i.e.* for bioenergy), and also the pressure of urbanization and desertification, the current LCA method is incomplete and does not exhaustively evaluate some aspects that are essential for long-term sustainable food production. Also, the inherent variability of the agricultural systems is an element that affects the inventory assessment, impact assessment and interpretation. When compared to other sectors, food systems are more variable in both inventory of data and possible impacts, and this means that it requires a specific implementation methodology. This finding also suggests the need for specific guidelines for agricultural inventories, including the improvement of quality of the data available in LCA databases. The aforementioned variability and geographical specificity of food systems require the existence of clearly structured regionalized data sets that allow the LCA practitioner to adapt the data to specific case studies [11]. A distinct direction of synthesis is *correlation of data related to determinants identification methods and evaluation of the food waste impact*. K. L. Thyberg and co-authors systematized the influence of industrialization, of economic growth, urbanization and globalization, as well as of cultural and socio-demographic factors, all in the context of the policies that are determinants of food waste and food loss. Last but not least, the authors identified behavioral patterns that generate food waste at the household, institutional or commercial level [12, 13]. A synthetic analysis of eight methods applied for investigating the environmental impact showed that the production link of the food chain plays a decisive role in reducing waste. Also, a significant influence was assigned to the transportation and processing at the household level, in relation with the small quantities of food involved in each stage [14]. The approach of *waste prevention* was considered for research. Thus, a synthesis performed at the level of European countries indicates that rather communication measures, with low costs, have been taken: awareness campaigns, seminars, networks or information platforms. The more efficient measures, such as eliminating food subsidies or introducing a significant taxation on

food waste processing, are not yet undertaken by EU member states governments [15].

Product packaging was considered to play an important role in the dynamics of food losses generation. The new methods of intelligent packaging have a positive influence on both the environment and the availability of products and consumer behavior [16, 17].

Food loss recovery was considered as approach in a wide number of research studies. Thus, various methods of food loss recovery have been systematized, analyzing the role of community in the selective collection of waste [18-21]. Technological interconnection with parallel production of bio-fuels and other bio-active products has been revealed as the preferred strategy in maximizing the recovery of food waste, in relation to their use for animal feed or to redistribution of the surplus to food banks [22-24]. A distinct research direction is aimed at the anaerobic biodegradation of food waste with the scope of energy generation. A review made on 173 articles showed that intensive research has been performed in 2017 on the process influence on the co-substrate, on the environment, and also in relation with and evaluation of the specific costs involved [25]. Significant reviews refer to the results of the research regarding processing of waste with the scope to obtain lactic acid [26], [27]. Numerous research studies target the residues in the meat industry [28, 29]. Bio-vanillin is one of the specific products intensively researched. A synthesis of 108 articles brought together the contributions in this field [30]. In bakery industry, some directions in relation to the functionality of various ingredients to increase the nutritional value of the products have been explored, and the effect in reducing the risk of waste has been demonstrated [31,32].

System analysis at the food chain level

An OECD analysis took into consideration available data on food waste and evaluated the policies related to this phenomenon at the level of member countries [1]. Authors proposed a hierarchy of food waste management options and related actions. The form of a pyramid was proposed, at its base the most environmental and economic friendly actions were included, and while at its top actions with the higher environmental and economic impact were indicated. The first and most important actions are to use the surplus as food products, together with actions to reduce and prevent direct food loss. Next priority options recommended are

related to food waste recovery by actions like feeding hungry people, donating fresh, wholesome food to people in need. Next priority option was to use food waste to safely feeding of animals (*i.e.* pig farms) or to produce animal food products. The last two options in food waste use would be industrial uses (*i.e.* rendering fats, oils, and grease and turning it into products or energy), and disposal (end-of-life treatment with no valorization). A similar analysis was proposed by E. Papargyropoulou [33], and also by other research scientists [34]. They systematized data collected from 31 countries reported by Eurostat, finding that Netherlands and USA have the highest transparency in publishing data related to food loss and waste. By the contrary, China, Australia, Mexico and Iceland appear to have the smallest public database on this phenomenon. The authors also propose models of good practice in political actions to reduce food waste and to enhance product recycling, presenting the example of the Republic of Korea. Food waste was also analyzed as an effect of social relations and assuming the principle that in current economies, the flow of value induces a parallel flow of loss [35]. The limitation of waste cannot be obtained by technical innovation only, but by integrated innovation, in other words by its insertion in the socio-administrative level [36, 37]. The social dimensions of the food waste phenomenon are increasingly considered for the sociological studies, and from a wide variety of perspectives [2]. Thus, the approaches considered are related to food security [38-41], ethics [42], ethnographic [43], behavioural theory [44], socio-political environment [45,46] or socio-environmental aspects [47,48].

The aim of reducing the food waste together with the need of integrated policies throughout the food chain were highlighted in correlation with the health status [49]. The authors propose an integrated iterative method in four steps: highlighting, analysis, visualization and dissemination of data at the level of the whole agro-food chain. Quantitative analyzes are based on the analysis of the life cycle of resources and their approach proposes several paths of breaking down the barriers at the organizational level. The model of life cycle assessment (LCA) as a method of evaluation of food waste leads to defining of some critical categories of wastes: *avoidable*, *potentially avoidable* and *inevitable loss* [50]. Authors' analysis includes food over-consumption aspects, and also differences related

to the waste generated by the poor quality of the products existing on the market. An analysis of strategies at the level of food processing is considered to have a certain influence on the behaviour of consumers, and this reveals the interactions that exist between the links of the food chain [51]. The life cycle assessment (LCA) method was applied for comparative evaluation of the sustainability of some systems of production and distribution of endives in northern Italy, with focus on food loss aspects [10, 52]. Also, life cycle assessment was implemented to evaluate the impact of food waste on the environment [53, 54]. The agro-food domain may be analyzed as a system, with its own resistance to change. This resistance can be seen in a holistic manner, integrating all the component sub-systems, including the social, economic, and biophysical and at all the scales where these sub-systems operate [55]. Evaluation of the environmental impact induced by the so called daily basket of food consumption shows that meat and dairy products have the highest contribution [11]. The impact assessments of food waste may have economic dimensions. Thus, the loss on the United States vegetable retail market were evaluated to \$ 42.8 billion [56]. In South Africa, the loss in 2012 was in the range 7.14 - 7.7 billion US dollars [57, 58]. Another important dimension is the environmental impact. One of the methods used for evaluation by research groups took into consideration the effect on the carbon footprint [59]. A parallel study of waste minimization solutions in France and United States highlighted the efficiency of the applied solutions, concluding that the most important actions are those related to waste prevention [60]. Another analysis was performed at the level of agricultural producers, traders, processors and retailers in Switzerland, and took into account 22 food products types. The study showed that approximately one third of the calories produced for consumption are lost at the level of the whole food chain. Also, this study reconfirms the final consumer as a determinant in the food waste generation [61]. Some other studies were performed from the same perspective, and revealed that a significant role may be assigned to an efficient preservation / refrigeration methods [62-64], as well as various packaging systems [65, 66]. The retail system is the subject of many impact studies on food waste [67-69]. Its distribution weight in the total volume of food

wastes leads to the concentration of the impact of this chain link, for both developed and developing countries [70]. A new concept of social value of the food waste recoveries was proposed, and that is the estimation of the number of food portions that can be obtained from these [71]. Another sector intensely analyzed is that of restaurants, canteens and fast food chains [72-77]. The integrated analysis of the link between food waste and catering practices in restaurants in Wales reveals a higher degree of waste than that reported by authorities [78]. The avoidable loss of food in the restaurants of the two existing categories (business and education) in Switzerland reveal as main causes of wastage the portion size or a reduced appetite when serving the meal [79]. The analysis of the impact of the usual menu in the student canteens of Mc Gill University in Montreal revealed that the chicken or egg meat dishes have a similar impact to the vegetable ones. Beef and cheese diets have a great impact on the environment. Furthermore, vegetarian diets that replace meat with cheese seem to have a negative environmental impact [80].

Conclusions

A significant number of approaches were adopted by scientists acting in the field of food waste and food loss, and five of these were found to be main alternatives of scientists that published in the studied time frame of 10 years (2007 – 2017): system evaluation procedures, correlation of determinants identification with environmental impact, prevention actions, packaging methods, and recovery processes. Both the perspective of food waste/loss as a global phenomenon, and that of specific food chain analysis were adopted in present study.

References

1. Bagherzadeh M., *et al.*, *Food Waste Along the Food Chain*, OECD Food, Agric. and Fisheries, ISSN:1815-6797;
2. Evans D., Campbell H., Murcott A., *A Brief Pre-History of Food Waste and the Social Sciences*, *The Sociological Review*, **60** no.2, 2012, p.5;
3. Secondi L., Principato L., Laureti T., *Household food waste behaviour in EU-27 countries: A multilevel analysis*, *Food Policy* **56**, 2015, p. 25;
4. Salemdeeb R., Vivanco D.F., *et al.*, *A holistic approach to the environmental evaluation of*

- food waste prevention*, Waste Manag. **59**, 2017, p. 442;
5. Morgan K., *The moral economy on food*, Geoforum **65**, 2015, p. 294;
 6. Grote U., *Can we improve global food security? A socio-economic and political perspective*, Food Security **6**, 2014, p.187;
 7. Lucifero N., *Food Loss and Waste in the EU Law between Sustainability of Well-being and the Implications on Food System and on Environment*, Agriculture and Agricultural Science Procedia **8**, 2016, p. 282;
 8. Cloke J., *Empires of Waste and the Food Security Meme*, Geography Compass **7**, no. 9, 2013, p. 622;
 9. Chen H., Yang Y., Yang Y., Man X., *State of the art on food waste research: a bibliometrics study from 1997 to 2014*, J. of Cleaner Production **140**, no.2, 2017, p. 840;
 10. Baldini C., Gardoni D., Guarino M., *A critical review of the recent evolution of Life Cycle Assessment applied to milk production*, J. of Cleaner Product **140**, no.2, 2017, p. 421;
 11. Notarnicola B., Sala S., et al., *The role of life cycle assessment in supporting sustainable agri-food systems: A review of the challenges*, Journal of Cleaner Production **140**, no. 2, 2017, p. 399;
 12. Raak N., Symmank C., et al., *Processing- and product-related causes for food waste and implications for the food supply chain*, Waste Management **61**, 2017, p.461;
 13. Thyberg K.L., Tonjes D.J., *Drivers of food waste and their implications for sustainable policy development*, Resources, Conservation and Recycling **106**, 2016, p. 110;
 14. Schott A.B.S, Cánovas A.A., *Current practice, challenges and potential methodological improvements in envirom. evaluations of food waste prevention*, Resources, Conserv. and Recycling **101**, 2015, p. 132;
 15. Priefer C., Jörissen J., Bräutigam K-R., *Food waste prevention in Eu. – A cause-driven approach to identify the most relevant leverage points for action*, Resources, Conserv. and Recycling **109**, 2016, p. 155;
 16. Marsh K., Bugusu B., *Food Packaging—Roles, Materials, and Environmental Issues*, J. of Food Science **72**, no.3, 2007, p. R39;
 17. Mlalila N., Kadam D., Swai H., Hilonga A., *Transformation of food packaging from passive to innovative via nanotechnology: concepts and critiques*, J. of Food Science and Technology **53**, no. 9, 2016, p. 3395;
 18. Wyngaard A.T., De Lange R., *The effectiveness of implementing eco initiatives to recycle water and food waste in selected Cape Town hotels*, International Journal of Hospitality Management **34**, 2013, p.309;
 19. Pirani S.I., Arafat H.A., *Solid waste management in the hospitality: A review*, J. of Cleaner Production **146**, 2014, p. 320;
 20. Giroto F., Alibardi L., Cossu R., *Food waste generation and industrial uses: A review*, Waste Management **45**, 2015, p. 32;
 21. Ravindran R., Jaiswal A.K., *Exploitation of Food Industry Waste for High-Value Products*, Trends in Biotechnology **34**, no. 1, 2016, p. 58;
 22. Mirabella N., Castellani V., Sala S., *Current options for the valorization of food manufacturing waste: a review*, J. of Cleaner Production **65**, 2014, p. 28;
 23. Dhillon G.S., Kaur S., Brar S.K., *Perspective of apple processing wastes as low-cost substrates for bioproduction of high value products: A review*, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews **27**, 2013, p. 789
 24. Matharu A.S., De Melo E.M., Houghton J.A., *Opportunity for high value-added chemicals from food supply chain wastes*, Bioresources Technology **2115**. 2016, p. 123;
 25. Paritosh K., Kushwaha S.K., Yadav M., Pareek N., Chawade A., Vivekanand V., *Food Waste to Energy: An Overview of Sustainable Approaches for Food Waste Management and Nutrient Recycling*, BioMed Research International 2017:2370927;
 26. Panesar P.S., et al., *Bioutilisation of whey for lactic acid production*, Food Chem. **105**, no.1, 2007, p.1;
 27. Panesar P.S., Kaur, S., *Bioutilisation of agro-industrial waste for lactic acid production*, International Journal of Food Science and Technology, **50**, no. 10, 2015, p. 2143;
 28. Franke-Whittle I. H., Insam H., *Treatment alternatives of slaughterhouse wastes, and their effect on the inactivation of different pathogens: a review*, Critical Reviews in Microbiology, 39, no.2, 2013, p.139;
 29. Jayathilakan K., et al., *Utilization of byproducts and waste materials from meat, poultry and fish processing industries: a review*, Journal of Food Science and Technology **49**, no. 3, 2012, p. 278;

30. Zamzuri N.A., Suraini A.A., *Biovanillin from agro wastes as an alternative food flavour*, Journal of Science of Food and Agriculture **93**, no. 3, 2013, p. 429;
31. Rawat N., Indrani D., *Functional Ingredients of Wheat-Based Bakery, Traditional, Pasta, and Other Food Products*, Food Reviews International **31**, no. 2, 2015, p. 125;
32. Villarino B.J., Jyasena V., Coorey R., Johnson S.K., *Nutritional, Health, and Technological Functionality of Lupin Flour Addition to Bread and Other Baked Products: Benefits and Challenges*, Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition **56**,no.5,2016, p. 835;
33. Papargyropoulou E., *et al.*, *The food waste hierarchy as a framework for the management of food surplus and food waste*, J. of Cleaner Production **76**, 2014, p. 106;
34. Garcia-Garcia G., Woolley E., Rahimifard S., Colwill J., White R., Needham L., *A Methodology for Sustainable Management of Food Waste*, Waste and Biomass Valorization ISSN: 1877-2641 (Print) 1-19;
35. Gille Z., *From risk to waste: global food waste regimes*, The Sociological Review **60**, no.S2, 2012, p. 27;
36. Finn S.F., *Valuing our food: Minimizing waste and optimizing resources*, Zygon Journal of Religion & Science **49**, no. 4, 2014, p. 992;
37. Russ W., Schnappinger M., *Waste Related to the Food Industry: A Challenge in Material Loops*, © Springer Science+Business Media, LLC 2007;
38. Cloke J., *Food Security and Food Waste*, SpringerBriefs in Global Understanding Series, Eating, Drinking: Surviving part, 2016, p. 99;
39. Ortiz-Miranda D., Moreno-Pérez O.M., Alegre E.A., *Food and nutrition security discursive frames in the context of the Spanish economic crisis*, Food Security **8**, no.3, 2016, p. 665;
40. Modi A.T., *A simple model to evaluate integrated vegetable production for food security in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa*, Food Research Inter. **76**, no. 4, 2015, p. 946;
41. Ingram J.S.I., Wright H.L., Foster L., *et al.*, *Priority research questions for the UK food system*, Food Security **5**, 2013, p. 617;
42. Gjerris M., Gaiani S., *Food Waste and Consumer Ethics*, Encyclopedia of Food and Agricultural Ethics, Springer, 2014;
43. Goonan S., Miroso M., Spence H., *Getting a Taste for Food Waste: A Mixed Methods Ethnographic Study into Hospital Food Waste before Patient Consumption Conducted at Three New Zealand Foodservice Facilities*, J. of the Acad. of Nutr. and Dietetics **114**, no. 1, 2014, p. 63;
44. Ghani W.A.W.A.K., *et al.*, *An application of the theory of planned behaviour to study the influencing factors of participation in source separation of food waste*, Waste Management **33**, no. 5, 2013, p. 1276;
45. O'brien M., *A 'lasting transformation' of capitalist surplus: from food stocks to feedstocks*, The Sociological Review **60**, no. 2, 2012, p. 192;
46. Parfitt J., Barthel M., Macnaughton S., *Food Waste within Food Supply Chains: Quantification and Potential for Change to 2050*, Philosophical Transactions of The Royal Society B Biological Sciences **365**, 2010, p.3065;
47. Garrone P., Melacini M., Perego A., *Opening the black box of food waste reduction*, Food Policy **46**, 2014, p. 129;
48. Reutter B., Lant P, *et al.*, *Food waste consequences: Environmentally extended input-output as a framework for analysis*, J. of Cleaner Production **153**, 2017, p. 506;
49. Horton P., Koh L., Guang V.S., *An integrated theoretical framework to enhance resource efficiency, sustainability and human health in agro-food systems*, Journal of Cleaner Production **120**, 2016, p. 164;
50. Corado S., Ardente F., Sala S., Saouter E., *Modelling of food loss within life cycle assessment*, Journal of Cleaner Production **140**, 2017, p. 847;
51. Manzocco L., Alongi M., Sillani S., Nicoli M.C., *Technological and Consumer Strategies to Tackle Food Wasting*, Food Engineering Reviews **8**, 2016, p. 457;
52. Tasca A.L., Nessi S., Rigamonti L., *Environmental sustainability of agri-food supply chains: An LCA comparison between two alternative forms of production and distribution of endive in northern Italy*, J. of Cleaner Production **140**, no. 2, 2017, p. 725;
53. Sala S., Anton A., McLaren S.J., *et al.* *In quest of reducing the environmental impacts of food production and consumption*, J. of Cleaner Production **140**, 2017, p. 387;
54. Salemdeeb R., Zu Ermgassen E.K.H.J., *et al.*, *Environmental and health impacts of*

- using food waste as animal feed: a comparative analysis of food waste management options, *J. of Cleaner Prod.* **140**, no. 2, 2017, p. 871;
55. Tendall D.M., Joenin J., *et al.*, *Food system resilience: Defining the concept*, *Global Food Security* **6**, 2015, p. 17;
56. Buzby J.C., Hyman J., *et al.*, *The Value of Retail- and Consumer-Level Fruit and Vegetable Losses in the US*, *The J. of Consumer Affairs* **45**, no.3, 2011, p. 492;
57. De Lange W., Nahman A., *Costs of food waste in South Africa: Incorporating inedible food waste*, *Waste Manag.* **40**, 2015, p. 167;
58. Nahman A., De Lange W., Oelofse S., Godfrey L., *The costs of household food waste in South Africa*, *Waste Management* **32**, no. 11, 2012, p. 2147;
59. Oldfield T.L., White E., Holden N.M., *An environmental analysis of options for utilizing wasted food and food residue*, *J. of Envir. Manag.* **183**, 2016, p.826;
60. Mourad M., *Recycling, recovering and preventing "food waste": competing solutions for food systems sust. in the US. and France*, *J. of Cleaner Prod.* **126**, 2016, p. 461;
61. Beretta C., Stoessel F., Baier U., Hellweg S., *Quantifying food losses and the potential for reduction in Switzerland*, *Waste Management* **33**, no. 3, 2013, p.764;
62. Xu J.C., Mujumdar A.S., Adhikari B., *Recent developments in smart freezing techn. applied to fresh foods*, *Critical Reviews in Food Scie. and Nutr.* **57**, no.13, 2017, p.2835;
63. Waitt G., Phillips C., *Food waste and domestic refrigeration: a visceral and material approach*, *Social & Cultural Geography* **17**, no. 3, 2016, p. 359;
64. Tromp S-O., Haijema R., *et al.*, *A systematic approach to preventing chilled-food waste at the retail outlet*, *Internat. J. of Production Economics* **182**, 2016, p. 508;
65. Verghese K., Lewis H., Lockrey S., Williams H., *Packaging's Role in Minim. Food Loss and Waste Across the Supply Chain*, *Pack. Techn. and Sci.* **28**, no.7, 2015, p. 603;
66. Hanssen O.J., Vold M., Schakenda V., *et al.*, *Environmental profile, packaging intensity and food waste generation for three types of dinner meals*, *J. of Cleaner Production* **142**, no.1, 2017, p. 395;
67. Scholz K., Eriksson M., Strid I., *Carbon footprint of supermarket food waste*, *Res., Conserv. and Recycl.* **94**, 2015, p.56;
68. Lebersorger S., Schneider F., *Food loss rates at food retail, influencing factors and reasons as a basis for waste prev. measures*, *Waste Manag.* **34**, no.11, 2014, p. 1911;
69. Lee D., Tongaralak W., *Converting retail food waste into by-product*, *Eu. J. of Operational Research* **257**, no. 3, 2017, p. 944;
70. Calvo-Porrall C., Faina A., Lopez C.L., *Can Marketing Help in Tackling Food Waste?: Proposals in Developed Countries*, *Food Products Marketing* **23**, no.1, 2017, p. 42;
71. Cicatiello C., Franco S., *et al.*, *The value of food waste: An exploratory study on retailing*, *J. of Retailing and Consumer Services* **30**, 2016, p. 96;
72. Duursma G., Vrengoor F., Kobus S., *Food waste reduction at Restaurant De Pleats: Small steps for mankind*, *Research in Hospitality Manag.* **6**, no. 1, 2016, p. 95;
73. Goonan S., Miroso M., Spence H., *Systems-practice framework: An integrated approach for foodservice management*, *Nutrition & Dietetics* **72**, no. 1, 2015, p. 81;
74. Dias-Ferreira C., Santos T., Oliveira V., *Hospital food waste and environmental and economic indicators – A Portuguese case study*, *Waste Manag.* **46**, 2015, p.146;
75. Silvennoinen K., Katajajuuri J.M., *et al.*, *Food waste volume and origin: Case studies in the Finnish food service sector*, *Waste Manag.* **46**, 2015, p. 140;
76. Papargyropoulou E., Wright N., Lozano R., *et al.* *Conceptual framework for the study of food waste generation and prevention in hospitality*, *Waste Manag.* **49**, 2016, p. 326;
77. Pirani S.I., Arafat H.A., *Reduction of food waste generation in the hospitality industry*, *J. of Cleaner Production* **132**, 2016, p. 129;
78. Sonnino R., McWilliams S., *Food waste, catering practices and public procurement: A case study of hospital food systems in Wales*, *Food Policy* **36**, no. 6, 2011, p. 823;
79. Betz A., Buchli J., Göbel C., Müller C., *Food waste in the Swiss food service industry – Magnitude and potential for reduction*, *Waste Manag.* **35**, 2015, p. 218;
80. Chen D.M., Tucker B., Badami M.G., *et al.* *A multi-dimensional metric for facilitating sustainable food choices in campus cafeterias*, *J. of Cleaner Production* **135**, 2016, p. 1351.

FOOD SAFETY FOR MOUNTAIN PRODUCTS – STRATEGIES, POLICIES, ACTORS

L. GACEU^{1,2,*}

¹ Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania, Faculty of Food and Tourism Brasov, Castelului street no. 148, Tel / Fax: 0268 472222

² CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy;

*Corresponding author: gaceul@unitbv.ro

Abstract: This European countries operate excellent research infrastructures and are leading in many fields concerning climate, ecosystems, life in extreme environments, pollution monitoring and other aspects.

Food safety of the mountain products consist an important issue, with many connection in the area of: human resources in production and management; specific equipment; high variability of raw materials and finished products; limited resources for utilities, materials and accessories; waste management. The paper present the context, a new strategy for solving this issue, identifying the main actors and the policies need to be used.

Making the most efficient use of mountain bioresources and the latest scientific developments for addressing the abovementioned challenges, while contributing to climate change mitigation efforts targeted at this specific ecosystem, requires a high degree of coordination within Europe and beyond.

Keywords: food safety, mountain products, bioresources;

1. Introduction

European mountain regions play a central role for the well-being of many highly populated European regions for instance for water and energy supply, weather regimes, recreation and tourism. European mountain regions are home to a high degree of biodiversity, including many endemic species that occur nowhere else. However, mountain regions are expected to react far more sensitively to global change than other parts of the world. Therefore, research on sustainability of these regions is important not only for the population living there and the many tourists visiting them (e.g. 150 Millions/year for the Alps) but for a significant part of Europe's population [5, 7, 10].

The paper proposes strategies for the efficient use of genetic resources in the mountain area for increasing the sanitary hygienic quality of the mountain product, by designing safe food technologies in small, local processing units.

The hygienic-sanitary quality of the mountain product is an increasingly addressed topic in the specialized literature, due to the variability of the factors involved, starting from the human resources, the diversity of raw materials, of final products, networks and

technologies, etc. and a certain resource is limited in terms of personnel, utilities, materials and accessories, etc [2].

The concept of food safety is well-grounded and successfully applied to high-capacity food technology flows, events that endanger the health of the consumer, constituting single cases during the last decade.

However, in small production units in the mountain area, which often process local raw materials in order to obtain traditional foods, the classical approach to the concept of food safety present many difficulties, due to aspects such as [3, 12]:

- Lack of training of personnel in production and management;
- Equipment not designed hygienically, difficult to clean and hygienized;
- High variability of raw materials and finished products;
- Limited resources for utilities, materials and accessories;
- Waste management.

The main aims is to develop clear, simple and efficient solutions to ensure the hygienic quality of sanitary products of the mountain products

produced in local production micro-units, in the following directions [13]:

- Studies Special sources of contamination in the mountain area
- Factory Design, including Design of Utility Systems
- Liquid Food Processing
- Dry Particulate Materials Processing
- Equipment for open processing (Belt Conveyors for the Food Industry; Hygienic Design Requirements for Processing of Fresh Fish)
- Packaging Filling of Food Products
- Heat Treatment
- Food Refrigeration & depository
- Cleaning & Disinfection
- Waste management

2. Relevant policies

The legal requirements for the food industry, respectively in “mountain product” are described generally in the Codex Alimentarius, in the European Legislation on Hygienic Regulations and in the Machinery Directive [1, 6].

There are several EU-regulations dealing with hygiene aspects, but mostly with food safety :

REGULATION (EC) No 852/2004
 REGULATION (EC) No 853/2004;
 REGULATION (EC) No 854/2004. These are called also „Hygiene package“ [14].

At world level there are currently 3 categories of standards and recommendations that ensure food safety implementation:

- European Hygienic Engineering and Design Group (EHEDG) (www.ehedg.org) (Guidelines, seminars and certification of equipment and components)
- 3-A Sanitary Standards (USA, www.3-a.org) (Guidelines and certification of equipment and components)
- NSF National Sanitation Foundation (www.nsf.org) (Certification of equipment and components)

Nevertheless, solving the problem of “mountain product” food safety requires advanced knowledge about how handling, preparation processing and packaging of food is done hygienically, using hygienic machinery and in hygienic premises according to the food hygiene directive, the machinery directive and the food contact materials directive (EC Directive 2006/42/EC for Machinery, EN 1672-2 and EN ISO 14159 on Hygiene requirements for the design of machinery).

Fig. 1. Connection between Machinery risk assessment and Product risk assesment

As can be seen in the figure above, between the (mountain) product quality and equipment quality there is a close connection, and the

responsible for the product quality and has to follow the corresponding regulations, as well as standards and publications according to the state

of the art for the entire process area, for the production, the product, the personnel and the cleaning [13].

3. Actor mapping

In order to successfully implement food security policies existing at European level, in the case of mountain processed products in small capacity local units, it is imperative an approach to provide adequate technical solutions to the management and production personnel in the mountain area. At European level, useful in this area there are two main directions:

- construction of modular factories that can be operated by a small number of workers low level;
- design of equipment that can be easily cleaned and sanitized.

The construction of modular factories has grown in the last decade, with multiple applications, from breweries, dairy or meat products, canned fruits and vegetables, etc. renowned producers such as: Baroncini, Czech Mini Breweries, etc., offering solutions that work with success in the hill and plain areas.

For use in the mountain area, where access to human, material and energy resources is limited, the technical solutions provided by the current modular factories must be improved by implementing the concept of "hygienic design" so that all the equipment existing in these modular factories, as well as the entire factory to be designed and executed based on this concept.

"European Hygienic Engineering and Design Group" currently owns the entire portfolio of knowledge required for the application of accredited technical solutions, in order to ensure food security worldwide and at European level. The main goal of EHEDG is the promotion of safe food by improving hygienic engineering and design in all aspects of food manufacturing.

EHEDG has approximately 60 representatives in countries in Europe and worldwide, including Romania. Together with the veterinary health departments in each region and the suppliers of modular plant solutions, a consortium should be built in order to provide:

- a technical solution for the "modular mountain factory" on product type;
- revision of the specific legislation according to the requirements of the new type of mountain production unit [9].

Human resource need to be trained in order to apply the concept of hygienic design [4, 8, 11]. Each training module should be based on a

respective EHEDG guideline, some of which can be assembled together to establish a comprehensive training course with a particular focus. Each module contains a list of key learning points to assure the effective and uniform knowledge sharing of the EHEDG hygienic design principles with the training course participants. The main module contains:

- Legal requirements
- Hazards in hygienic processing
- Hygienic design criteria
- Materials of construction
- Welding stainless steel
- Static seals and couplings
- Valves
- Pumps and Homogenizers
- Cleaning and disinfection
- Building and process lay out
- Installation, maintenance and Lubricants
- Hygienic design criteria for equipment processing dry materials
- Verification of HD. Test methods and Certification
- Hygienic Design aspects of typical components such as: Sensors, Packaging machines
- Process aspects such as: Rheology, Thermodynamics, Aseptic processes

Conclusions

Development of clear, simple and efficient solutions to ensure the sanitary quality of the mountain products can be easily achieved through modular factories re(designed) in the spirit of "hygienic design". This technical solution also produces a minimum of technological waste and technological water, also simplifying the management of such micro-unit productions.

The main actors that should be involved are: local food safety agencies, the main local producers, the modular factories producers, different research units.

References

1. Bowen, S. and K. d. Master (2011). "New rural livelihoods or museums of production? Quality food initiatives in practice." *Journal of Rural Studies* n°27: pp.73-82;
2. Fabien Santini, Fatmir Guri, Sergio Gomez y Paloma, Labelling of agricultural and food products of mountain farming , Report EUR 25768 EN, 2013

- https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/food-farming-fisheries/food_safety_and_quality/documents/jrc-report-labelling-mountain-farming-products_2013_en.pdf;
3. Gordon, A., Case study: food safety and quality systems implementation in small beverage operations—Mountain Top Springs Limited, Food Safety and Quality Systems in Developing Countries, Volume 2, Case Studies of Effective Implementation, 2017, Pages 81-116. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780128012260000049>;
 4. Guri, F., F. Santini, et al. (forthcoming). Agriculture on mountain areas. JRC Scientific and technical reports. JRC. Seville, IPTS-JRC;
 5. Holloway, L., R. Cox, et al. (2006). "Managing sustainable farmed landscape through 'alternative' food networks: a case study from Italy " The geographical journal 172(3): 11;
 6. Macdonald, D., J. R. Crabtree, et al. (2000). "Agriculture abandonment in mountain areas of Europe: environmental consequences and policy response." Journal of Environmental Management (59): 13;
 7. Meiberger, E. and M. Weichbold (2010). How can mountain quality food reduce the vulnerability of mountain farming systems? 9th European IFSA Symposium. Vienna (Austria): 1626-1635;
 8. Nordregio (2004). Mountain areas in Europe : analysis of mountain areas in EU Member States, acceding and other European countries. Final report. E. C. c. N. 2002.CE.16.0.AT.136;
 9. Pieniadz, A., J. H. Hanf, et al. (2009). Small farmers in the Romanian dairy market: Do they have a future? 111 EAAE-IAAE Seminar 'Small Farms: decline or persistence'. U. o. Kent. Canterbury, UK: 14;
 10. Schjøll, A., V. Amilien, et al. (2010). Promotion of mountain food: An explorative a study about consumers' and retailers' perception in six European countries. 9th European IFSA Symposium. IFSA. Vienna (Austria): 1558-1567;
 11. Tasser, E. and U. Tappeiner (2002). "The impact of land-use changes in time and space on vegetation distribution in mountain areas." Applied Vegetation Science 5(173-184);
 12. *** Mapping the vulnerability of mountain peoples to food insecurity, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations Rome, 2015, <http://www.fao.org/3/a-i5175e.pdf>
 13. *** <https://ehedg.org>
 14. *** https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_hygiene/legislation_en

OPTIMIZATION OF IMAGE ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES FOR QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF WHEAT BREAD WITH GRAPE SEED FLOUR SUBSTITUTION

O. B. OPREA^{1*}, L. GACEU^{1,2}

¹ Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania, Faculty of Food and Tourism Brasov, str. Castelului no. 148
Tel / Fax: 0268 472222

²CSCBAS & CE-MONT Centre / INCE - Romanian Academy;

*Corresponding author: oprea.oana.bianca@unitbv.ro

Abstract: This paper presents a new approach about the color of wheat bread crumb with grape seed flour (GSF) substitution. This is an important contribution to the assessment of bread quality, that can be quantified by image analysis of color. This paper analyze the bread slice images in order to quantify the differences in crumb color of bread products made with different substitution percentages of grape seed flour. Comparative analysis of the results achieved with ImageJ algorithms showed a significant difference between the studied parameters.

Keywords: GSF, grape seeds, CIELab, ImageJ.

1. Introduction

The crumb color of cereal-based products, such as bakery products, is an important contributing factor to their textural properties [8] and to the determination and quantification of sensory quality [1, 2]. Therefore, knowledge of the color of breads may help predict many of the quality properties [1, 2], particularly in wheat bread crumb with grape seed flour (GSF) substitution, which are known to be less appealing to consumers in terms of quality than are breads made with simple wheat flour.

Furthermore, the color elements of food products such as bread, starch, fruits and vegetables can be quantified by image analysis [3-7], contributing to the understanding of quality-related properties such as texture.

In the search for improved bread formulations, image processing is a useful tool to

investigate, approximate and predict many properties, such as color [5, 7], by assessing cell size, cell size distribution, number of cells per unit area, cell wall thickness, void fraction and shape factor [3, 4].

The paper takes into consideration case study of wheat bread with grape seed flour substitution (0%, 5%, 10%, 15%).

2. Materials, equipments and research methodology

2.1. Materials

Three types of mixtures of 650 type wheat flour and different proportions of defatted grapes seed flour were obtained, in the following ratios: 95:5, 90:10, and 85:15 (w/w). The types of flour mixtures used in this study are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Types of mixtures of flours used in this study

Category	Mixtures of flours	
	Wheat type 650	Grapes seed flour
P0	100%	-
P1	95%	5%
P2	90%	10%
P3	85%	15%

2.2. Equipments

The technological flow used for experimental research was bought by NOVA PAN company, Brasov, Romania and consist from the following equipments:

1. Flour sieve, type SF100 equipped with magnetic impurity retention system of metallic nature - Capacity: 100kg/h, Installed electric power: 0,37 kw;
2. Mixer with fixed tank, type SILVER 50 - Capacity: 60 l, Installed electric power: 4,60 kw;
3. Hydraulic divider type SQ 20 - Capacity: 10 pcs / batch, Installed electric power: 1,50 kw;
4. Round modeler with conical outer surface - Capacity: 500 pcs/h, Installed electric power: 0,48 kw;
5. Modeling machine in long format, Installed electric power: 0.75 kw;
6. Fermenter, type TELBO, Installed electric power: 6,80 kw;
7. Oven with ring tubes 6 6 sqm, type MiniStar MSR4C - Capacity: 6 mp: 90 buc 450 gr, Installed electric power: 1,50 kw;
 - Baking cycle (loading, baking time and unloading): 25minutes;
 - Hourly capacity: 225 pcs of 350 g;
 - 8 hour exchange capacity: 1.680 pcs of 350 g ;
 - Capacity in kg of 1 work shift of 8 hours: 590 kg.

2.3. Research methodology

2.3.1. Image acquisition

All types of the analyzed bread products were sliced in 4 to 6 pieces after complete cooling and scanned with scanner HP Scanjet. From each slice a representative area 40mm x 50mm were cropped and later analyzed using ImageJ software.

2.3.2. RGB Color Histogram

For analyzing the color histogram, it was used the plugin *Color Histogram* [9], author Dimiter Prodanov, from Netherland. After installing the plugin a new "Color Histogram" command appears in the Analyze/Tools submenu. The plugin generates a color histogram of RGB images.

2.3.3. Conversion RGB to CIELab

For conversion RGB to CIELab, it was used the plugin „Color Space Converter” [10], author Duane Schwartzwald. After installing the plugin there will be a new *Color Space Converter* command in the Plugins menu or submenu. The plugin generates a color histogram of RGB images. This plugin converts between any combination of RGB, HSB, LAB and XYZ, possibly modifying the image in place.

The HSB conversions use the java Color class. All others rely on code that converts to XYZ and then on to something else. The RGB to XYZ conversion assumes sRGB as input (with it's D65 white point). Pretty standard, should give decent results in most cases.

The RGB to L*a*b* conversion assumes sRGB for conversion to XYZ but then uses the specified white point to convert from XYZ to L*a*b*.

All in-place output is scaled and placed in the RGB image. HSB is normally 0..1, L*a*b* is normally 0..100, -100..100, -100..100 and XYZ is normally 0..100, 0..100, 0..100.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Crumb color evaluation

Figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 show the scanned slices in RGB format, for P0 (control test bread), P1, P2 and P3, and table 2 presents the RGB and CIELab mean values for P0, P1, P2 and P3 bread samples.

Fig. 1. P0 control test bread sample (picture and RGB histogram)

Fig.2. P1, bread samples with 5% GSF substitution (picture and RGB histogram)

Fig.3. P2, bread samples with 10% GSF substitution (picture and RGB histogram)

Fig.4. P3, bread samples with 15% GSF substitution (picture and RGB histogram)

Table 2. The RGB and CIELab mean values for all 4 analyzed bread samples

Samples / Color parameters	RGB			CIELab		
	R	G	B	L*	a*	b*
P0	241.947	223.819	178.356	89.522	-0.558	24.602
P1	168.437	135.505	112.862	58.851	9.322	16.932
P2	158.885	124.942	105.645	54.902	10.458	15.545
P3	144.270	11.822	99.700	49.723	11.168	11.600

Figures 5, 6, 7 and 8 show 3 pictures (only L*, a*, b* components) for each of the P0, P1, P2 and P3 slices.

Fig. 5. P0 control test bread sample – L*, a*, b* components

Fig.6. P1, bread samples with 5% GSF substitution – L^* , a^* , b^* components

Fig.7. P2, bread samples with 10% GSF substitution – L^* , a^* , b^* components

Fig.8. P3, bread samples with 15% GSF substitution – L^* , a^* , b^* components

Conclusions

Comparison of the color of wheat bread crumb with grape seed flour substitution is a necessary action for evaluation of quality parameters and can predict information about consumer acceptance.

Also, the results of image analysis with the ImageJ software can be used to predict different properties of the bread (with the help of „Color Histogram” and „Color Space Converter” plugins).

Future research will provide a more reliable representation of the crumb structure of bread sample, in order to represent the crumb texture.

References

1. Collar, C., Santos, E., & Rosell, C. M. (2007). Assesment of the rheological profile of fibre-enriched Bread doughs by response surface methodology. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 78(3), 820-826;
2. Dubois, D. K. (1978). Practical application of fibre materials in bread production. *The Bakers Digest*, 52(2), 30-33;
3. Farrera-Rebollo, R. R., Salgado-Cruz, M. P., Chanona-Pérez, J., Gutiérrez- Lopes, G. F., Alamilla-Beltrán, L., & Calderón-Dominguez, G. (2012). Evaluation of image analysis tools for characterization of sweet bread crumb structure. *Food Bioprocess Technology*, 5(2), 474-484;
4. Herbert, A. (2014). *ImageJ colocalisation plugins*. *ImageJ*. Retrieved from <http://www.sussex.ac.uk/gdsc/intranet/pdfs/Colocalisation.pdf>;
5. Hruskova, M., Svec, I., Hofmanova, T., & Dvorakova, J. (2012). Image analysis – comparison of recipe composition effect. *Procedia Engineering*, 42, 955-963;
6. Sahoo, P. K., Soltani, S., & Wong, K. C. (1988). A survey of thresholding techniques. *Computer Vision Graphics and Image Processing*, 41(2), 233-260;
7. Scheuer, P.M., Ferreira, J. A.S., Mattioni B., Miranda, M. Z., et al., *Optimization of image analysis techniques for quality assessment of whole-wheat breads made with fat replacer*, *Food Science and Technology*, Campinas, 35(1): 133-142, Jan.-Mar. 2015, pp. 133-142;
8. Zghal, M. C., Scanlon, M. G., & Sapirstein, H. D. (1999). Prediction of bread crumb density by digital image analysis. *Cereal Chemistry*, 76(5), 734-742;
9. ***
<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/plugins/color-histogram.html>;
10. *** <https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/plugins/color-space-converter.html>.